

Deliverable 2.2

Report on overview of needs, barriers and enablers for policies and governance of EU food systems and FNS R&I

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Document History and Information

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2.0	14 April 2019	Added various classification elements (including governance), included FOOD 2030 priorities and challenges, improved descriptors of classification items, extension and cleaning of the database	Beatrice Biondi, Mario Mazzocchi, Chiara Pontillo
3.0	06 May 2019	Added definition of the governance variable, specification for unclear points in the report.	Beatrice Biondi, Mario Mazzocchi, Chiara Pontillo
3.1	06 May 2019	Added detailed explanation on how the charts were built (section 6)	

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1 Executive summary

- This report accompanies an electronic database of policies, which is provided separately as an Excel file that includes an up-to-date mapping of current EU and national food system-related policies.
- The deliverable is intended to serve the emerging transformative networks. Indeed, exchange with the FIT4FOOD2030 City and Policy Labs has taken place during the development of the database to improve its understandability and completeness.
- To the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt to compile a systematic database containing information on measures across the spectrum of food policy goals.
- Food policy is defined as *any government action that can affect the food system concerning production and its inputs, package, process, trade, retail and consumption, and the disposal of waste.*
- The collected policies are classified according to FOOD 2030 priorities and challenges, policy goals, targets (primary target and ultimate beneficiary), and instruments, plus two additional items related to governance, and links to relevant sources.
- The sources for the policy mapping were: (a) already existing collections (NOURISHING database, SCAR qualitative mapping); (b) governmental web-sites of EU member states; (c) web-site of the European Commission; (d) academic databases (Web of Science, Scopus, Google Scholar).
- The current database contains 460 policies (as of 20th of March 2019), of which 281 have been implemented at the Member State level and 179 at the EU level.
- The work has been comprehensive in scope (i.e. we ensured that some policy information is available for all goals, targets and instruments relevant to food and nutrition security policies).
- The best possible effort within the available resources has been done to cover all European policies, but there is no guarantee that all existing food policies implemented by Member States have been included.
- The last chapter of this report includes illustrative examples of data extractions from the database, in the form of «Policy Cards». Even though the Policy Cards go beyond the objectives of the deliverable and will be released as a separate document, they represent an extra output that could prove useful in understanding the content of the database and be used in the project for Lab activities as a facilitator tool to stimulate debate.

2 Introduction

This report accompanies an electronic database of policies, which is currently provided separately as an Excel file. The excel file provides an up-to-date mapping of current EU and national policies influencing the food system in Europe and how they relate to Food and Nutrition Security Research & Innovation (FNS R&I) policy implementation. The aim of this database goes beyond the mere listing of food policies and provides a classification of policies in terms of goals, targets and instruments, which represents an essential information to support the identification of gaps and priorities, and promote discussion within multisectoral or multimministerial collaboration efforts, like those established in the FIT4FOOD2030 Policy labs and City Labs.

A comprehensive mapping of food policies is, indeed, essential to highlight where national governments and European institutions need to take action to achieve health, environment, economic and social policy goals and, in particular, FOOD 2030 priorities and challenges. Its relevance lies in its potential to address current gaps and needs in food system measures and policy development, as well as to show progress in specific policy areas and sub-areas. Nevertheless, it is a complex exercise as policies exist at different implementation levels (local, regional, national, EU), their priorities evolve over time, and their scope and goal are not always explicit or univocal.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first attempt to compile a systematic database containing information on measures across the spectrum of food policy goals. It thus describes the results of an extensive effort to provide a first mapping of the current food policies implemented in Europe and propose a classification in terms of their goal and instruments.

The report is intended to serve the emerging transformative networks (i.e. the three instruments of the FOOD 2030 Platform, namely the EU Think Tank, Policy Labs and City Labs; policy makers at all territorial levels who are willing to develop a FNS R&I strategy; public and private researchers whose work is centred on food system's matters or relatable ones). To ensure its future exploitation, and in order to improve its usage and completeness, during the development of the database, exchange with the FIT4FOOD2030 City and Policy Labs has taken place.

Box 1: The three different structural elements of the FOOD 2030 Platform.

The three different structural elements of the FOOD 2030 Platform that have been established by the FIT4FOOD2030 project are the following:

- The **EU Think Tank**, a strategic hub aimed at working towards an integrated vision of food systems and the transformation in R&I to deliver impact on FNS, by linking the European Commission to the Member States;
- **Policy Labs** mobilise key stakeholders in order to align the R&I policy programmes and investment schemes of national governments, so that R&I activities have a maximum impact on local, regional or national FNS goals;
- **City Labs** create a link between city-based Science Centres or research institution-based Science Shops and the networks of the cities of the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact (MUFPP) to develop and pilot hands-on (in)formal trainings for students and professionals, bringing a wide diversity of actors together.

Although we cannot claim that the *first release* of this database provides a complete coverage of food policies in Europe, and we acknowledge that some of the accompanying information might contain inaccuracies, we believe that this extensive mapping effort constitutes a valuable information tool to serve the policy debate and the development of future food system strategies. More specifically:

- The database is **dynamic**. We envisage progressive updating of the database to incorporate feedback, corrections and additions by qualified users, starting from the FIT4FOOD2030 project partners. At

least one new release of the electronic database is expected by the end of the FIT4FOOD2030 project¹;

- The structure of the database is **flexible**. We have developed a taxonomy of food policies based on existing classification of policy goals (from the SUSFANS project² and from the European Commission FOOD 2030 policy framework), and we provide other classification dimensions in terms of the policy instruments and the economic and social actors targeted. The database can be extended with other classification variables to be designed according to specific purposes;
- The database provides links to the **original source of information**.

The main contribution of this European food policy mapping task is that it goes beyond the specificity of the currently available information, as most of the available policy data at the international level is specific to a given policy goal, for example:

- mapping of nutrition policies in the NOURISHING data-base (World Cancer Research Funding International);
- information on EU-level food policies as described in the European Commission documents, reports and website;
- questionnaire-based survey on 21 EU member states by the Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR) Strategic Working Group on Food Systems (SWG) (mainly focusing on Food and Nutrition Systems and R&I policies)³;
- WHO global database on nutrition policies and programmes.

The best possible effort within the available resources has been done to cover all European policies, but there is no guarantee that all existing food policies implemented by Member States are included. For example, policies for which no on-line documentation is provided are likely to have been missed by our search strategy. Furthermore, the mapping was limited to policies implemented at the national level, and does not cover regional or local policies (with some relevant exceptions), and policies without any documentation in English may also have been overlooked by our search strategy. The University of Bologna has allocated own resources to transfer the excel database into a searchable on-line database, with the possibility for users to provide feedback to amend, complete and improve the data available.

Nevertheless, the work has been *comprehensive in scope* (i.e. we ensured that some policy information is available for all goals, targets and instruments relevant to FNS R&I policies). In this report the concept definitions and classification framework of the database is explained and the search protocol is introduced.

This Deliverable does not provide a policy analysis beyond a quantitative presentation of the policies over the different classification variables (goal, target, instrument, governance). However, the database does invite further analysis. Although not an objective of this deliverable, we do provide in the last chapter and the Annex some illustrative examples of data extractions from the database, in the form of «Policy Cards». These Cards are designed to help understand the structure and content of the database and show how the mapping could provide useful elements for discussion on policy gaps and priorities within and outside the project. The Policy Cards are an additional output of the mapping activity and, therefore, go beyond the scopes of this report. The full set of Cards will be made available on the FIT4FOOD2030 project website (and the future web-based platform provided by the University of Bologna) together with the on-line searchable version of the database, and this Deliverable contains a selection of Policy Cards (see Appendix).

¹ A web-based implementation of the database, with features to promote user feedback, is currently under construction at the University of Bologna.

² <http://susfans.eu>

³ The SCAR survey (see the final report in EU SCAR, 2018) aimed at a qualitative mapping of existing FNS policies and was based on a questionnaire administered to participating countries. The inputs were based on policy documents and a self-analysis by participants. In our mapping exercise, we exploited the links to the policy documents kindly provided by SCAR, and our classification was based on the original policy documents rather than on the SCAR survey information, since our objectives were different. Starting from the policy documents we identified about 34% of the policies currently included in the database.

3 Concept definitions and classification framework

This section explains the definition of terms that guided the extraction of the policies, and their classification within the database. It is important to emphasize that multiple definitions exist, and different definitions often relate to different disciplinary background.

Definitions

- **Public policy:** public policy includes actions of government and/or public agencies to convert competing private objectives into public commitments and includes decisions not to take action. Public policies are purposeful decisions made by authoritative actors in a political system who have the formal responsibility for making binding choices among societal goals. Public policy is a form of government control usually expressed in a law, a regulation, or an order. Since it reflects an intent of government, it is backed by an authorized reward, incentive or penalty (Cochran and Malone, 2005, p. 13).
- **Food policy:** any government action that can affect the food system concerning production and its inputs, package, process, trade, retail and consumption, and the disposal of waste.
- **Innovation:** implementation of a new or significantly improved product (good or service), or process, a new marketing method, or a new organisational method in business practices, workplace organisation or external relations (EU SCAR, 2012).
- **(R&)Innovation activity:** all scientific, technological, organisational, financial and commercial steps that actually, or intend to, lead to the implementation of innovations (EU SCAR, 2012).
- **FNS-R&I policy:** any government action that funds, stimulate or directs R&I to promote innovation for food systems.
- **Governance:** in our analysis we follow the definition provided in Treib et al. (2007) and taken from Benz (2004) where governance is identified as “*steering and co-ordination of interdependent (usually collective) actors based on institutionalised rule systems*”. In other words, this notion refers to the interactions and implementation issues across policy levels, and the management of the context in which such interactions take place. This concept has gained relevance in our policy mapping, as it has been recognised that conventional policy actions addressing individual issues may be unable to capture the complex and evolving nature of food systems. This entails a shift towards the adoption of a systemic perspective that takes into account the interrelatedness of the whole food chain and the whole food cycle (Lang and Barling, 2012). The need for a new approach to governance is reflected in our database by underlying the share of horizontal policies (i.e. those policies that address multiple policy goals and/or target multiple policy actors) and policies built on interactions across scales between public and/or private entities aiming at the realisation of collective goals (Termeer et al., 2011).
- **Policy goal:** statements describing the fundamental outcomes that a policy aims to achieve through its activities. Policy goals are high order statements of desired outcomes (e.g. reduced environmental impact).
- **Policy instrument:** techniques or means through which public actors (e.g. national and EU government bodies, public agencies, etc.) attempt to attain their goals.
- **Policy target group(s):** the societal groups that are directly affected by the policy, more specifically:
 - **Primary target:** the main societal group towards which the policy action is directed or applied by the instrument used;
 - **Ultimate beneficiary:** the societal group that is linked to the overall policy goal (e.g. a sugar tax affects manufacturing companies but is intended to promote healthy eating habits among consumers, who thus are the ultimate beneficiaries).

Classification

The collected policies are classified according to policy **goals**, **targets** (primary target and ultimate beneficiary), and **instruments**.

Figure 1: Food policies' classification criteria.

As for the policy classification by goal, two options are provided:

- a) The first is based on the **SUSFANS conceptual framework**, slightly adjusted to reflect the desired outcomes expressed in EU or national policies.

Box 2: SUSFANS proposed metrics for assessing sustainable food and nutrition security of the EU food system.

SUSFANS (Metrics, Models and Foresight for European **S**ustainable **F**ood **A**nd **N**utrition **S**ecurity) is a H2020 multidisciplinary research program aimed at building the conceptual framework, the evidence-based and analytical tools for underpinning EU-wide food policies with respect to their impact on consumer diet and their implications for nutrition and public health in the EU, the environment, the competitiveness of the EU agri-food sectors, and global FNS.

The SUSFANS team developed an approach to derive from a wide set of variables a smaller set of high level performance metrics describing the four SUSFANS policy goals formulated for the EU food system, namely (i) 'Balanced and sufficient diets for EU citizens', (ii) 'Reduced environmental impacts of the EU food system', (iii) 'Competitiveness of EU agri-food businesses', and (iv) 'Equitable outcomes and conditions of the EU food system'. This approach should allow policy and decision makers concerned with different parts of the EU food system to make sense of present trends and think about possible innovations to move the EU food system towards sustainability.

More specifically, the chosen food policy goals for FIT4FOOD2030 are:

- Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens;
- Food safety;
- Reduced environmental impact;
- Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business;
- Equitable outcomes and conditions.

Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Food safety	Reduced environmental impact	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Equitable outcomes and conditions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reduced economic and social burden of diet-related diseases ○ Food security 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Animal welfare ○ Biodiversity ○ Climate ○ Plant health ○ Resource efficiency and waste management ○ Water and soil management ○ Multiple subgoals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Competitiveness ○ Market regulation (e.g. prices, VAT, marketing rules) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Equity and social cohesion in the EU ○ Aid and cooperation ○ Global Food and Nutrition Security

Figure 2: First set of policy goals and sub-goals adopted in the food policy mapping, based on the SUSFANS conceptual framework with adaptations.

- b) The second classification reflects the four **FOOD 2030 overarching priorities** (EC, 2017), namely⁴:
- NUTRITION for sustainably and healthy diets, whose main challenges are: (i) Tackling malnutrition and obesity; (ii) Improving nutrition for healthy ageing, (iii) Supporting protein alternatives to meat; (iv) Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems; (v) Recovering forgotten crops for nutrition and resilience; (vi) Promoting healthy and sustainable African diets.
 - CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems, whose main challenges are: (i) Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe, (ii) Enabling precision farming for small farmers, (iii) Boosting photosynthesis for food and energy; (iv) Fighting climate change through healthy soils.
 - CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems, whose main challenges are: (i) Achieving zero food waste; (ii) Tackling primary production waste streams; (iii) Converting food waste into bio-based products; (iv) Rethinking food packaging and labelling; (v) Sharing data for short-circuit food systems.
 - INNOVATION and empowerment of communities, whose main challenges are: (i) Ensuring sustainable and accessible food in cities; (ii) Engaging citizens in food systems and science policy; (iii) Fostering a sharing economy for food production and consumption; (iv) Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems.

| NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets
 |
|---|--|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Tackling malnutrition and obesity ○ Improving nutrition for healthy ageing ○ Supporting protein alternatives to meat ○ Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems ○ Recovering forgotten crops for nutrition and resilience ○ Promoting healthy and sustainable African diets | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe ○ Enabling precision farming for small farmers ○ Boosting photosynthesis for food and energy ○ Fighting climate change through healthy soils | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Achieving zero food waste ○ Tackling primary production waste streams ○ Converting food waste into bio-based products ○ Rethinking food packaging and labelling ○ Sharing data for short-circuit food systems | <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Ensuring sustainable and accessible food in cities ○ Engaging citizens in food systems and science policy ○ Fostering a sharing economy for food production and consumption ○ Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems |

Figure 3: Second set of policy goals adopted in the food policy mapping, following the FOOD 2030 four overarching priorities and related challenges.

⁴ The above classification and definitions were not exhaustive in terms of covering the mapped policies included in the dataset. For example, income and price support measures for the agricultural sector that are independent from nutrition and environmental outcomes (e.g. some of past CAP measures like milk quotas) are not covered in the priority list and were marked as NA (not applicable). Other specific measures, e.g. those aimed at promoting animal welfare, were included in the CLIMATE priority, but no specific challenge has been selected. Similarly, aid and cooperation policies for agriculture in developing countries that do not fall under the “diets in Africa” challenge were left unclassified.

The mapped policies refer to the entire food system: from inputs, primary production, harvesting, storage, processing, packaging and distribution, to consumers. The mapping has considered not only policies targeting actors (i.e. policy target groups) involved in the food system, but also those targeting actors who, even if not directly involved in the food system, can influence food availability and consumption or other related matters (e.g. the logistic sector, import/export companies, the education sector, research institutions, the health sector, media and public authorities). Furthermore, the possibility of public-private partnerships as policy targets has been envisaged. Figure 4 displays the actors considered in the FIT4FOOD2030 framework for the mapping of food policies.

Figure 4: Food system actors, including ultimate beneficiaries and primary targets.

Finally, the following policy instruments were considered in the food policy classification:

- **R&I**, which we chose to define as a **policy instrument** designed to reach a given policy goal, rather than a policy target by itself. Following the classification by Rogge and Reichardt (2016), the class of R&I policy instruments has been broken down into three dimensions:
 - Economic instruments (i.e. R&D grants and loans, tax incentives, state equity assistance, subsidies, feed-in tariffs, trading systems, deposit-refund-systems, public procurement, export credit guarantees, infrastructure provision, cooperative R&D grants);
 - Regulation (i.e. patent law, intellectual property rights, technology/performance standards, prohibition of products/practices, application constraints, market design, grid access guarantee, priority feed-in, environmental liability law);
 - Information (i.e. professional training and qualification, entrepreneurship training, scientific workshops, training on new technologies, rating and labelling programs, public information campaigns, education system, thematic meetings, public debates, cooperative R&D programs, clusters);
- **Regulation and self-regulation** (e.g. quality, safety or nutrition laws concerning the production and processing of food products; advertising restrictions and bans; sale restrictions; food marketing rules; regulation on health, nutrition and safety claims; GMO regulations; etc.);
- **Fiscal policies** (e.g. taxes or subsidies applied to certain categories of food and drink ingredients; subsidies for farmers to grow certain crops; return systems to reduce packaging waste; financial support for withdrawals of food products; tax exemptions; etc.);
- **Income support measures** (e.g. income-based or other conditional food vouchers or cash transfers targeting, for instance, farmers or low-income consumers), with the aim of improving

their purchasing power and access to food products and/or agricultural inputs, equipment and machineries, thus helping to tackle disparities;

- **Border measures** (import and export licences, tariffs and quotas for certain food products; animal and animal-derived products transit rules; veterinary certifications for imports; etc.);
- **Food and agricultural standards**, either voluntary or mandatory, setting rules on content (ingredients) and composition of foods; use of food additives, supplement and improvement agents;
- **Labelling measures**, which set the type and extent of information about a product, its container or packaging that must be imparted by a label;
- **Information measures** (i.e. social marketing; awareness campaigns; recommendations; dedicated informative websites; knowledge transfer programmes; guidelines; etc.);
- **Education measures** (i.e. educational programmes on European agriculture, healthy eating addressed to pre-primary, primary, secondary and tertiary school students; the inclusion of food-related curricula or classes in schools; trainings addressed to food services personnel and staff; tailor-made advice for farmers and fishermen; etc.);
- **Delivery of services** (e.g. support for the internationalisation of EU agri-food businesses; common catalogues for agricultural product varieties; networks and databases to connect multiple public and private bodies; etc.);
- **Procurement** (i.e. government food purchases, generally for food assistance, hospitals, schools, nursing homes, prisons, the military, etc. – they are often part of public food procurement strategies to boost rural economies, promote agricultural development, encourage the development of SMEs, improve food security and nutrition, and support the achievement of social, environmental and economic objectives by linking public food purchases to domestic food production);
- **SME-targeted support** (i.e. guarantee funds for SMEs to promote access to funding sources; measures to regulate aid to SMEs; etc.).

Governance characteristics of the policies

A change in the governance approach towards integration is recognized as a key element for the success of current and future food policies in the recent policy debate (see e.g. Ipes Food, 2019; OECD/FAO/UNCDF 2016). More specifically, in order to achieve the overarching objective of environmental, economic and social sustainability, food policies and their governance should reach a higher level of integration at (a) the coordination level (integrate objectives across different food policies and minimize trade-offs and conflict); (b) the territorial level (across regions/countries); and (c) in terms of geographical scope (integrate local, national and international policies).

Relative to the past, this means a major change in the governance paradigm. Our database provides some information on governance through two additional classification variables, which identify: (a) **horizontal** policies serving more than one goal and benefitting several food system actors; and (b) **voluntary self-regulations** by the private sector and public-private partnerships/agreements (**PPPs**). The other dimension (internationalization of policies) is mainly related to policy-making at the EU level⁵.

⁵ Since our database is targeted at policies at the national and international level, it does not allow to explore integration with and within the local level policies.

4 Search protocol

Selection criteria

For a policy to be included in the database, all the following criteria have to be met.

It must be:

- a government action, an action implemented in partnership with government, or an action that is supported, sponsored or endorsed by government (i.e. by EC or member states' governments);
- a policy implemented in, or funded by, the EU or Member States;
- related to the food system and the R&I goals displayed in the classification section;
- directed to one of the target groups displayed in the classification section.

Whenever possible, additional information on the policy as described in a specific document, publication or hyperlink has been provided under the following conditions:

- the document must clearly specify the description of the policy, which has to include its goal and sub-goal, ultimate beneficiary, primary target, policy instruments used, policy maker who implemented it, geographical information, year or period of implementation, etc.;
- the document should belong to one of the following categories:
 - it is published by a Member State government or the EU/EC;
 - it is a study published as a scientific article;
 - it has been included in existing review or collection of policies (e.g. the NOURISHING database);
- the document has to be written in English, with some exceptions for documents published in the national original language that we translated into English.

Search strategy

The policy mapping aims to be comprehensive in scope, but not necessarily exhaustive. The aim was to collect several examples for each policy goal, targeted actor and instrument used, but it is not claimed that all the policies implemented in the EU have been gathered in this first release of the data set. However, the mapping does cover at least one example of policy for each (sub-)goal considered.

As first thing, references from collections of policies already available, such as the NOURISHING database, have been collected and classified. A collaboration and an exchange of information with the SCAR group has allowed the inclusion of information from a qualitative mapping performed on Member States, focusing on R&I food policies. Then, additional policies were identified through the EC website and Member States government websites. Scientific literature available on on-line databases (e.g. Google scholar, WOS, Scopus) has been used to fill the gaps, and is cited in the database for further information about the policies.

Figure 5: Sources used for the policy mapping, listed in chronological sequence.

For each source, a specific search procedure has been adopted.

NOURISHING: For each policy included in the Nourishing database, a research is performed on the website of the Member State that promoted and implemented it. Other official sources are reviewed – such as

scientific literature quoting the policy, online news websites, websites of public and private associations – in order to find detailed information about the policy.

SCAR: The Standing Committee on Agricultural Research (SCAR) Strategic Working Group on Food Systems (SWG) has performed an extensive quantitative and qualitative analysis of the research projects and policies in Europe in the last 5 years as related to food systems, covering the major trends and ambitions, improvements needed and gaps in R&I. This mapping activity involved the collection of questionnaires from twenty EU Member States, asking them for weblinks regarding:

1. National and regional policies or strategies that are relevant to ensuring food and nutrition security (e.g. agriculture, health, food safety, climate, fisheries, etc.);
2. National and regional R&I policies, strategies or funding programmes relevant to food and nutrition security (e.g. agriculture, health, food safety, climate, fisheries, etc.).

Starting from the indicated weblinks, information is searched in Member States websites. Websites in languages different from English have been translated using Google translate; websites that provided information about policies only in pdf file could not be translated.

Governments EU Member States websites: For all the EU Member States a search has been conducted on their government's websites, focusing on agriculture, health and economics ministries.

EC website: The European Commission website has been consulted to collect R&I policies covering topics that are relevant for the food system (e.g. agriculture and rural development, fisheries, environment, climate change, food safety).

5 Final data-base

The food policy mapping is provided as a separate Excel file, but has been structured in a way that offers the possibility to develop a dedicated searchable on-line policy database.

The database contains the following information for each policy:

- **Source:** the source from which the policy has been retrieved (e.g. EC, Nourishing, SCAR, Member State websites);
- **ID policy:** a unique number for each policy ranging from 1 to 460;
- **Policy:** the name of the policy;
- **Policy description:** a brief description of the policy taken from reference sources;
- **SUSFANS-based Policy goal:** the goal of the policy (see *Classification* section);
- **SUSFANS-based Policy sub-goal:** the sub-goal of the policy (see *Classification* section);
- **FOOD 2030 Priority:** the overarching priority at which the policy is addressed (see *Classification* section);
- **FOOD 2030 Challenge:** the specific FOOD 2030 challenge at which the policy may contribute (see *Classification* section);
- **Ultimate beneficiary:** the ultimate beneficiary of the policy (see *Classification* section);
- **Policy instrument:** the instrument of the policy (see *Classification* section);
- **Primary Target:** the primary target of the policy (see *Classification* section);
- **Geography:** the country or region where the policy was implemented;
- **Policy formulator** (governments or public agencies): the formulator of the policy (e.g. a Member State ministry, an European Commission DG, an association);
- **Governance – Horizontal:** a binary variable indicating policies that pertain to multiple policy goals and benefit different actors of the food system, hence denoting integration across different policy areas
- **Governance – Partnerships:** a binary variable highlighting policies based on an active collaboration between the public and private sectors (e.g. public-private partnerships, responsibility deals, voluntary agreements, etc.), hence promoting involvement of key food chain actors
- **Year:** the year or period in which the policy was implemented;
- **Web link1:** reference to website reporting information about the policy;
- **Web link2:** reference to website reporting information about the policy;
- **Web link3:** reference to website reporting information about the policy;
- **Scientific article1:** reference to scientific article about the policy (if any);
- **Scientific article2:** reference to scientific article about the policy (if any).

6 Selected mapping outputs

Database contents and graphical representations

This section is aimed at providing an overview of the content of the database through graphs and tables which show the distribution of the mapped policies according to the different classification criteria.

The dataset contains **460 policies** (as of 22th of March 2019), of which 281 have been implemented at the Member State level and 179 at the EU level. As mentioned before, our policy mapping is comprehensive in scope (*i.e.* it includes examples for all policy goals, target and instruments), but not necessarily exhaustive, given the complexity and rapid evolution of the policy environment.

The distribution of the policies is provided through the following graphs and tables

- 1) **FOOD 2030 priorities and challenges** (Figure 6). This set of pie charts shows the percentage of policies included in the dataset classified according to the FOOD 2030 priorities (top pie chart) and for each of the four FOOD 2030 challenges. All policies but a small part (4%) had a classification in terms of *FOOD 2030 priorities*. The 4% of policies that had no classification referred to measures that

had no univocal correspondence among the priorities (for example some of the animal welfare measures, quotas and other agricultural support measures that have been abandoned, non-targeted aid policies). The four bottom graphs refer to the distribution of policies according to their *FOOD 2030 challenge*. To improve the clarity of the chart under the Nutrition priority, we aggregated items (challenges) which were only represented by 1 or 2 policies into the „Others“ category but the specific challenge remains available in the data-set. Under the other priorities, for some policies it was not possible to identify a meaningful challenge, and these policies still appear in the graph under the „NA“ item.

- 2) **SUSFANS-based classification of policy goals** (Figure 7). The bar chart shows how the mapped policies are classified based on the SUSFANS classification described in Section 3, making a distinction between policies regulated at the EU level, and those implemented at the member state level.
- 3) **Ultimate beneficiary** (Figure 8). The pie chart was built considering the proportion of policies for each category of ultimate beneficiary, as defined in Section 3.
- 4) **Primary targeted actor** (Figure 9). The bar chart displays the proportion of policies based on the primary targeted actor, as defined in Section 3, distinguishing between policies implemented at the National or EU level. To enhance the readability of the graph, we aggregated actors appearing less than 10 times in the database (e.g. there were 7 policies targeting SMEs, 4 targeting the logistic sectors, 2 aimed at Third Countries, etc.). Again, the database provides the original classification and not the aggregated one which is shown in the graph and it is possible to extract policies pertaining to specific actors.
- 5) **Type of instrument** (Figure 10). The aim of these two pie chart is to display the distribution of policies based on their instrument, according to the classification of instruments introduced in Section 3, and distinguishing between policies implemented at the EU level, and those designed at the National-level. The three policy instruments related to R&I were grouped into a single item, and instruments that were adopted in less than 5 policies listed in the database were grouped into the „Other“ category, but the detailed classification can be extracted from the dataset.

Results

Proportion of mapped policies by FOOD 2030 priority

Proportion of mapped policies by FOOD 2030 challenges

NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets

CLIMATE-smart and environmentally sustainable food systems

CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems

INNOVATION and empowerment of communities

Figure 6. Distribution of mapped policies according to the FOOD 2030 priorities and challenges

Proportion of mapped policies by GOAL (SUSFANS-BASED classification)

Figure 7. Distribution of mapped policies according to the policy goal (SUSFANS-based classification).

Proportion of mapped policies by ULTIMATE BENEFICIARY

Note: Consumers are defined as citizen targeted in their act of consuming food (e.g. promoting a healthier diet), while the broader category defined as *society at large* includes benefits not necessarily associated with consumption (e.g. reducing greenhouse gas emissions). Other target beneficiaries should be self-explanatory.

Figure 8. Distribution of mapped policies according to the ultimate beneficiary.

Proportion of mapped policies by PRIMARY TARGET

Figure 9. Distribution of mapped policies according to the primary targeted actor.

Proportion of mapped policies by INSTRUMENT

Figure 10. Distribution of mapped policies according to the policy instrument.

Policies and governance approach

Tables 1, 2 and 3 below summarize evidence on our governance classification of the mapped policies, identifying those policies who are *horizontal* as they pertain multiple policy goals, or they explicitly refer to public-private partnerships (PPPs) as a policy instrument. These classifications are necessarily fuzzy and suffer from some degree of subjectivity, but they provide a useful first insight on the level of integration relative to the different policy goals.

Among the policies included in the mapping, 57 horizontal policies (12% of the total) and 22 policies (5% of the total) have been found.

Table 1 shows the percentages of Horizontal policies for each FOOD2030 priority; innovation and empowerment of communities is the priority that has the largest share of horizontal policies. Table 2 displays the FOOD2030 priorities of PPPs policies, which represent 7% among the policies aimed at circularity and resource efficiency of food systems and 8% among those aimed at nutrition for sustainable and healthy diets, being represented for the most part by public-private partnerships in setting voluntary nutritional standards for consumers. In Table 3 there is the distribution of national and EU policies again for each of the FOOD2030 priorities, from which appears that compared to EU policies, higher shares of national policies focus on innovation and empowerment of communities, and circularity and resource efficiency of food systems.

Table 1 - Number and proportion of horizontal policies for each FOOD2030 priority.

Governance - Horizontal	n	%
INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	31	33%
CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	3	23%
CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	11	17%
NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	12	4%
Total	57	12%

Note: the Total 12% refers to the proportion of all mapped policies presenting horizontal integration, thus it does not refer to the sum of the above values. The values under column “%” refer to the percentage of policies that present horizontal integration within the given FOOD2030 priority.

Table 2 - Number and proportion of Public-Private Partnerships policies for each FOOD2030 priority.

Governance - PPPs	n	%
CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	1	8%
NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	19	7%
CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	1	2%
INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	1	1%
Total	22	5%

Note: The Total 5% refers to the proportion of all mapped policies presenting horizontal integration, thus it does not refer to the sum of the above values. The values under column “%” refer to the percentage of policies that refer to PPPs within the given FOOD2030 priority.

Table 3 - Number and proportion of National and EU-wide policies for each FOOD2030 priority.

Geography	EU (n)	EU (%)	National (n)	National (%)
CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	33	51%	32	49%
NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	119	44%	150	56%
CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	4	31%	9	69%
INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	12	13%	83	87%
NA	11	61%	7	39%
Total	179	39%	281	61%

7 Using the data-base to support discussion on gaps and policy priorities: a demonstration using “Policy Cards”

Although the output of this deliverable is a database providing a comprehensive overview of food policies classified according to goal, target, instrument and governance variables, in this last chapter we provide illustrative examples of data extractions from the database, in the form of «Policy Cards». The Policy Cards serve as a demonstrator and facilitator tool for the policy mapping database. The full set of policy cards will be released as a separate document from this Deliverable, but three examples are provided in the Appendix. The aim of Policy Cards is to provide different stakeholder groups with an easy-to-read tool to better understand the structure and content of the food policy database.

Extractions and graphical representation of data from the policy mapping simply reflect the number of policies identified for each goal / economic actor / instrument, and no claim is made on the effectiveness or desirability of the various policy alternatives, in absence of clear scientific evidence and consensus on their impacts. The amount of available scientific evidence greatly varies across policy types, and one of the potential future extensions of the database is the inclusion of references to robust scientific evidence.

Building on the food policies’ classification criteria detailed in the Classification section, the Policy Cards are divided into three groups:

1. **Policy Cards by goal**, which include infographics and charts for each of the five mentioned policy goals. The aim of this set of cards is to understand which are the actors mostly targeted to reach the different objectives and which policy instruments are used accordingly⁶.
2. **Policy Cards by actor**, which include infographics and charts for each target group, both ultimate beneficiaries and primary targets. The objective of these cards is to see which policy goal the various stakeholder groups insist on and which kind of policy instrument they adopt to reach the intended goal⁷.
3. **Policy Cards by instrument**, which include infographics and charts for each policy instrument. The purpose of this set of cards is to evaluate which instruments are more (or less) effective in tackling the various issues related to the food system, and to which degree they are used by the different actor groups.

Beyond these Policy Cards groups, a first and more general card named “Mapping Food Policies” has been designed to give a very brief overview of the methodology, results and representativeness of the overall mapping activity, with infographics and charts by goal, ultimate beneficiary, primary target and instrument regarding all the 460 policies that have been mapped.

Moreover, those pie charts or histograms reflecting food policy trends, which have been considered of particular interest, are supported in the Policy Cards by coloured boxes. These “Food for Thought” boxes consist of comments, considerations or open questions that exemplify, based on the mapped food policies in the EU, what sort of possible issues might emerge in a policy discussion among various stakeholders, such as those occurring in Policy Labs. The idea behind them is not, indeed, that of making policy statements or

⁶ In addition to the original goals, a **cross-sectional R&I oriented goal** was introduced for the policy cards, since FNS R&I policies might have more than one goal, or the only goal of increasing general knowledge. The mentioned goals are expressed through sub-goals to allow for a more accurate classification of policies (see Figure 2).

⁷ Among actors, **Consumers** are defined as citizen targeted in their act of consuming food (e.g. promoting a healthier diet), while the broader category defined as **Society at large** includes benefits not necessarily associated with consumption (e.g. reducing greenhouse gas emissions). Other target beneficiaries should be self-explanatory.

giving opinions or recommendations, but rather providing inputs to stimulate debate occasions on existing food policies. The template used for the policy cards is shown in Figure 11.

Template for Policy Card (by goal/actor/instrument): Name of the goal/actor/instrument

*Brief **text** to describe the features of the specific food system’s goal/actor/instrument considered serves as an introduction to each Policy Card.*

In the case of Policy Cards by goal, the list of respective **subgoals** is provided here.

Proportion of mapped policies by:

- In the case of Policy Cards by **GOAL**, the proportion is done by actor (ultimate beneficiaries and primary targets) and instrument.
- In the case of Policy Cards by **ACTOR**, the proportion is done by goal (and subgoal, when relevant) and instrument; plus, some Cards include different graphs depending on how users want to consider the actor, either as a policy beneficiary or primary target.
- In the case of Policy Cards by **INSTRUMENT**, the proportion is done by goal (and subgoal, when relevant) and actor (ultimate beneficiaries and primary targets).

To illustrate such proportions, **pie charts** with their respective legends are added to this section, keeping the same colour selection throughout the entire set of Cards so that to facilitate cross-Cards comparisons.

Colour boxes providing “**food for thought**” accompany most infographics and charts.

*These “food for thought” boxes develop very general questions based on the mapping results. The aim of the questions is to **stimulate discussion** and promote critical thinking on the development and prioritization of policies rather than draw conclusions.*

Figure 11: Template of the Policy Cards reflecting their general structure and sections.

Appendix A – Examples of Policy Cards

This appendix provides some examples of Policy Cards that draw from the policy database to illustrate the potential use of the EU food policy mapping.

We provide three examples:

A.1 – Policy cards by goal: *Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens*

A.2 – Policy cards by targeted actor: *Consumers*

A.3 – Policy cards by instrument: *Research & Innovation*

A.1 Example of policy card by goal

Policy goal: **Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens**

Food systems may shape health impacts through changing diets. Balanced and sufficient diets are determined by their contribution of energy, macronutrients and micronutrients to total daily body needs. Diet composition is a major determinant of not only the **increasing burdens of overweight and obesity** – which affect about 50% and 20%, respectively, of the EU adult population (WHO, 2018) – but also a number of **nutrient deficiencies, chronic diseases** and **non-communicable diseases** (NCDs), all considered significant causes of mortality and premature death in the EU. Eating habits have an important role to play in preventing these diseases and, accordingly, a number of strategic policies and actions have been adopted in the EU to improve health for all citizens and reduce health inequalities. Access to healthy diets has been undermined by economic hardship and, in this regard, the definition of **food and nutrition security** at the EU level is taken to address the heterogeneous socio-economic and demographic realities within the Union and the consequently diversified conditions of food utilisation and access.

Subgoals

- ❖ **Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases**
- ❖ **Food security**

In terms of beneficiaries, unsurprisingly **99%** of mapped policies aimed at promoting balanced and sufficient diets benefits **consumers**. In our policy actor classification '*Consumers*' are defined as citizens targeted in their act of consuming food (e.g. promoting a healthier diet), which differ from the broader category defined as '*Society at large*' as the latter considers benefits not necessarily associated with consumption (e.g. reducing greenhouse gas emissions).

Proportion of mapped nutrition policies by PRIMARY TARGET

'Balanced and sufficient diets' goal

- Food industry
- School food services
- Media
- Consumers
- Education sector
- Others

All goals

- Food industry
- Import/export companies
- Research sector
- Fisheries
- Others
- Farmers
- School food services
- Public authorities
- Industry-based research

Policies targeting this goal privilege the **private sector** (food industry, school food services and the media) as their initial target.

*Could the **education sector** and the **farmers** be also primary targets for policies aimed at reaching balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens?*

Proportion of mapped nutrition policies by INSTRUMENT

- Regulation
- Information measure
- Food and agricultural standards
- R&I
- Labelling measure
- Fiscal policy
- Border measure
- Others

'Balanced and sufficient diets for all' goal

All goals

Relative to other food policies, there is more emphasis on **information measures** and **food & agricultural standards** and fewer policies acting through R&I.

*Could the R&I measures be effective also in promoting a balanced and sufficient diet?
Is there room to target the R&I sector and/or use R&I instruments?*

Is the combination of fiscal policies and information measures effective in inducing a sustained behavioural change? Or are substitutions affecting product choices, but not the overall healthiness of diets?

Relevant related trends in the food system

Source: FIT4FOOD2030 (2018), "Trends in the food system", D2.1

A.2 Example of policy card by actor

Policy actor: Consumers

Across Member States, **household expenditure on food products** varies from 10% to 31%, with an average of 13.8% at EU level (FoodDrinkEurope, 2018). Consumer behaviours reflect all choices and decisions (at the household or individual level) on what foods to purchase, store, prepare, eat and how to allocate them within the household, and is influenced not only by **personal preferences** (e.g. taste, convenience, values, traditions, culture and beliefs) but also by the **existing food environment** (e.g. food prices, income, knowledge and skills, time and equipment, social and cultural norms). Collective changes in consumer behaviour can open a pathway towards healthier and more sustainable food systems. From our mapping, it emerges that consumers act more as **ultimate beneficiaries** of food policies (262 policies) rather than their **primary targets** (16 policies).

On which GOAL do consumers-benefitting policies focus?

- Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens
- Food safety
- Viable and socially balanced agri-food business
- Reduced environmental impacts
- Equitable outcomes and conditions

The majority of food policies that benefit consumers focuses on **nutrition** (47%) and **food safety** (38%), as they represent the closest issues to the act of consuming food products.

What are the R&I-oriented policies that generate immediate benefits to consumers?

Co-creation – a new people-engaging perspective where consumers are active participants of the development of new products – has rapidly taken hold, together with the spread of **smart domestic appliances** requiring consumers' acceptance.

With this in mind, is there room to strengthen the role of R&I in designing consumer-based policies, rather than mostly focusing on industry-based ones?

Through which TARGET do consumer-benefitting policies act?

As expected the **food industry, school food services and import/export companies** are the primary actors through which consumer-benefitting policies are implemented (53% overall), with the view of guaranteeing balanced and sufficient diets and food safety.

*Within the private sector, is the central role of **retailers** adequately exploited to promote consumer-oriented regulations?*

*Should **media** play a less subordinate role? Are they key players in providing consumers with useful information to change their behaviours towards more sustainable choices?*

Through which INSTRUMENTS are they implemented?

Consumers as food policies' **ultimate beneficiaries**

Consumers as food policies' **primary targets**

From the mapping, **R&I** does not currently emerge as a major policy instrument for targeting and/or benefitting consumers. *Is this gap real? If so, how could R&I policies be enhanced as a mean to benefit consumers more directly?*

*Is **information** a powerful instrument to achieve a healthy and sustainable diet?*

Relevant consumer trends

Source: FIT4FOOD2030 (2018), "Trends in the food system", D2.1

A.3 Example of policy cards by instrument

Policy instrument: Research & Innovation

Within the mapping strategy, we chose to define R&I as a **policy instrument** designed to reach a given policy goal, rather than a policy target by itself. Following the classification by Rogge and Reichardt (2016), the class of R&I policy instruments has been broken down into three dimensions:

- **Economic instruments** (e.g. fiscal measures, research funds, etc.)
- **Information instruments** (e.g. funding trainings/education measures, scientific workshops, etc.)
- **Regulations** (e.g. regulation on intellectual property rights and patenting, technology standards, banning practices etc.)

Only one food policy exploiting an R&I regulatory approach has been mapped.

Is this type of instrument useful at all in addressing food system issues? Is there room for a greater use of this kind of regulation?

On which POLICY GOAL do R&I economic instruments focus?

Since some R&I actions are not explicitly targeted to a goal, we included an additional dimension called “**Cross-sectional R&I oriented goal**” (e.g. funding SMEs, but without constraining the ultimate goal of their R&I activities; incentives to hire R&I personnel; etc.) among policy goals.

While it must be kept into account that the above graph refers to the *number of the mapped policies*, and might be misleading relative to the funding levels, the low proportion of R&I actions targeting nutrition and food safety goals is striking. This is also due to the fact that a large proportion of R&I measures (30%) is not strictly connected to a goal, but leave flexibility to the research actors.

Through which PRIMARY TARGET do R&I economic instruments act?

Should information about R&I opportunities, funding options etc. act more through *civil society actors* in order to achieve a more effective and **bottom-up** transformation of food systems?

R&I information instruments predominantly focus on the **“Cross-sectional, R&I oriented” goal** and act through the **food industry** and the **research sector** – for example:

Flanders’ Food
Belgium

Target: Food industry

A strategy-driven **platform** that contributes through innovation to a more competitive, innovative and sustainable agrifood industry.

State Research Agency
Spain

Target: Research sector

It aims at improving accountability, the monitoring of actions, the management of available funds and at reducing administrative burdens.

Strategic Innovation
Sweden

Target: Research sector for the food industry

Swedish companies, authorities and universities act together to formulate challenges, set common goals and prioritise investment in R&D&I.

Who do R&I instruments ultimately benefit?

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See <https://www.wcrf.org/int/policy/nourishing-database> for NOURISHING database

FIT4FOOD -ANNEX TO DELIVERABLE 2.2 – ELECTRONIC DATABASE OF FOOD POLICIES

This is a full reproduction of the database as a pdf document. The original database is available as an Excel file

METADATA – Column descriptors

Source	The source from which the policy has been retrieved (e.g. EC, Nourishing, SCAR, Member State websites);
ID policy	Identification number, a unique number for each policy ranging from 1 to 460;
Policy	Name of the policy;
Policy description	A brief description of the policy taken from reference sources;
SUSFANS-based policy goal	The goal of the policy according to the SUSFANS-FIT4FOOD taxonomy;
SUSFANS-based policy sub-goal	The goal of the policy according to the SUSFANS-FIT4FOOD taxonomy;
FOOD 2030 priority	The overarching priority at which the policy is addressed, based on the FOOD 2030 taxonomy;
FOOD 2030 challenge	The specific FOOD 2030 challenge at which the policy may contribute;
Ultimate beneficiary	The ultimate beneficiary of the policy ;
Policy instrument	The instrument of the policy ;
Primary Target	The primary targeted actor of the policy ;
Geography	The country or region where the policy was implemented;
Policy formulator (Governments/Public agencies)	The key formulator of the policy (e.g. a Member State ministry, an European Commission DG, an association);
Governance - Horizontal	A binary variable indicating policies that pertain to multiple policy goals and benefit different actors of the food system, hence denoting integration across different policy areas
Governance - PPPs	A binary variable highlighting policies based on an active collaboration between the public and private sectors (e.g. public-private partnerships, responsivity deals, voluntary agreements, etc.), hence promoting involvement of key food chain actors
Year	The year (or period) in which the policy was implemented;
Web link1	Reference to website reporting information about the policy;
Web link2	Reference to website reporting information about the policy;
Web link3	Reference to website reporting information about the policy;
Scientific article1	Reference to scientific article about the policy (if any);
Scientific article2	Reference to scientific article about the policy (if any);

FULL DATABASE

Source	ID	Policy	Policy description	SUSFANS-based policy goal	SUSFANS-based policy sub-goal	FOOD 2030 priority	FOOD 2030 challenge	Ultimate beneficiary	Policy instrument	Primary Target	Geography	Policy formulator (Governments/Public agencies)	Governance - Horizontal	Governance - PPPs	Year	Web link1	Web link2	Web link3	Scientific article1	Scientific article2	
Nourishing	1	Regulation (EC) No 1169/2011 on the provision of food information to consumers	food labelling legislation - mandatory nutrient list on packaged food	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	2011	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/labelling_nutrition/labelling_legislation_en	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=LEGISSUM:co0019&from=IT&isLegisum=true				
Nourishing	2	Choices logo	the voluntary logo identifies healthier options in each food category	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Belgium, Czech Republic, Netherlands, Poland	Choices International Foundation	0	0	2006	https://www.choicesprogramme.org/about/the-programme/					
Nourishing	3	Keyhole logo	the voluntary logo identifies healthier options in each food category	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Sweden, Denmark, Norway, Iceland, Lithuania	Norwegian Directorate of Health	0	0	2009	https://helsenorge.no/other-languages/english/keyhole-healthy-food	https://helsedirektoratet.no/Lists/Publikasjoner/Attachments/1148/Enkelt-a-velge-sunnere-IS-0520E-engelsk.pdf				
Nourishing	4	Warning labels on high-salt food	compulsory labels on high-salt food. Each food category has a cutoff for percentage of salt above which the product is labelled as high salt content	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Finland	Finnish Ministry of social affairs and health	0	0	1993	https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/health/files/nutrition_physical_activity/docs/ev20091021_pietinen_en.pdf	http://stm.fi/en/frontpage		Pietinen, Pirjo & Valsta, Liisa & Hirvonen, Tero & Sinkko, Harri. (2008). Labelling the salt content in foods: A useful tool in reducing sodium intake in Finland. Public health nutrition. 11. 335-40. 10.1017/S136898007000249.		
Nourishing	5	Heart symbol	the heart symbol tells the consumer that the product is a better choice in its product group regarding fat and sodium. In some product groups, also sugar and fibre contents are taken into account.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Finland	Finnish Heart Foundation and Finnish Diabetes Foundation	0	0	2000	https://www.sydanmerkki.fi/en					
Nourishing	6	Nutri-Score labelling	voluntary colour-coded scheme for nutritional quality. Synthetic information system based on colours and letters from green/A to dark orange/E	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	France	Santé publique France-French national public health agency	0	0	2017	https://www.santepubliquefrance.fr/Sante-publique-France/Nutri-Score	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/eli/arrete/2017/10/31/SSAP1730474A/joytekte	https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/health/files/nutrition_physical_activity/docs/ev_20171130_co04_en.pdf	https://www.ernaehrungs-umschau.de/fileadmin/Ernaehrungs-Umschau/pdfs/pdf_2017/12_17/EU_12_2017_WuF_Nutriscore_englisch.pdf	http://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanpub/article/PIIS2468-2667(18)30009-4/fulltext	
Nourishing	7	School fruit, vegetable and milk scheme	the scheme supports the distribution of fruit and vegetables and milk to schools across the EU as part of a wider programme of education about European agriculture and the benefits of healthy eating	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Education measure	School food services	EU	EC - DG Agri	1	0	2017	https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/school-scheme_en					
Nourishing	8	Special Ordinance for healthy nutrition at schools and at kindergarten	Specific safety and quality requirements for food provided in schools.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	Bulgaria	Bulgarian Ministry of Health	0	0	2011	https://lex.bg/index.php/en/laws/doc/2135752009	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/sites/jrcsh/files/jrc-school-food-policy-factsheet-bulgaria_en.pdf				
Nourishing	9	Health protection requirements for pre-school childcare facilities and schools	Nutrition requirements for food served in school and pre-school canteens.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	Estonia	Estonian Minister of Social Affairs	0	0	2008	https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/12912436	https://janpa-toolbox.eu/page.php?id=45				
Nourishing	10	Health tax on soft drinks	health tax on soft drinks in the form of excise duties	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Fiscal policy	Food industry	Belgium	Belgian Federal Public Service - Finance	0	0	2018	https://financien.belgium.be/nl/douane_accijnzen/ondermengen/accijnzen/verhoging-accijnstarieven-1-januari-2018					

Nourishing	11	Tax on saturated fat	tax on saturated fat in food products	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Fiscal policy	Food industry	Denmark	Danish Ministry of Environment and Food	0	0	2011	http://skat.dk/skat.aspx?oid=1942614	https://www.retsinformation.dk/Forms/R0710.aspx?id=136314&newwindow=true	Jensen, J. D., & Smed, S. (2013). The Danish tax on saturated fat—short run effects on consumption, substitution patterns and consumer prices of fats. <i>Food Policy</i> , 42, 18-31.	Smed, S., Scarborough, P., Rayner, M., & Jensen, J. D. (2016). The effects of the Danish saturated fat tax on food and nutrient intake and modelled health outcomes: an econometric and comparative risk assessment. <i>European journal of clinical nutrition</i> , 70(6), 681.
Nourishing	12	Excise duty on Sweets, Ice-cream and Soft drinks	excise duty on Sweets, Ice-cream and Soft drinks	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Fiscal policy	Food industry	Finland	Finnish Ministry of Finance	0	0	2011-2017	http://tulli.fi/sv/artikel/-/asset_publisher/laki-makeisten-jaatelon-ja-virvoitusjuomien-valmisteverosta?_101_INSTANCE_QFqaWaieEuk1_languageId=fi_FI	http://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/alkup/2010/20101127		
Nourishing	13	Soda tax	excise duty on soft drinks	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Fiscal policy	Food industry	France	French Ministry of Economy, Finance and Industry	0	0	2012	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000025044460&categorieLien=id	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000025044460&categorieLien=id	Berardi, N., Sevestre, P., Tepaut, M., & Vigneron, A. (2016). The impact of a 'soda tax' on prices: evidence from French micro data. <i>Applied Economics</i> , 48(41), 3976-3994.	
Nourishing	14	Children's commercial communications code	It deals with advertising, sponsorship, product placement and other forms of commercial promotion aimed at children or broadcast in or around children's programming. It includes rules on the promotion to children of food that is high in fat, salt or sugar.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Media	Ireland	Broadcasting Authority of Ireland	0	0	2013	http://www.bai.ie/en/bai-issues-rules-on-food-advertising-to-children/	http://www.bai.ie/en/codes-standards/#al-block-5	Scully, P., Macken, A., Leddin, D., Cullen, W., Dunne, C., & Gorman, C. O. (2015). Food and beverage advertising during children's television programming. <i>Irish Journal of Medical Science (1971-)</i> , 184(1), 207-212.	
Nourishing	15	Radio and tv act	The act prohibits any (food) advertising to children below the age of 12.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Media	Sweden	Swedish Ministry of Culture	0	0	2010	http://www.mprt.se/documents/styrdokument/radio%20and%20television%20act.pdf	https://www.riksdagen.se/sv/dokument-lagar/dokument/svensk-forfattningssamling/radio--och-tv-lag-2010696_sfs-2010-696		
Nourishing	16	Eu pledge	voluntary initiative by leading food and beverage companies to change the way they advertise to children	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Food industry	EU	Association of industries - World Federation of Advertisers	0	1	2007	http://www.eu-pledge.eu/			
Nourishing	17	Less salt is healthier	reduce the salt content in bread and certain pastries by 15% by 2015	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Retailers	Austria	Austrian ministry of Health	0	1	2011	https://www.wko.at/branchen/gewerbe-handwerk/lebensmittelgewerbe/baecker/weniger-salz-ist-gesunder.html			
Nourishing	18	Salt agreement	Reduce salt consumption by the population by 10% through the reduction of salt in food products	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Food industry	Belgium	Belgian Federal Public Service - Health, food chain safety and environment, Food industry federation, Federation of shops and services	0	1	2009	https://www.health.belgium.be/fr/la-convention-sel			
Nourishing	19	Stop the salt campaign	Raising awareness of the public about the risks of excess salt in food. This campaign highlights the direct link between the overconsumption of this ingredient and hypertension.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Media	Belgium	Belgian Federal Public Service - Health, food chain safety and environment	0	0	2010	https://www.health.belgium.be/fr/stop-le-sel			
Nourishing	20	Change4Life convenience stores programme	intervention to improve provision of fresh fruit and vegetables in convenience stores in deprived, urban areas in England with poor existing retail access to fresh fruit and vegetables. Convenience stores received support to help them redesign the layout of the store	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Ensuring sustainable and accessible food in cities	Consumers	Income support	Retailers	UK	English Department of Health, Association of Convenience Stores	1	1	2008	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/change4life-convenience-stores-evaluation-report	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/change4life-convenience-stores-evaluation-report	Adams, J., Halligan, J., Watson, D. B., Ryan, V., Penn, L., Adamson, A. J., & White, M. (2012). The Change4Life convenience store programme to increase retail access to fresh fruit and vegetables: a mixed methods process evaluation. <i>PLoS One</i> , 7(6), e39431.	

Nourishing	21	Prohibition on the unlimited provision of drinks with added sugars or sweeteners	free access to sweetened or sweetened beverages at all times is prohibited in all public dining places and minors' places of reception. This ban will help to reduce the obesity and overweight of the French population, especially young people, and prevent the risk of chronic diseases.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Food services	France	French ministry of solidarity and health	0	0	2017	http://solidarites-sante.gouv.fr/prevention-en-sante/preserver-sa-sante/boissons-a-volonte
Nourishing	22	Public Health Responsibility Deal - Salt reduction (Caterers)	pledges specific to caterers as part of the Responsibility Deal, in a bid to enable caterers and their suppliers to play a fuller part in salt reduction. Three separate pledges focus on three key areas (training and kitchen practice, reformulation, and procurement)	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Food services	UK	UK department of Health	0	1	2011-2015	http://www.actiononsalt.org.uk/uk-salt-reduction-programme/caterers/ http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20180201175643/https://responsibilitydeal.dh.gov.uk/ http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20180201181150/https://responsibilitydeal.dh.gov.uk/pledges/pledge/?pl=42
Nourishing	23	Hot food takeaway supplementary planning document	control the location of and access to unhealthy food outlets	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Food services	UK	Local authorities in the UK	0	0	2010	https://www.gov.uk/government/case-studies/planning-document-to-limit-the-proliferation-of-takeaways https://www.bradford.gov.uk/planning-and-building-control/planning-policy/the-hot-food-takeaway-supplementary-planning-document-spd/
Nourishing	24	Beverage recommendations	Recommendations for beverages for children and adolescents, adults and older people.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Media	Finland	Finnish national nutrition council	0	0	2009	https://www.evira.fi/en/foods/tuff/healthy-diet/beverages/ https://www.evira.fi/globalassets/vm/pdf/beverages_in_nutrition_summary_of_opinions.pdf
Nourishing	25	Eat move (Manger Bouger)- National Health Nutrition Program	Public health plan aimed at improving the health status of the population by acting on one of its major determinants: nutrition.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Media	France	French ministry of solidarity and health, Santé publique France-French national public health agency	0	0	2001	http://www.mangerbouger.fr/ http://www.mangerbouger.fr/Manger-Mieux
Nourishing	26	Honest about food website	Information about a healthy, safe and more sustainable food choice.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Media	Netherlands	Netherlands nutrition center	0	0	2002	http://www.voedingscentrum.nl/nl.aspx http://www.voedingscentrum.nl/mijn-gewicht/gezond-gewicht.aspx
Nourishing	27	Change4life & Start4life campaigns	Health program for preventing childhood obesity.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Media	UK	UK National health service	1	1	2009	https://www.nhs.uk/change4life https://www.nhs.uk/start4life https://www.gov.uk/government/news/new-change4life-campaign-encourages-parents-to-be-food-smart
Nourishing	28	5 a day	The 5 A Day campaign is based on advice from the World Health Organization, which recommends eating a minimum of 400g of fruit and vegetables a day to lower the risk of serious health problems, such as heart disease, stroke and some cancers.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Media	Germany	German Federal Ministry of Health, Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture	0	0	2003	https://www.5amtag.de/
Nourishing	29	5 a day	The 5 A Day campaign is based on advice from the World Health Organization, which recommends eating a minimum of 400g of fruit and vegetables a day to lower the risk of serious health problems, such as heart disease, stroke and some cancers.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Media	UK	UK Public Health England	0	0	2003	https://www.nhs.uk/Livewell/5ADAY/Pages/5ADAYhome.aspx https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/government-5-a-day-logo https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167629610001372?via%3DIihub
Nourishing	30	6 a day	The official Dietary Council recommends that we eat 6 pieces of fruit and vegetables a day	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Media	Denmark	Danish Food Administration	0	0	2001	http://altomkost.dk/deofficielleanbefalingertilensundlivsstil/de-officielle-kostraad/spis-frugt-og-mange-groensager/hvad-taeller-med-i-6-om-dagen/
Nourishing	31	Little Heart logo	voluntary logo for pre-packed food and canteen menus that meet specific requirements and are considered to have a preventive effect on cardiovascular health	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Slovenia	Society for Cardiovascular Health, Slovenian Ministry of Health	0	1	1993	http://zasrce.si/159/

Nourishing	32	Front of Pack nutrition labelling scheme	The Front of Pack nutrition labelling scheme combines colour coding and percentage reference intakes	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	UK	UK Department of Health, Food Standards Agency	0	0	2013	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/front-of-pack-nutrition-labelling-guidance	https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/health/files/nutrition_physical_activity/docs/ev_20151028_co06_en.pdf	https://www.food.gov.uk/business-guidance/nutrition-labelling
Nourishing	33	Public Health Responsibility Deal - Out of Home Calorie Labelling	Out of home calorie labelling aims to inform and empower people to make healthier choices more often when eating out, as well as encouraging food businesses to make healthier options more available. Businesses voluntary provide calorie information for customers on menus or menu boards.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food services	UK	UK department of Health	0	1	2011-2015	http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20180201180712/https://responsibilitydeal.dh.gov.uk/f1-factsheet/		
Nourishing	34	Law on the circulation of energy drinks	The law prohibits the sale of energy drinks to minors, regulates energy drinks display at retail outlets, regulates the advertising of energy drinks	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Retailers	Latvia	Latvian Ministry of Health, Consumer rights protection center	0	0	2016	https://likumi.lv/doc.php?id=280078	http://www.ptac.gov.lv/lv/news/stajas-speka-enerijas-dzerienu-aprites-likums	
Nourishing	35	EU regulation on nutrition and health claims made on foods (1924/2006)	regulation on nutrition and health claims made in labelling, presentation or advertising of foods. The objective is to ensure that any claim made on a food's labelling, presentation or advertising is clear, accurate and based on scientific evidence.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	EU	EC	0	0	2006	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/labelling_nutrition/claims_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A02006R1924-20121129	
Nourishing	36	Eat and learn together - a school lunch recommendation	The school meal recommendation contains nutritional recommendation for school meals. The focus is on strengthening pupils' inclusion, providing lunches and snacks promoting health and sustainable development, taking into account the entire dining environment.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	Finland	Finnish Ministry of Social Affairs and Health, national nutrition council	0	0	2017	http://www.julkari.fi/handle/10024/131834	https://thl.fi/fi/-/uusi-kouluruokailusositus-opastayhdessa-syomiseen-jaterveellisiin-aterioihin-monipuolisesti	
Nourishing	37	Nutritional quality of school meals	Nutritional requirements for food provided in schools.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	France	French ministry of agriculture and food	0	0	2011	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000024614716&categorieLien=id		
Nourishing	38	Quality standard for school catering	The quality standard explains the requirements for optimal food selection as well as food planning and production.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	Germany	German Nutrition Society	0	0	2014	https://www.schuleplusessen.de/dge-qualitaetsstandard/	https://www.dge.de/gv/dge-qualitaetsstandards/	
Nourishing	39	Regulation of educational institutions - healthy nutrition	The maintainer or head of the educational institution may not conclude an agreement if, according to the school health service, the supply of goods does not comply with the recommendations	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Education sector	Hungary	National Association of Hungarian Dietitians	0	0	2012	https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=a1200020.emm	http://mdosz.hu/uj-taplalkozasi-ajanlasok-okos-tanyer/	
Nourishing	40	Regulation on the availability of soft drinks in school	banned the sale of unhealthy foods and beverages in Latvian schools and kindergartens	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Education sector	Latvia	Latvian Ministry of Health	0	0	2006	http://www.tvnet.lv/zinas/latvija/212736-aiqliedz-skolas-tirgot-neves-eligu-partiku-un-dzerienus		
Nourishing	41	Regulations on nutrition standards for educational institutions	Nutritional requirements for food provided in schools.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	Latvia	Latvian Ministry of Health	0	0	2012	https://likumi.lv/doc.php?id=245300		
Nourishing	42	Catering standards for schools	Catering standards for pre-schools, secondary schools and children's social care institutions.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	Lithuania	Lithuanian Ministry of Health	0	0	2011	https://www.e-tar.lt/portal/lt/legalAct/TAR.3B14F18E2B3C/YIUsixwN Lj		

Nourishing	43	Nutrition standards for school canteens	Nutrition standards for food and beverages served in school canteens, also regulating promotion and advertisement of food in schools.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	Poland	Polish Ministry of Health	0	0	2014	https://parenting.pl/rewolucja-na-szkolnych-stolowkach-od-1-wrzesnia		
Nourishing	44	Government Buying Standards (GBS) for food and catering services	All government departments and their related organisations must make sure that they meet the minimum mandatory Government Buying Standards (GBS) standards when buying goods and services.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Society at large	Procurement	Public Authorities	UK	UK Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs	0	0	2014	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/sustainable-procurement-the-gbs-for-food-and-catering-services	https://www.gov.uk/guidance/public-sector-procurement-policy#the-procurement-policy-framework	
Nourishing	45	Public Health Product Tax	The tax applies to certain categories of pre-packed food containing salt, sugar or caffeine exceeding a threshold level. The aim of the policy is to improve the health of the population.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Fiscal policy	Food industry	Hungary	Hungarian Ministry of Health, Ministry of Finance	0	0	2011	http://www.euro.who.int/_data/assets/pdf_file/0004/287095/Good-practice-brief-public-health-product-tax-in-hungary.pdf	Bíró, A. (2015). Did the junk food tax make the Hungarians eat healthier?. Food Policy, 54, 107-115.	
Nourishing	46	Charges on chocolate, sugar confectionery and sugar. Tax on non-alcoholic beverages (3.16, 3.17, 3.4)	This regulation applies to fees levied pursuant to the Act of 19 May 1933 No. 11 on excise duties.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Fiscal policy	Food industry	Norway	Norwegian Ministry of Finance	0	0	2001	https://lovdata.no/dokument/SF/forskrift/2001-12-11-1451?q=s%C3%A6ravgiftsfor skriften#KAPITTEL_3		
Nourishing	47	Charges on beverage packaging (environmental and basic tax, 3.5)	This regulation applies to fees levied pursuant to the Act of 19 May 1933 No. 11 on excise duties.	Reduced environmental impact	Resource efficiency and waste management	CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	Rethinking food packaging and labelling	Society at large	Fiscal policy	Food industry	Norway	Norwegian Ministry of Finance	0	0	2001	https://lovdata.no/dokument/SF/forskrift/2001-12-11-1451?q=s%C3%A6ravgiftsfor skriften#KAPITTEL_4		
Nourishing	48	Waste Regulations - Chapter 6. Return systems for packaging for beverages	The aim is to contribute to efficient return systems for packaging of beverages, so that those return systems could help reducing waste quantities from such packaging.	Reduced environmental impact	Resource efficiency and waste management	CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	Rethinking food packaging and labelling	Consumers	Fiscal policy	Consumers	Norway	Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment	1	0	2004	https://lovdata.no/dokument/SF/forskrift/2004-06-01-930?q=avfallsforskriften	https://lovdata.no/dokument/SF/forskrift/2004-06-01-930 KAPITTEL_6#KAPITTEL_6	
Nourishing	49	Code of Excise Tax - tax on non alcoholic beverages	tax on beverages containing added sugar or other sweeteners	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Fiscal policy	Food industry	Portugal	Portuguese Ministry of Health, Ministry of Finance	0	0	2017	https://www.pwc.pt/pt/pwcinforfisco/codigos/ciec.html	https://www.theguardian.com/society/2016/oct/15/portugal-to-levy-sugar-tax-on-soft-drinks-in-2017	http://www.nielsen.com/pt/pt/press-room/2017/tax-on-sugar-and-health-concern.html
Nourishing	50	Tax on packaged sugary drinks	the tax applies to those sugary drinks that contain added caloric sweeteners	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Fiscal policy	Food industry	Spain	Catalan regional government	0	0	2017	https://web.gencat.cat/en/actualitat/detall/Impost-sobre-begudes-ensucrades		
Nourishing	51	Healthy start scheme	If you're pregnant or have a child under 4, the Healthy Start scheme can help you buy basic foods like milk or fruit. Receive vouchers every week to spend on milk, plain fresh and frozen fruit and vegetables, and infant formula milk. You can also get free vitamins.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Food security in EU	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Income support	Consumers	UK	Department of Health - Northern Ireland	0	0	2006	https://www.gov.uk/healthy-start	https://www.healthystart.nhs.uk/	McFadden, A., Green, J. M., Williams, V., McLeish, J., McCormick, F., Fox-Rushby, J., & Renfrew, M. J. (2014). Can food vouchers improve nutrition and reduce health inequalities in low-income mothers and young children: a multi-method evaluation of the experiences of beneficiaries and practitioners of the Healthy Start programme in England. BMC public health, 14(1), 148.
Nourishing	52	Hungarian Aqua Promoting Programme in the Young (HAPPY)	Promoting water consumption and decreasing the consumption of sugary soft drinks among pre-school and primary school students through provision of free drinking water and education measures	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Education measure	School food services	Hungary	Hungarian National Institute of Pharmacy and Nutrition	0	0	2007	https://janpa-toolbox.eu/files/Hungary%202-HAPPY%20.pdf	https://www.ogyei.gov.hu/nyitodal/	Nagy, Barbara & Varga, Anita & Anna Kovács, Viktória & Erdei, Gergő & Bakacs, Marta & Martos, Éva. (2015). The Hungarian Aqua Promoting Programme in the Young (HAPPY) - A best practice, sustainable community-based intervention program in Hungary.
																	Scantlebury, R. J., Moody, A., Oyebo, O., & Mindell, J. S. (2018). Has the UK Healthy Start voucher scheme been associated with an increased fruit and vegetable intake among target families? Analysis of Health Survey for England data, 2001–2014. J Epidemiol Community Health, jech-2017.	

Nourishing	53	Sugar smart	national campaign to raise public awareness about the dangers of eating too much sugar on health and wellbeing. The aim is to help organisations and individuals to reduce the amount of sugar we all consume.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Consumers	UK	Jamie Oliver Food Foundation and Sustain	0	0	2015	https://www.sugarsmartuk.org/about/		
Nourishing	54	Nutrition online campaign	website to inform on how to eat well	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Consumers	Estonia	Estonian National Institute for Health Development	0	0		http://toitumine.ee/kuidas-tervislikult-toituda/toidusoovituse/d/magu-sad-ja-soolased-naksid/sool		
Nourishing	55	Salt intake reduction campaign	Awareness campaign, advertisements warning the public of the dangers of too much salt and work with the food industry to encourage product reformulation	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Consumers	UK	UK Food Standards Agency	0	0	2004	https://www.food.gov.uk/business-guidance/salt	Shankar, B., Brambila-Macias, J., Traill, B., Mazzocchi, M., & Capacci, S. (2013). An evaluation of the UK Food Standards Agency's salt campaign. <i>Health Economics</i> , 22(2), 243-250.	
Nourishing	56	Education on nutrition, health and food preparation in schools	Curriculum or classes on healthy diet, nutrition, food preparation	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Education measure	Education sector	Finland	Finnish government	0	0		https://www.wcrf.org/int/policy/nourishing-database		
Nourishing	57	Education on nutrition, health and food preparation in schools	Curriculum or classes on healthy diet, nutrition, food preparation	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Education measure	Education sector	Slovenia	Slovenian government	0	0		https://www.wcrf.org/int/policy/nourishing-database		
Nourishing	58	Education on nutrition, health and food preparation in schools	Curriculum or classes on healthy diet, nutrition, food preparation	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Education measure	Education sector	Germany	German Federal ministry of food and agriculture, Ministry of health	0	0		https://www.bmel.de/EN/Food/Healthy-Diet/_Texte/IN%20FORM.html		
Nourishing	59	Education on nutrition, health and food preparation in schools	Curriculum or classes on healthy diet, nutrition, food preparation	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Education measure	Education sector	UK	UK Department of education	0	0		https://www.nutrition.org.uk/foodinschools/curriculum/the-curriculum.html	https://www.in-form.de/	
Nourishing	60	Regulations on standards for school meals	The list of non-recommended foods for pre-schooler and school children is approved. In schools it is forbidden to sell the products which exceed limits set out in the list.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	Romania	Romanian Ministry of Public Health	0	0	2008	http://www.anpc.gov.ro/anpcftp/anpc_junior/ordin_1563_150218.pdf		
Nourishing	61	Law on school nutrition	Dietary guidelines for school nutrition: it regulates the organization of school meals for students.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	Slovenia	Slovenian Ministry of education, science and sport	0	0	2013	http://pisis.si/Pis.web/pregledPredpisa?id=ZAKO6564	http://www.mizs.gov.si/delovna_podrocja/direktorat_za_predsolsko_vzgojo_in_osnovno_solstvo/prehrana/	Gregorič, M., Pograjc, L., Pavlovec, A., Simčič, M., & Blenkuš, M. G. (2015). School nutrition guidelines: overview of the implementation and evaluation. <i>Public health nutrition</i> , 18(9), 1582-1592.
Nourishing	62	Education act	The Swedish School Law stipulates that school lunches must be nutritious, thus equal a third of the recommended daily intake of energy and nutrients.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	Sweden	Swedish Ministry of Education and Research, National Food Agency	0	0	2011	https://www.livsmedelverket.se/en/food-habits-health-and-environment/maltider-i-varld-skola-och-omsorg/skola	https://www.livsmedelverket.se/globalassets/english/food-habits-health-environment/public-meals/good_school_meals.pdf	Emma Patterson, Liselotte Schäfer Elinder; Improvements in school meal quality in Sweden after the introduction of new legislation—a 2-year follow-up, <i>European Journal of Public Health</i> , Volume 25, Issue 4, 1 August 2015, Pages 655–660, https://doi.org/10.1093/eurpub/cku184
Nourishing	63	School food regulation	Legislation applies to food provided within schools in England.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	UK- England	UK Department for Education	0	0	2014	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/standards-for-school-food-in-england	http://www.schoolfoodplan.com/actions/school-food-standards/	

Nourishing	64	The Nutritional Requirements for Food and Drink in Schools	School meals requirements.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	School food services	UK-Scotland	Food Standards Scotland, NHS Health Scotland and Education Scotland	0	0	2008	https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ssi/2008/265/contents/made
Nourishing	65	Nutritional standards for school lunches and other food in schools	Nutritional standards for school lunches and other food in schools.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	UK-Northern Ireland	Northern Ireland Government	0	0	2007	https://www.education-ni.gov.uk/articles/nutritional-standards
Nourishing	66	The Healthy Eating in Schools (Nutritional Standards and Requirements)	It states the type of food which can and can't be provided by schools. Initiative to improve the catering offer for children and adolescents at the school buffet. An offer that is based on nutritional recommendations, meets physiological needs and supports health-promoting nutritional behavior.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	UK-Wales	Welsh government	0	0	2013	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/wsi/2013/1984/made http://learning.gov.wales/docs/learningwales/publications/160226-healthy-eating-maintained-schools-en-v2.pdf
Nourishing	67	Our School Buffet		Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	School food services	Austria	Austrian Federal Ministry of Health and Women's affairs	0	0	2012	https://www.bmgf.gv.at/home/Schwerpunkte/Ernaehrung/Unser_Schulbuffet
Nourishing	68	School food policy	Policy for Promoting Healthy Dietary and Physical Attitudes for Children and Youth.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	School food services	Belgium - Wallonia	Government of the French Community, Ministry of Health, of Obligatory Education and of Sport	0	0	2013	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/sites/jrcsh/files/jrc-school-food-policy-factsheet-belgium_wallonia_en.pdf
Nourishing	69	Healthy eating at school	Practical guide for the development of a balanced diet and food supply at school.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	School food services	Belgium - Flanders	Belgian Ministry of Education and Flemish Institute for Health Promotion and Disease Prevention	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/sites/jrcsh/files/jrc-school-food-policy-factsheet-belgium_flanders_en.pdf
Nourishing	70	Quality standards for school meals	The DGE quality standards show in detail how balanced nutrition should look for children in schools.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	School food services	Germany	German Ministry of Health, Ministry of Food and Agriculture	0	0	2011	https://www.dge.de/gv/dge-qualitaetsstandards/ https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/sites/jrcsh/files/jrc-school-food-policy-factsheet-germany_en.pdf
Nourishing	71	Healthy Eating Lifestyle Plan (HELP)	Outlines the goals and highlights the school environment, school curriculum and school nutrition as the three key objectives for this initiative.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	School food services	Malta	Maltese Ministry of Education, Youth and Employment	0	0	2007	https://education.gov.mt/en/resources/Documents/Policy%20Documents/healthy%20eating%20lifestyle%20plan.pdf https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/sites/jrcsh/files/jrc-school-food-policy-factsheet-malta_en.pdf
Nourishing	72	School lunch guidelines	Nutrient-based standards for lunch taking into account the principles of Good Hygienic Practice and the HACCP system for school meals.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	School food services	Poland	Polish Ministry of Health	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/sites/jrcsh/files/jrc-school-food-policy-factsheet-poland_en.pdf
Nourishing	73	Special measures directed to the school environment (Ley 17/2011, Art 40)	The sale of foods and beverages with a high content of saturated fatty acids, trans fatty acids, salt and sugars will not be allowed in schools. Children's schools will be spaces protected from advertising.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Health	0	0	2011	https://www.boe.es/buscar/pdf/2011/BOE-A-2011-11604-consolidado.pdf
Nourishing	74	Consensus document on food in educational centres	The competent authorities will ensure that the meals served in schools are varied, balanced and adapted to the nutritional needs of each age group. They will be supervised by professionals with accredited training in human nutrition and dietetics.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	School food services	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Education, Culture and Sport; Ministry of Health, Social Services and Equality	0	0	2010	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/sites/jrcsh/files/jrc-school-food-policy-factsheet-spain_en.pdf

Nourishing	75	Law No. 2004-806 on public health policy (Art.30)	Pay and food vending machines accessible to students are prohibited in schools	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Education sector	France	French government	0	0	2004	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000000787078&categorieLien=cid	Capacci, S., Mazzocchi, M. and Shankar, B. (2018), Breaking Habits: The Effect of the French Vending Machine Ban on School Snacking and Sugar Intakes. J. Pol. Anal. Manage., 37: 88-111. doi:10.1002/pam.22032
Nourishing	76	School Nutrition Act (Art 4)	In the area of school and educational institutions and on the surface belonging to school premises, vending machines for distribution of food and beverage must not be installed.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Education sector	Slovenia	Slovenian Ministry of Education, Science and Sport, Ministry of Health	0	0	2013	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/sites/jrcsh/files/jrc-school-food-policy-factsheet-slovenia_en.pdf	https://www.uradni-list.si/glasilo-uradni-list-rs/vsebina/111596
Nourishing	77	National guidelines for the school catering	The aim is to facilitate the adoption of correct eating habits for health promotion and the prevention of chronic-degenerative diseases.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	School food services	Italy	Italian ministry of Health	0	0	2010	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/sites/jrcsh/files/jrc-school-food-policy-factsheet-italy_en.pdf	http://www.salute.gov.it/imgs/_17_publicazioni_1248_allegato.pdf
Nourishing	78	Guidelines for the school meal	Guidelines for the school meal.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	School food services	Norway	Norwegian Directorate of Health	0	0	2003	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/sites/jrcsh/files/jrc-school-food-policy-factsheet-norway_en.pdf	https://helsedirektoratet.no/Lists/Publikasjoner/Attachments/492/Retningslinjer-for-skolem%C3%A5stidet-IS-0048.pdf
Nourishing	79	Regulation on nutrition prescriptions for public catering	Regulation on food offered in schools.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	Hungary	Hungarian Ministry of Human Resources	0	0	2014	http://njt.hu/cgi_bin/njt_doc.cgi?docid=169011.268148	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/sites/jrcsh/files/jrc-school-food-policy-factsheet-hungary_en.pdf
Nourishing	80	Organization of catering in pre-school education, general education schools and children's social care institutions	Regulation on food offered in schools.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	School food services	Lithuania	Lithuanian Ministry of Health	0	0	2011	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/sites/jrcsh/files/jrc-school-food-policy-factsheet-lithuania_en.pdf	https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/TAIS.411986
Nourishing	81	Guidelines for the school meal	Guidelines for the school meal.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	School food services	Netherlands	Dutch Ministry of Education, Science and Culture and Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport	0	0	2011	https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/sites/jrcsh/files/jrc-school-food-policy-factsheet-netherlands_en.pdf	http://gezondeschoolkantine.voedingscentrum.nl/nl.aspx
Nourishing	82	Regulation on Energy Drinks advertising	prohibited to promote energy drinks in all places involving persons under the age of 18 years	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Media	Lithuania	Lithuanian Ministry of Health	0	0		https://sam.lrv.lt/lt/veiklos-sritys/visuomenes-sveikatos-prieziura/mityba-ir-fizinis-aktyvumas-2/vaiku	
Nourishing	83	Ban on selling Energy Drinks to Minors	Law that prohibits the sale of energy drinks to children under the age of 18 years .	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Retailers	Lithuania	Lithuanian Ministry of Health	0	0	2014	https://sam.lrv.lt/lt/veiklos-sritys/visuomenes-sveikatos-prieziura/mityba-ir-fizinis-aktyvumas-2/vaiku	
Nourishing	84	Basic Requirements and Certain Restrictions of Commercial Advertising Activities (Act XLVIII, article 8)	Advertising activities shall be prohibited in a dormitory which provides primary care and pre-school child care facilities, kindergarten, elementary school and primary school pupils.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Education sector	Hungary	Hungarian Government	0	0	2008	http://njt.hu/cgi_bin/njt_doc.cgi?docid=117843.338492	
Nourishing	85	Salt agreement with the Hungarian Baker Association	representatives of the Hungarian bakers committed to reduce the salt content of bread to a certain target; a number of companies reported voluntary salt reduction programs to the government	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Food industry	Hungary	Hungarian Government	0	1	2012	https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/health/files/nutrition_physical_activity/docs/salt_report1_en.pdf	Trieu, K., Neal, B., Hawkes, C., Dunford, E., Campbell, N., Rodriguez-Fernandez, R., ... & Webster, J. (2015). Salt reduction initiatives around the world—a systematic review of progress towards the global target. PloS one, 10(7), e0130247.

Nourishing	86	Salt reduction in bread	pledges by bakers associations to reduce the salt content in bread	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Food industry	Italy	Italian Ministry of Health	0	1	2009	http://www.salute.gov.it/portale/temi/p2_6.jsp?lingua=italiano&id=1400&area=stiliVita&menu=protocoll			
Nourishing	87	Salt reduction in frozen foods	pledges by food producers associations to reduce the salt content in frozen foods	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Food industry	Italy	Italian Ministry of Health	0	1	2014	http://www.salute.gov.it/portale/news/p3_2_1_1_1.jsp?lingua=italiano&menu=notizie&p=dalministero&id=1796			
Nourishing	88	National Agreement to Improve Product Composition	The purpose of the National Agreement To Improve Product Composition is to reduce the salt, unsaturated fat and calorie content (sugar and fat) of products. This will result in a healthier range of products.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Food industry	Netherlands	Dutch Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport and food industry and retail associations	0	1	2014-2020	http://www.akkoordverbeteringproductamenstelling.nl/en	Temme, E. H. M., Hendriksen, M. A. H., Milder, I. E. J., Toxopeus, I. B., Westenbrink, S., Brants, H. A. M., & van der A, D. L. (2017). Salt Reductions in Some Foods in The Netherlands: Monitoring of Food Composition and Salt Intake. <i>Nutrients</i> , 9(7), 791. http://doi.org/10.3390/nu9070791		
Nourishing	89	Royal Decree relating to breads and other products of the bakery	Compositional requirements for bread made in bakeries. The content of cooking salt may not be greater than 2.0%	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	Belgium	Belgian Ministry of Public health and Ministry of Economic Affairs	0	0	1985	http://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/cgi_loi/change_lg.pl?language=fr&la=F&table_name=loi&cn=1985090231	https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/health/files/nutrition_physical_activity/docs/ev20091021_wagemans_en.pdf		
Nourishing	90	Limits for salt content in bread	Limits for salt content for bread and some other bakery products	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	Hungary	Hungarian Government	0	0	2012	https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/health/files/nutrition_physical_activity/docs/salt_report_1_en.pdf			
Nourishing	91	Limits for salt content in bread	Limits for salt content for bread	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	Netherlands	Dutch Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport	0	0	2012	https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/health/files/nutrition_physical_activity/docs/salt_report_1_en.pdf			
Nourishing	92	Salt content reduction in dehydrated products	voluntarily reduce the sodium content in branded dehydrated culinary products to at least half the recommended daily amount, ie 1.2 grams of sodium or less, per serving.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Food industry	Czech Republic	Food Chamber of the Czech Republic	0	1	2009-2014	http://www.foodnet.cz/polozka/?jmeno=Zbyte%C4%8Dn%C3%A1+s%C5%AF+z+potravin+bude+mizet+&id=19310			
Nourishing	93	Charters of voluntary commitments of nutritional progress	validation by the public authorities of voluntary commitments taken by a company of the food field mainly concerned with the improvement of the nutritional quality of food products that it puts on the market.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Food industry	France	French ministry of solidarity and health	0	1	2013	http://solidarites-sante.gouv.fr/prevention-en-sante/preserver-sa-sante/le-programme-national-nutrition-sante/article/les-chartes-d-engagements-volontaires-de-progres-nutritionnel	https://www.oqali.fr/Publications-Oqali/Etudes-transversales	Combris, Pierre & Enderli, Géraldine & Gauvreau Béziat, Julie & Ménard, Céline & Soler, Louis-Georges & Spiteri, Marine & Volatier, Jean-Luc. (2014). Interventions publiques et démarches d'entreprises pour l'amélioration de la qualité nutritionnelle de l'offre alimentaire : apports et limites. <i>Cahiers de Nutrition et de Diététique</i> , 49, 10.1016/j.cnd.2013.12.001.	
Nourishing	94	Salt reduction programme	Salt Reduction Undertakings by the Food Industry	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Food industry	Ireland	Food Safety Authority of Ireland	0	1	2003-2012	https://www.fsai.ie/science_and_health/salt_and_health.html	https://www.fsai.ie/science_and_health/salt_commitments_and_updates.html	https://www.fsai.ie/science_and_health/salt_and_health/salt_commitments/salt_reduction_presentation.html	
Nourishing	95	Salt reduction agreement with bakers	Reduction in the percentage of salt used in bread making	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Food industry	Spain	Spanish Confederation of Bakery Organizations, Ministry of health	0	1	2005	http://www.aecosan.msssi.gob.es/AECOSAN/docs/documentos/nutricion/jornadas_debate.pdf	https://elpais.com/sociedad/2005/02/10/actualidad/1107990001_850215.html	http://www.ceopan.es/index.php?type=public&zone=items&action=view&categoryID=284&codeID=280	

Nourishing	96	Public Health Responsibility Deal - Food industry pledges on nutritional content	Pledges by the food industry to reformulate products to reduce salt, saturated fats and trans fats	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Food industry	UK	UK department of Health	0	1	2011-2015	http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20180201175857/https://responsibilitydeal.dh.gov.uk/pledges/	Knai, C., Petticrew, M., Durand, M. A., Eastmure, E., James, L., Mehrotra, A., ... & Mays, N. (2015). Has a public-private partnership resulted in action on healthier diets in England? An analysis of the Public Health Responsibility Deal food pledges. <i>Food Policy</i> , 54, 1-10.
Nourishing	97	Public Health Responsibility Deal - Food industry pledges on calories reduction	Pledges by the food industry to reformulate products to reduce calories	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Food industry	UK	UK department of Health	0	1	2011-2015	http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20180201180608/https://responsibilitydeal.dh.gov.uk/pledges/pledge/?pl=23	
Nourishing	98	Mandatory limits for salt content	Mandatory maximum level of salt in bread, milk, meat and poultry products	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	Bulgaria	Bulgarian government	0	0	2011	https://ec.europa.eu/health/sites/health/files/nutrition_physical_activity/docs/salt_report_1_en.pdf	
Nourishing	99	Maximum limits of salt content in bread	Mandatory maximum level of salt in bread	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	Portugal	Portuguese Ministry of Health	0	0	2009	http://www.asae.gov.pt/seguranca-alimentar/informacoes-sobre-atividades-economicas-na-area-alimentar/pao.aspx	
Nourishing	100	Trans-fatty acids regulation	It is prohibited to produce or place on the market foods containing more than 2g / 100g of trans fatty acids in total fat.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	Austria	Austrian Federal Minister of Health	0	0	2009	https://www.ris.bka.gv.at/GeltendeFassung.wxe?Abfrage=Bundesnormen&Gesetzesnummer=20006420 https://www.sozialversicherung.at/cdscontent/?portal=forumgesundheitportal&contentid=10007688460&viewmode=content&portal:componentId=gtn8bd22a65-38a5-4975-ace1-084644e4de2e	
Nourishing	101	Trans fat ban	Ban of industrially-produced trans fats	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	Denmark	Danish government	0	0	2003	https://www.wcrf.org/int/policy/nourishing-database	Restrepo, B. J., & Rieger, M. (2016). Denmark's policy on artificial trans fat and cardiovascular disease. <i>American journal of preventive medicine</i> , 50(1), 69-76.
Nourishing	102	Maximum limits of trans fatty acids in foodstuffs	Regulation on the maximum permissible quantities of trans fatty acids in foodstuffs, the conditions for the marketing and control of trans fatty acids and the monitoring of trans fatty acid in the population	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	Hungary	Hungarian government	0	0	2013	http://portal.nebih.gov.hu/-/tajekoztato-a-transz-zsirsavakrol https://portal.nebih.gov.hu/documents/10182/406632/4-6-4_Transzszs%3C%ADrsavak.pdf/e289ba45-3002-44cf-b4a6-6878713f46f8 https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A1300071.EM&celpara=#xcelparam	
Nourishing	103	Restriction of trans-fatty acids in foodstuffs	The restrictions are designed to improve the nutritional habits of the population of Latvia and thus improve public health indicators in the long term.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	Latvia	Latvian Government	0	0	2016	https://www.mk.gov.lv/lv/aktualitates/nosaka-maksimali-pielaujamo-transtaukskabjudaudzumu-partikas-produktos	
Nourishing	104	Regulation on trans fatty acids in foods	This regulation will help promote health in the population by limiting the content of industrially produced trans fatty acids in foods.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	Norway	Norwegian Ministry of Health and Care Services	0	0	2014	https://lovdata.no/dokument/LTI/forskrift/2014-01-16-34 http://www.matportalen.no/matvaregrupper/tema/margarin_sm_or_matojje_ol/strengere_regulering_av_transfett	
Nourishing	105	Code of Broadcast Advertising	CAP broadcast code covers issues including taste, decency and product placement. As well as setting standards about accuracy and honesty businesses must stick to, they also have rules about things like scheduling.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Media	UK	UK Advertising Standards Authority	0	0	2010	https://www.asa.org.uk/asset/846f25eb-f474-47c1-ab3ff571e3db5910.97855-baf-833f-4b75-9e10729e8807c7b8/ https://www.asa.org.uk/codes-and-rulings/advertising-codes/broadcast-code.html https://www.gov.uk/market-ing-advertising-law/advertising-codes-of-practice	Whalen, R., Harrold, J., Child, S., Halford, J., & Boyland, E. (2017). Children's exposure to food advertising: the impact of statutory restrictions. <i>Health promotion international</i> .

Nourishing	106	Consumer Ombudsman's guidelines	The primary aim is to supervise that the Consumer Protection Act and other laws passed to protect consumers are observed. Particular attention is paid to ensuring that marketing activities, contractual terms, and collection activities conform to the laws.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Media	Finland	Finnish Competition and Consumer Authority	0	0	2004	https://www.kkv.fi/en/decisions-and-publications/publications/consumer-ombudsmans-guidelines-by-trade/children-and-foodstuffs-marketing/	https://www.kkv.fi/en/about-us/the-consumer-ombudsman/
Nourishing	107	Mandatory health message in advertisement	Mandatory health messages in advertising of processed food and drinks, and food and drinks with added sugar, fats, and salt.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Media	France	French Ministry of Health and Solidarity and Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries	0	0	2007	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000000426255&categorieLien=id	http://inpes.santepubliquefrance.fr/70000/cp/08/cp080204.asp
Nourishing	108	Code of Responsible Food Marketing communication to children	The food, grocery and media and advertising industries have agreed on a voluntary code not to advertise foods with high levels of fat, sugar and salt in media aimed at children.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Media	Denmark	Forum of Responsible Food Marketing Communication	0	0	2014	https://kodeksforfoedevareklamer.di.dk/Pages/forside.aspx	https://kodeksforfoedevareklamer.di.dk/SiteCollectionDocuments/Code%20with%20guide%20english%20october%202014%20-%20endelig1.pdf
Nourishing	109	Memorandum of Cooperation on the advertising of soft drinks to children	Changes in the advertising of soft-drinks to children	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Media	Latvia	Latvian Ministry of Health and Federation of Latvian Food Operators	0	0	2011	http://www.vm.gov.lv/lv/aktualitates/preses_relizes/3135_nosledz_sadarbibas_memorandu_par_izmainam_uz_berniem_verstu/	
Nourishing	110	Advertising of Food and Beverages addressed to Children - PAOS code	Code of self-regulation of food and drink advertisement aimed at minors for prevention of obesity and health	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Media	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Health and Consumer Affairs	0	0	2005	http://www.aecosan.msssi.gob.es/AECOSAN/docs/documentos/nutricion/Nuevo_Codigo_PAOS_2012_espagnol.pdf	
Nourishing	111	Subsidies for supporting healthy meals at universities	To qualify for a grant to reduce the price of student meal, it is necessary that student meals meet quality, health and nutritional requirements.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Fiscal policy	School food services	Finland	Finnish Ministry of Culture	0	0	2003	http://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/alkup/2003/20030564	
SCAR	112	Research Stimulus Fund	The Research Stimulus Fund provides funding to the Irish research institutes for 'public good' agricultural production related research. The main aims of the programme are to support sustainable and competitive agricultural production practices.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Farmers	R&I economic	Research sector	Ireland	Ireland Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine	1	0	2010-2016	https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/research/competitivenationalprogrammes/researchstimulusfund/	
SCAR	113	Food Institutional Research Measure (FIRM)	Primary national funding mechanism for food research in higher education institutions and other public research institutes.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	Farmers	R&I economic	Research sector	Ireland	Ireland Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine	0	0	2010-2015	https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/research/competitivenationalprogrammes/	https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/research/competitivenationalprogrammes/foodinstitutionalresearchmeasurefirm/
SCAR	114	Beef Data and Genomics Programme (BDGP)	The Programme aims to lower the intensity of greenhouse gas emissions by improving the quality and efficiency of the national beef herd. It consists of six years of payments to farmers for completion of actions aimed at delivering accelerated genetic improvement in the national herd and improvement of its environmental sustainability.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	NA	Society at large	Income support	Farmers	Ireland	Ireland Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine	0	0	2017-2022	https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/beef/schemes/	https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/media/migration/farmingschemesandpayments/beefdataprogrammebdp/2017/BeefDataandGenomicsProgramme20172022TermsandConditionsrevised191217.pdf
SCAR	115	Knowledge Transfer Programme	The programme facilitates the transfer of information from research and advisory services to farmer discussion group networks.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	Farmers	Information measure	Farmers	Ireland	Ireland Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine	0	0	2016-2017	https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/farmerschemespayments/knowledgegettransferktprogramme/	https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/media/migration/farmingschemesandpayments/knowledgegettransferktlaunchpresentation181016.pdf
SCAR	116	Green, Low-Carbon, Agri-Environment Scheme - GLAS	The Scheme incentivises agricultural production methods to address issues of climate change, water quality and biodiversity loss.	Reduced Environmental impact	Multiple subgoals	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	NA	Society at large	Income support	Farmers	Ireland	Ireland Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine	0	0	2014-2020	https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/farmerschemespayments/glas/	https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/media/migration/farmingschemesandpayments/glastructure1/GLASstructure240215.pdf

SCAR	117	Organic Capital Investment Scheme (OCIS)	OCIS facilitates the development of the organic sector, so as to ensure a regular supply of high quality organic produce to the market.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Society at large	Income support	Farmers	Ireland	Ireland Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine	0	0	2014-2021	https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/farmingsectors/organicfarming/organicscheme/organicfarmingscheme/	https://www.agriculture.gov.ie/media/migration/farmingsectors/organicfarming/organicscheme/OCISTermsCond120517.pdf
SCAR	118	Catchment Sensitive Farming	It raises awareness on diffuse water pollution from agriculture.	Reduced Environmental impact	Water and soil management	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Society at large	Information measure	Farmers	UK	UK Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs	0	0	2014-2016	https://www.gov.uk/topic/farming-food-grants-payments/rural-grants-payments	https://www.gov.uk/guidance/catchment-sensitive-farming-reduce-agricultural-water-pollution
SCAR	119	Countryside Productivity Scheme	provides funding for projects in England which improve productivity in the farming and forestry sectors and help create jobs and growth in the rural economy.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Engaging citizens in food systems and science policy	Farmers	R&I economic	Farmers	UK	UK Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs	1	0	2017-2018	https://www.gov.uk/topic/farming-food-grants-payments/rural-grants-payments	https://www.gov.uk/guidance/countryside-productivity-scheme
SCAR	120	Countryside Stewardship	It provides financial incentives for land managers to look after their environment by: conserving and restoring wildlife habitats, flood risk management, woodland creation and management, reducing widespread water pollution from agriculture, keeping the character of the countryside, preserving historical features in the landscape, encouraging educational access.	Reduced Environmental impact	Multiple subgoals	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	NA	Society at large	Income support	Farmers	UK	UK Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs	1	0	2015-2018	https://www.gov.uk/topic/farming-food-grants-payments/rural-grants-payments	https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/countryside-stewardship-get-paid-for-environmental-land-management
SCAR	121	The Reduction and Prevention of Agricultural Diffuse Pollution	The Regulation provides new rules for all farmers in England to tackle diffuse water pollution from agriculture.	Reduced Environmental impact	Water and soil management	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Society at large	Regulation	Farmers	UK	UK Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs	0	0	2018	https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/695598/farming-rules-for-water-from-april-2018/farming-rules-for-water-overview	https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/695598/farming-rules-for-water-policy-paper-v2.pdf
SCAR	122	The Sea Fish (Marketing Standards) (England and Wales and Northern Ireland) Regulations 2018	fishery products may be marketed only if they meet the requirements of the Regulation	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	UK	UK Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs; Marine Management Organisation	0	0	2018	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/buyers-and-sellers-of-first-sale-fish-and-submission-of-sales-notes/processing-presentation-and-marketing-information-for-fish	
SCAR	123	Farming Ammonia Reduction Grant Scheme	One-to-one on-farm advice on ways to reduce emissions and 100% grants for slurry store covers.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Society at large	Income support	Farmers	UK	UK Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs	0	0	2016-2017	https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/farming-ammonia-reduction-grant-scheme-claim-form-and-offer-terms/guide-to-farming-ammonia-reduction-grant-scheme	https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/env/documents/2017/AR/WGSR/8_Farming_Ammonia_Reduction_Grant_Scheme_Finonuala_Byrne.pdf
SCAR	124	Agri-tech catalyst	Funding for collaborative projects, taking innovative ideas from any sector or discipline to tackle challenges in agriculture. Agri-tech Catalyst funding scheme helps businesses and researchers commercialise their research and develop innovative solutions to global challenges in the agri-tech sector.	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Global FNS	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Third countries	R&I economic	Industry-based research	UK	UK Department for International Development	1	0	2015	https://www.gov.uk/international-development-funding/the-agri-tech-catalyst	https://connect.innovateuk.org/web/biosciencesktn/agri-tech-catalyst
SCAR	125	R&I fiscal measures	measures for all companies that want to seize the opportunities related to the fourth industrial revolution.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	Food industry	R&I economic	Food industry	Italy	Italian Ministry of Economic Development, Ministry of Education, Ministry of Economy and Finance, Ministry of Labour and Social Policy, Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Environment and Protection of Land and Sea	0	0	2017-2019	http://www.mise.gov.it/images/stories/documenti/2017_01_16-Industria_40_English.pdf	http://www.mise.gov.it/index.php/it/industria40
SCAR	126	Competence centers	The measure promotes the establishment of highly specialized competence centers on Industry 4.0 issues, in the form of public-private partnerships	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Food industry	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Italy	Italian Ministry of Economic Development, Ministry of Education, Ministry of Economy and Finance, Ministry of Labour and Social Policy, Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Environment and	0	0	2017-2019	http://www.mise.gov.it/images/stories/documenti/2017_01_16-Industria_40_English.pdf	http://www.mise.gov.it/index.php/it/industria40

											Protection of Land and Sea								
SCAR	127	Startups and innovative SMEs	New innovative start-ups enjoy a dedicated framework in matters such as administrative simplification, the labor market, tax breaks, bankruptcy law.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	SMEs	R&I regulation	SMEs	Italy	Italian Ministry of Economic Development, Ministry of Education, Ministry of Economy and Finance, Ministry of Labour and Social Policy, Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Environment and Protection of Land and Sea	0	0	2017-2019	http://www.mise.gov.it/images/stories/documenti/2017_01_16-Industria_40_English.pdf	http://www.mise.gov.it/index.php/it/industria40		
SCAR	128	Guarantee Fund for SMEs	The Fund facilitates access to financial sources of small and medium-sized enterprises through the granting of a public guarantee that accompanies and often replaces the real guarantees brought by the companies.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	SMEs	SME support	SMEs	Italy	Italian Ministry of Economic Development	0	0	2000	http://www.mise.gov.it/index.php/it/incentivi/impresa/fondo-di-garanzia-per-le-pmi	http://www.fondidigaranzia.it/		
SCAR	129	National Research, Development and Innovation Fund (Article 29, 41)	The NKFI Fund is a separate state fund for public support for R & D and innovation, and exclusively for that purpose.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	SMEs	R&I economic	SMEs	Hungary	National Office for Research, Development and Innovation	0	0	2014	http://njt.hu/cgi_bin/njt_doc.cgi?docid=173572.287758	http://nkfih.gov.hu/szakpolitika-strategia/fontosabb-jogszabalyok	http://njt.hu/cgi_bin/njt_doc.cgi?docid=172811.328188#foot1	http://nkfih.gov.hu/funding/portfolio-of-calls-to-calls-of-the-national
SCAR	130	National Research, Development and Innovation Fund-NKFIA (Article 48)	The NKFI Fund is a separate state fund for public support for R & D and innovation, and exclusively for that purpose.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Food industry	R&I economic	Research sector	Hungary	National Office for Research, Development and Innovation	0	0	2014	http://njt.hu/cgi_bin/njt_doc.cgi?docid=173572.287758	http://nkfih.gov.hu/szakpolitika-strategia/fontosabb-jogszabalyok	http://njt.hu/cgi_bin/njt_doc.cgi?docid=172811.328188#foot1	
SCAR	131	National Research, Development and Innovation Fund-NKFIA (Article 43)	The NKFI Fund is a separate state fund for public support for R & D and innovation, and exclusively for that purpose.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Fisheries	R&I economic	Research sector	Hungary	National Office for Research, Development and Innovation	0	0	2014	http://njt.hu/cgi_bin/njt_doc.cgi?docid=173572.287758	http://nkfih.gov.hu/szakpolitika-strategia/fontosabb-jogszabalyok	http://njt.hu/cgi_bin/njt_doc.cgi?docid=172811.328188#foot1	investment-in-the-future-RDStrategy2020 pag 48
SCAR	132	Regulation on the animal welfare rules for slaughter	Regulation on the animal welfare rules for slaughter.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	NA	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	Hungary	Hungarian government	0	0	2012	http://www.njt.hu/cgi_bin/njt_doc.cgi?docid=157809.234623			
SCAR	133	Decree on the protection of waters against nitrate pollution from agricultural sources	The purpose of the Regulation is to protect water against nitrate pollution from agricultural sources and to reduce the existing nitrate contamination of waters. It is forbidden to introduce slurry, fertilizer, and leachate waters of manure deposits into the waters.	Reduced Environmental impact	Water and soil management	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	Hungary	Hungarian government	0	0	2006	https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=a0600027.kor			
SCAR	134	Certified Hungarian Food label	aim of distinguishing high-quality Hungarian foods from the market	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Hungary	Hungarian Ministry of Agriculture	0	0	1998	http://elelmiszerlanc.kormany.hu/altalanos-informaciok-a-kme-programrol			
SCAR	135	SBIR- Small Business Innovation Research	SBIR is a competition in which the companies with the best offers receive an assignment for a feasibility study. Companies with the most promising feasibility studies are instructed to further develop their products.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	Consumers	R&I economic	Food industry	Netherlands	Dutch Enterprise Agency	0	0		https://www.rvo.nl/subsidies-regelingen/sbir?wssl=1	https://business.gov.nl/subsidy-small-business-innovation-research/		
SCAR	136	EKO label	Not only a certified organic product, but relates to ecology, health, fairness and care. EKO quality mark 2017 for sustainable organic products.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Netherlands	EKO quality mark	1	0	2017	https://www.eko-keurmerk.nl/faq			

SCAR	137	GMO indication on food label	required producers to indicate on the label if a food product contains more than 0.9% genetically modified ingredients. In this case the words "genetically modified" or "produced with genetically modified" are placed before the name of the ingredient.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Netherlands	Dutch Ministry for Economic affairs and Climate policy	0	0	2004	https://www.government.nl/topics/biotechnology/labelling-of-foods-and-products-containing-gmos
SCAR	138	Stimulation of Sustainable Energy Production (SDE+)	Producers receive financial compensation for the renewable energy they generate. SDE+ compensates producers for a fixed number of years, depending on the technology used.	Reduced Environmental impact	Resource efficiency and waste management	CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	Tackling primary production waste streams	Society at large	Fiscal policy	Farmers	Netherlands	Dutch Enterprise Agency, Ministry for Economic affairs and Climate policy	1	0	2018	https://english.rvo.nl/subsidies-programmes/sde
SCAR	139	Activities Decree	This Decree contains rules for - among others- odour and ammonia from livestock farming.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	NA	Society at large	Regulation	Farmers	Netherlands	Dutch Ministry of Infrastructures and Water Management	0	0		https://rwsenvironment.eu/subjects/agriculture/ https://rwsenvironment.eu/subjects/environmental-0/activities-decree/
SCAR	140	Soil Quality Decree	The Soil Quality Decree guarantees an unequivocal policy on sustainable soil management.	Reduced Environmental impact	Water and soil management	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Society at large	Regulation	Farmers	Netherlands	Dutch Ministry of Infrastructures and Water Management	0	0	2007	https://rwsenvironment.eu/subjects/soil/legislation-and/ https://rwsenvironment.eu/subjects/soil/legislation-and/soil-quality-decree/
SCAR	141	Top Sector Agri & Food	Top Sector Agri & Food stimulates new knowledge and innovations, first and foremost by creating and financing research and innovation projects. This does not just include fundamental and applied research, but also valorisation.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Consumers	R&I economic	Food industry	Netherlands	Top Sector Agri & Food	1	0		https://topsectoragrifood.nl/en/over/ https://topsectoragrifood.nl/en/c-ofinanciering/
SCAR	142	National Beekeeping Program	The Program sets out the conditions for the granting of Community aid for beekeeping and the modalities for payment and control of the actions submitted for this purpose.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	NA	Farmers	Fiscal policy	Farmers	Romania	Romanian Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development	1	0	2017-2019	http://www.madr.ro/programul-national-apicol.html
SCAR	143	Agricultura Ecologica - AE logo	The "ae" logo is used for certification-identification of organic food products and guarantees that agri-food products bearing this logo come from organic farming in Romania.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Romania	Romanian Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry, National Consumer Protection Authority	0	0	2002	http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliuDocumentAfis/81347 http://www.madr.ro/agricultura-ecologica/sigle-agricultura-ecologica.html http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliuDocumentAfis/21942
SCAR	144	Traditional Romanian product	Logo and regulation for traditional Romanian Food products	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Romania	Romanian Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry, Ministry of Health, National Consumer Protection Authority	0	0	2013	http://www.madr.ro/industria-alimentara.html http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliuDocument/152468
SCAR	145	Law on safety of food and feed	This law provides the basis for ensuring a high level of protection of public health and consumers' interests with regard to food, taking into account the diversity of food sources, ensuring the efficient functioning of the national market.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Industry-based research	Romania	Romanian government	0	0	2004	http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliuDocument/77221
SCAR	146	Regulation on food supplements	Food supplements may only be marketed in Romania if they comply with the provisions of these standards.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	Romania	Romanian Ministry of Health	0	0	2007	http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliuDocumentAfis/83380
SCAR	147	GMO regulation	ensure the traceability of products containing genetically modified organisms, to facilitate appropriate labeling, monitoring of environmental effects and, where necessary, the withdrawal of products from the market.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	Romania	Romanian government	1	0	2006	http://legislatie.just.ro/Public/DetaliuDocument/69535

SCAR	148	Phytosanitary Strategy - Phytosanitary Police	The Phytosanitary Police is empowered to carry out controls, to detect contraventions and to apply sanctions in accordance with the legislation in force. The aims are: sustainability and competitiveness of agriculture, food safety and environmental protection.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	Romania	Romanian Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development	0	0	2015	http://www.madr.ro/politia-fitosanitara.html	http://www.madr.ro/strategia-in-domeniul-fitosanitar.html
SCAR	149	Environment Fund	Significant amounts are allocated from the Environment Fund for programs and projects aimed at environmental protection.	Reduced Environmental impact	Multiple subgoals	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	NA	Consumers	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Romania	Romanian Ministry of Environment, Waters and Forests	0	0		http://mmediu.ro/categorie/minister/6	
SCAR	150	Sustainable Innovation in Food and Bio-based Industries	The programme will promote research and innovation that enhances value creation in Norway's bio-based industries.	Reduced Environmental impact	Resource efficiency and waste management	CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	NA	Consumers	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Norway	Research Council of Norway	1	0	2012	https://www.forskingsradet.no/prognett-bioner/Programme_description/1253971968649	
SCAR	151	Large-scale Programme on Aquaculture Research (HAVBRUK2)	The primary objective of the HAVBRUK2 programme is to generate knowledge and solutions for socially, economically and environmentally sustainable growth in the Norwegian aquaculture industry, and to maintain and further develop Norway's leading position in aquaculture research.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Food industry	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Norway	Research Council of Norway	1	0	2016	https://www.forskingsradet.no/prognett-havbruk/Programme_description/1226994216945	
SCAR	152	Marine Resources and the Environment (MARINFORSK)	It seeks to generate new, relevant and applicable knowledge about marine and coastal marine life.	Reduced Environmental impact	Water and soil management	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Society at large	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Norway	Research Council of Norway	0	0	2016-2025	https://www.forskingsradet.no/prognett-marinforsk/Programme_description/1254009007272	
SCAR	153	Large-scale Programme on Climate Research (KLIMAFORSK)	The KLIMAFORSK programme will promote outstanding climate research to the benefit of society.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	Society at large	R&I economic	Research sector	Norway	Research Council of Norway	0	0	2014-2023	https://www.forskingsradet.no/prognett-klimaforsk/Programme_description/1253987906604	
SCAR	154	Norwegian Agriculture Agency	The Norwegian Agriculture Agency (NAA) administrates various agricultural research and development funds.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Consumers	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Norway	Norwegian Agriculture Agency	0	0		https://www.landbruksdirektoratet.no/en/agriculture-and-market/research-funds#research-funding-for-agriculture-and-food-industry	
SCAR	155	Norwegian Seafood Research Fund-FHF	The seafood industry's tool in managing the industry's investments into industry-based R&D. The clear objective is to create added value for the seafood industry.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Food industry	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Norway	Norwegian Ministry of Fisheries and Coastal Affairs, representatives from the industry	0	0		https://www.fhf.no/om-fhf/about-fhf/	
SCAR	156	Innovation Norway	This service helps enterprises by removing barriers for global success, by providing guidance for the implementation of necessary measures that establishments meet at an early startup phase.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Food industry	R&I information	Food industry	Norway	Norwegian Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries	0	0		https://www.innovasjon Norge.no/en/start-page/	
SCAR	157	FIVA: Financing instrument for the Flemish fisheries and aquaculture sector	The support covers capital premiums for structural improvement in the fisheries and aquaculture sector, especially aimed at sustainability, which are granted both for production (shipping companies and aquaculture companies), commercialization (processing)	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Income support	Food industry	Belgium - Flanders	Flemish Department of Agriculture and Fisheries	0	0	2016	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/nl/visserij/subsidies-visserij/fiva-financieringsinstrument-voor-de-vlaamse-visserij-en	
SCAR	158	Flemish Agricultural Investment Fund (VLIF)	The Flemish Agricultural Investment Fund (VLIF) supports Flemish agriculture and horticulture by encouraging sustainable investments to improve the structure of agricultural and horticultural businesses, to ensure their profitability and to reduce the cost price.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Farmers	Income support	Farmers	Belgium - Flanders	Flemish Department of Agriculture and Fisheries	0	0	2016	https://lv.vlaanderen.be/nl/subsidies/vlif-steen-voor-de-land-en-tuinbouw	

SCAR	159	LA projects	demand-driven projects from the agricultural and horticultural sector	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Farmers	R&I economic	Research sector	Belgium - Flanders	Agency for Innovation and Entrepreneurship	0	0		https://www.vlaio.be/nl/andre-doelgroepen/landbouw-latrajecten
SCAR	160	Project support for innovations in agriculture	stimulates innovation in the agricultural and horticultural businesses, supporting innovative ideas and concepts in the production, processing and marketing of agricultural products.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	Farmers	R&I economic	Food industry	Belgium - Flanders	Flemish Department of Agriculture and Fisheries	0	0	2018	https://www.vlaio.be/nl/subsidies-financiering/subsidedatabank/projectsteun-voor-innovaties-de-landbouw
SCAR	161	Sectoral support measures - Agriculture	The overall aim of the sector funds is to make it possible for sufficient and well-trained employees to work within the sector in question.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Fostering a sharing economy for food production and consumption	Farmers	Education measure	Farmers	Belgium - Flanders	Agency for Innovation and Entrepreneurship	0	0		https://www.vlaio.be/nl/subsidies-financiering/subsidedatabank/sectorale-ondersteuningsmaatregelen https://www.eduplus.be/nl/onderwijs
SCAR	162	Sectoral support measures - Food industry	The overall aim of the sector funds is to make it possible for sufficient and well-trained employees to work within the sector in question.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Fostering a sharing economy for food production and consumption	Food industry	Education measure	Food industry	Belgium - Flanders	Agency for Innovation and Entrepreneurship	0	0		https://www.vlaio.be/nl/subsidies-financiering/subsidedatabank/sectorale-ondersteuningsmaatregelen https://www.alimento.be/nl/wie-zijn-we
SCAR	163	KRATOS: free advice for farmers and horticulturists	farmers and horticulturists can request free tailor-made advice	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Fostering a sharing economy for food production and consumption	Farmers	Education measure	Farmers	Belgium - Flanders	Belgian Department of Agriculture and Fisheries	0	0		https://www.vlaio.be/nl/subsidies-financiering/subsidedatabank/kratos-gratis-advies-voor-land-en-tuinbouwers
SCAR	164	Research project	It is aimed at knowledge building, which, in the long run, forms the basis for changes within the company. The project starts from an innovative idea for which new knowledge is needed and research - and, possibly, also development-activities must be carried out.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Food industry	R&I economic	Food industry	Belgium - Flanders	Agency for Innovation and Entrepreneurship	0	0	2018	https://www.vlaio.be/nl/subsidies-financiering/onderzoeksproject https://www.vlaio.be/nl/nieuws/innovatiesteun-het-nieuw
SCAR	165	Development project	for innovative ideas - new or improved product, process or service - that can change and strengthen companies in the short term	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	Food industry	R&I economic	Food industry	Belgium - Flanders	Agency for Innovation and Entrepreneurship	0	0	2018	https://www.vlaio.be/nl/subsidies-financiering/ontwikkelingsproject https://www.vlaio.be/nl/nieuws/innovatiesteun-het-nieuw
SCAR	166	Hectare support organic production method (PDPO III)	Bio-farmers can request per hectare support for applying the organic production method.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Farmers	Income support	Farmers	Belgium - Flanders	Belgian Department of Agriculture and Fisheries	0	0		https://lv.vlaanderen.be/nl/bio/subsidies/hectaresteun-biologische-productiemethode-pdpo-iii https://lv.vlaanderen.be/nl/bio/subsidies/controlekosten-biologische-productiemethode
SCAR	167	Ecological logo	Organic products labeled with this brand have been cultivated, processed, labeled and supplied to the consumer in accordance with the strict requirements set by the EU and Lithuanian legislation for organic farming	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Lithuania	Lithuanian Ministry of Agriculture	0	0		http://zum.lrv.lt/lt/veiklosritys/maisto-sauga-ir-kokybe/ekologisku-produktu-zenktas
SCAR	168	Quality mark	product manufacturing process is verified by the certifying authority. According to the national agricultural and food quality system, use of fertilizers and pesticides is limited; synthetic food additives are not used; they are manufactured using environmentally-friendly technologies.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Lithuania	Lithuanian Ministry of Agriculture	0	0		http://zum.lrv.lt/lt/veiklosritys/maisto-sauga-ir-kokybe/pagal-nacionaline-zemes-ukio-ir-maisto-kokybes-sistema-pagaminti-produktai-1 http://zum.lrv.lt/lt/veiklosritys/maisto-sauga-ir-kokybe/pagal-nacionaline-zemes-ukio-ir-maisto-kokybes-sistema-pagaminti-produktai-1/zenklinimas
SCAR	169	National Research Programmes - Healthy and Safe Food	The programme is designed to comprehensively research the storage, transportation and processing of food products. The results of the research should become the basis for improving the biological value of food, developing new food products as well as supply of safe and wholesome food.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	R&I economic	Research sector	Lithuania		0	0	2011-2015	https://www.lmt.lt/en/competitive-research-funding/national-research-programmes/787 https://www.e-tar.lt/portal/lt/legalAct/TAR.0914434AACFF/BGKBTMarCm

SCAR	170	National Research Programmes - Sustainability of agro, forest and water ecosystems	The purpose of the programme is to understand - and be able to forecast - the general effects of climate change and the intensive use of ecosystem resources, and to obtain new fundamental and empiric knowledge to enable the avoidance of threats related to these effects.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	Society at large	R&I economic	Research sector	Lithuania		0	0	2015-2021	https://www.lmt.lt/en/competitive-research-funding/national-research-programmes/787	https://www.e-tar.lt/portal/lt/legalAct/04256f40b07211e48296d11f563abfb0
SCAR	171	Soil protection guidelines	Soil Protection Guideline for Industrial Activities	Reduced Environmental impact	Water and soil management	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Society at large	Information measure	Food industry	Netherlands	Dutch Ministry of Housing, Spatial Planning and the Environment/Directorate General for the Environment	0	0	2003	https://rwsenvironment.eu/subjects/soil/legislation-and/soil-protection/	
SCAR	172	Netherlands Enterprise Agency (RVO.nl)	encourages sustainable, agricultural, innovative and international entrepreneurship. With subsidies, finding business partners, knowledge and compliance with laws and regulations. The aim is to increase the opportunities for entrepreneurs and to strengthen their (international) position.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Consumers	R&I economic	Food industry	Netherlands	Dutch Enterprise Agency	1	0	2004	https://mijn.rvo.nl/subsidie-en-financiering-aanvragen	https://www.rvo.nl/over-rvonl/organisatie/wat-doet-rvonl
SCAR	173	National Support Program in the wine sector	finance to promotion of wines; restructuring and conversion of vineyards; harvest insurance; investments; distillation of by-products.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Consumers	Fiscal policy	Farmers	Romania	Romanian Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development	0	0	2014-2018	http://www.madr.ro/horticultura/viticultura-vinificatie.html	
SCAR	174	Research Council of Norway	The Research Council of Norway works to add value to the research system by facilitating research that actors in the system could not successfully achieve working on their own.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Consumers	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Norway	Research Council of Norway	1	0		https://www.forskningsradet.no/en/The_Research_Council/1138785832539	https://www.forskningsradet.no/en/Application_types/1138882215869
SCAR	175	Flanders Food	unique, strategy-driven platform that contributes through innovation to a more competitive, innovative and sustainable agri-food industry.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Consumers	R&I information	Food industry	Belgium - Flanders	Flanders Food	1	0		http://www.flandersfood.com/over-ons	
SCAR	176	Agency for Innovation & Entrepreneurship	contact point of the Flemish government for all entrepreneurs in Flanders. We stimulate and support innovation and entrepreneurship and contribute to a favorable business climate.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Consumers	R&I economic	Food industry	Belgium - Flanders	Agency for Innovation & Entrepreneurship	1	0		https://www.vlaio.be/nl/over-ons/logos	
SCAR	177	Agency for Innovation & Entrepreneurship	contact point of the Flemish government for all entrepreneurs in Flanders. We stimulate and support innovation and entrepreneurship and contribute to a favorable business climate.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Consumers	R&I economic	Food industry	Belgium - Flanders	Agency for Innovation & Entrepreneurship	1	0		https://www.vlaio.be/nl/over-ons/logos	
SCAR	178	Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Nutrition Research (information services)	The Institute for Agricultural, Fisheries and Food Research (ILVO) carries out multidisciplinary, pioneering and independent research aimed at sustainable agriculture and fisheries in economic, ecological and social terms.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Farmers and fisheries	R&I information	Farmers and the food industry	Belgium - Flanders	Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Nutrition Research	1	0		https://www.ilvo.vlaanderen.be/language/nl-BE/NL/Over-ILVO.aspx#.Ww1Mz0iFO71	https://www.ilvo.vlaanderen.be/language/nl-BE/NL/Diensten-producten.aspx
SCAR	179	Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Nutrition Research (economic services)	The Institute for Agricultural, Fisheries and Food Research (ILVO) carries out multidisciplinary, pioneering and independent research aimed at sustainable agriculture and fisheries in economic, ecological and social terms.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Farmers and fisheries	R&I economic	Farmers and the food industry	Belgium - Flanders	Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Nutrition Research	1	0		https://www.ilvo.vlaanderen.be/language/nl-BE/NL/Over-ILVO.aspx#.Ww1Mz0iFO71	https://www.ilvo.vlaanderen.be/language/nl-BE/NL/Diensten-producten.aspx
SCAR	180	FWO fund for scientific research	The FWO supports fundamental and strategic scientific research, stimulates international cooperation and advocates equal opportunities.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Society at large	R&I economic	Research sector	Belgium - Flanders	FWO fund for scientific research	1	0		http://www.fwo.be/nl/	http://www.fwo.be/nl/mandaten-financiering/onderzoeksprojecten/junior-en-senior-onderzoeksproject/

SCAR	181	Lithuanian Environmental Investment Fund	The Lithuanian Environmental Investment Fund (LEIF) is responsible for the organization of the announcement of calls for proposals, the receipt and evaluation of project applications, the monitoring of the implementation of projects and the execution of payments to beneficiaries.	Reduced Environmental impact	Multiple subgoals	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	NA	Society at large	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Lithuania	Lithuanian Ministry of Environment	0	0		http://www.am.lt/VI/index.php#a/12923	http://www.laaf.lt/lt/	http://www.laaf.lt/lt/apie-programa/
SCAR	182	National support for livestock producers	Supplementary national direct payments are paid from the national budget to support the incomes of livestock operators.	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Equity and social cohesion in EU	NA	NA	Farmers	Income support	Farmers	Lithuania	Lithuanian Ministry of Agriculture	0	0		http://zum.lrv.lt/lt/veiklos-sritys/zemes-ir-maisto-ukis/parama/nacionaline-parama-ukiniu-gyvunu-augintojams		
SCAR	183	National Paying Agency	The National Paying Agency under the Ministry of Agriculture (NMA) is the only accredited authority administering support measures for agriculture, rural development and fisheries.	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Equity and social cohesion in EU	NA	NA	Farmers and fisheries	Income support	Farmers	Lithuania	National Paying Agency under the Ministry of Agriculture	0	0	1999	https://www.nma.lt/index.php/veikla/apie-nma/veiklos-sritys/287		
SCAR	184	1st Animal Husbandry Ordinance	Ordinance on the minimum requirements for keeping farmed animals and fish.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets		Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	Austria	Austrian Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Environment and Water Management, Federal Ministry of Health	0	0	2005	https://www.bmnt.gv.at/english/agriculture/Productionandmarkets/Animal-production-in-Austria/Animal-Welfare-Act.html		
SCAR	185	Austrian Apiculture Programme	Measures improving the conditions for the production and marketing of apiculture products	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets		Farmers	Fiscal policy	Farmers	Austria	Austrian government	0	0	2017-2019	https://www.bmnt.gv.at/english/agriculture/Productionandmarkets/Animal-production-in-Austria/Austrian-Apiculture-Programme-2017---2019.html		
SCAR	186	AMA organic seal	A food may carry the AMA Bio seal if it complies with the AMA Directive. This prescribes stricter criteria than the organic laws. Red-white stands for the Austrian origin of agricultural organic raw materials. The black AMA organic label does not limit the source of organic raw materials to a particular region.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets		Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Austria	AMA-Marketing GesmbH	0	0		https://www.bmnt.gv.at/english/agriculture/Organicfarming/Labeling.html	http://www.amaexport.at/en/ama-marketing.html	https://amainfo.at/ueberuns/wir-wir-sind/
SCAR	187	Agri-environmental Programme ÖPUL	Austria's programme for the promotion of an agriculture which is appropriate to the environment, extensive and protective of natural habitats. It is the national implementation of: the Agri-environment-climate measure, Organic farming, animal welfare and the NATURA 2000 measure (Art.28,29,33, 30 of EU-Reg. 1305/2013).	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems		Society at large	Regulation	Farmers	Austria	Austrian Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Environment and Water Management.	1	0	2015-2020	https://www.bmnt.gv.at/english/agriculture/Rural-development/-puls2015until2020.html	https://www.bmnt.gv.at/english/agriculture/Rural-development/Environmenteconomy-puls2015.html	
SCAR	188	Organic Farming Action Programme	The objective of the Organic Farming Action Programme is to promote and significantly develop organic farming by means of priority measures.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems		Farmers	Fiscal policy	Farmers	Austria	Austrian Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Environment and Water Management.	0	0	2015-2021	https://www.bmnt.gv.at/english/agriculture/Organicfarming/The-Organic-Farming-Action-Programme-2015-2020.html		
SCAR	189	Sparkling Science	Sparkling Science is a research programme that adopts an unconventional way in the promotion of young scientists. Young researchers take an active part and work independently on parts of the research projects.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Society at large	R&I economic	Research sector	Austria	Austrian Federal Ministry of Science, Research and Economy	0	0	2007	http://www.sparklingscience.at/en	https://bmbwf.gv.at/english/home/research/national/research-institutions/	
SCAR	190	Science Fund FWF	The Science Fund FWF is the largest funder of basic research besides the universities.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Society at large	R&I economic	Research sector	Austria	Austrian Ministry of Education, Research and Science	0	0		https://bmbwf.gv.at/forschung/national/forschung-in-oesterreich/forschungsfoerderung/	http://www.sparklingscience.at/en/info/programmziele.html	

SCAR	191	Austrian bee health program	Austrian bee health program.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	NA	Farmers	Income support	Farmers	Austria	Austrian Federal Ministry of Health, the Federal Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry, Environment and Water Management, Bee Austria	1	0	2016	https://www.bmnt.gv.at/land/produktion-maerkte/tierische-produktion/andere-tierarten/oebgp2016.html	https://www.biene-oesterreich.at/startseite+2500++1000242
SCAR	192	Innovation Fund Denmark	Innovation Fund Denmark invests in the best research and innovation projects with the potential to create knowledge, growth and employment in Denmark. IFD wishes to facilitate cross-investments in knowledge institutions and companies – private as well as public.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Society at large	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Denmark	Innovation Fund Denmark	1	0		https://innovationsfonden.dk/en/about-ifd	
SCAR	193	Green Development and Demonstration Program (GUDP)	GUDP seeks to create greater green sustainability in the Danish food sector by solving some of the climate and environmental problems. At the same time, the food sector must continue to create growth and secure jobs. GUDP provides grants for projects that ensure business-oriented green change	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Society at large	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Denmark	Danish Ministry of Environment and Food	1	0		http://lbst.dk/tilskud-selvbetjening/tilskudsguide/groent-udviklings-og-demonstrationsprogram-gudp/#c5713	http://mst.dk/erhverv/groent-virksomhed/groent-udviklings-og-demonstrationsprogram-gudp/
SCAR	194	Promille Fund for Agriculture	The Agricultural Promille Fund provides support for projects under the Agriculture Support Act.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Fostering a sharing economy for food production and consumption	Farmers	R&I economic	Farmers and the food industry	Denmark	Danish Ministry of Environment and Food	0	0	1978	https://promilleafgiftsfonden.dk/om-fonden	
SCAR	195	Federal Funding Advisory Service on Research and Innovation	The centre informs potential applicants about the federal research structure, funding programmes and the persons to contact as well as about current funding priorities and initiatives.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Research sector	R&I information	Food industry	Germany	German Federal Government	1	0		https://www.foerderinfo.bund.de/en/funding-advisory-service-1799.php	
SCAR	196	Agricultural social policy	policy for active farmers and their families that helps to create the conditions for the development of efficient and competitive agriculture.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Farmers	Income support	Farmers	Germany	German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture	0	0		https://www.bmel.de/DE/Landwirtschaft/Foerderung-Agrarsozialpolitik/Agrarsozialpolitik/sozialpolitik_node.html	
SCAR	197	Bilateral Trust Fund with the FAO	The aim of the projects is to assist states in ensuring a qualitatively and quantitatively balanced diet of each individual.	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Global FNS	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Third countries	R&I economic	Research sector	Germany	German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture	0	0	2002	https://www.bmel.de/DE/Landwirtschaft/Weltmaechrung/_Texte/Ernaehrungssicherungsprojekte.html	
SCAR	198	Protein crops Strategy	The protein strategy aims at reducing the competitive disadvantages of domestic protein crops, closing research gaps and testing and implementing the necessary measures in practice, providing farmers with incentives to grow and use leguminous crops in addition to cereals and oilseeds	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Supporting protein alternatives to meat	Farmers	Fiscal policy	Farmers	Germany	German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture	0	0	2012	https://www.bmel.de/DE/Landwirtschaft/Pflanzenbau/Ackerbau/_Texte/Eiweisspflanzenstrategie.html#doc3743388bodyText1	
SCAR	199	Protein crops Strategy	The focus is the transfer of knowledge, the intensification of advice and the creation of value chains. Research and development projects are intended to generate innovations and provide impetus for economically successful cultivation of legumes and their utilization.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	Farmers	R&I economic	Research sector	Germany	German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture, Federal Agency for Agriculture and Food	0	0	2013	https://www.ble.de/DE/Projektfoerderung/Foerderung-Auftraege/Eiweisspflanzenstrategie/eiweisspflanzenstrategie_node.html	
SCAR	200	Research Cooperation for Global Food Security	development of Research Cooperation for Food Security with agricultural research institutions in partner countries and in Germany.	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Global FNS	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Promoting healthy and sustainable African diets	Third countries	R&I economic	Research sector	Germany	German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture	0	0		https://www.ble.de/EN/Project-Funding/Funding-Contracts/International-Research-Cooperation/Research-Cooperation-Global-Food-Security/research-cooperation-global-food-security_node.html	
SCAR	201	Regulation to prevent the slaughter of high-quality mammals	The release of animals during the last third of gestation for the purpose of slaughter is prohibited.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	NA	NA	Society at large	Regulation	Farmers	Germany	German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture	0	0		https://www.bmel.de/DE/Tier/Tierwohl/_texte/schlachten-traechtiger-tiere.html	

SCAR	202	Research for Sustainable Development FONA 3	The FONA-Framework Programme represents the implementation of the German National Sustainability Strategy and the Federal Governments High-Tech Strategy. The Research for Sustainable Development develops decision-making tools for future oriented action and delivers innovative solutions for a sustainable society.	Reduced Environmental impact	Multiple subgoals	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	Society at large	R&I economic	Research sector	Germany	German Federal Ministry of Education and Research	0	0	2015	https://www.fona.de/en/research-for-sustainable-development-fona-17833.html	https://www.fona.de/mediathek/pdf/bmbf_fona3_2016_englisch_barrierefrei.pdf
SCAR	203	KMU innovative SME - Biotechnology	Funding measure for strengthening the innovative potential of small and medium-sized enterprises in the area of cutting-edge research and making research funding within the framework of the biotechnology sector program more attractive, especially for first-time SMEs.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	SMEs	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Germany	German Federal Ministry of Education and Research	0	0		https://www.bmbf.de/foerderung/bekanntmachung-279.html	
SCAR	204	ZIM - Central Innovation Programme for SMEs	Funding programme for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with business operations in Germany which want to develop new or significantly improve existing products, processes or technical services.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	SMEs	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Germany	German Ministry of Economics and Energy	0	0	2008-2019	https://www.zim-bmwi.de/zim-overview	https://www.aif.de/en/central-innovation-programme-sme.html?L=0
SCAR	205	Industrial Collective Research for SMEs	Collective research is a mechanism enabling businesses to solve shared problems through shared projects. This kind of pre-competitive research closes the gap between basic research and industrial application.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	SMEs	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Germany	German Ministry of Economics and Energy	0	0		https://www.aif.de/en/collective-research.html	
SCAR	206	Federal Organic Farming Scheme and other forms of sustainable agriculture (BÖLN)	The federal program pursues the strengthening and expansion of the ecological and sustainable agriculture and food industry: identifies research needs, recruits research projects, examines their relevance, practical relevance and cost-benefit ratio, finances them and accompanies them to the end.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Farmers	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Germany	German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture	1	0	2001	https://www.bundesprogramm.de/wer-wir-sind/ueber-das-bundesprogramm/	https://www.bundesprogramm.de/was-wir-tun/projekte-foerdern/forschungs-und-entwicklungsvorhaben/
SCAR	207	Green innovation centres	The aim of the centres is to use innovation in the agriculture and food sector to increase regional food supplies, boost the income of smallholders, and to create more employment opportunities, particularly in the area of food processing.	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Global FNS	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Third countries	R&I economic	Farmers and the food industry	Germany	German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development	1	0		https://www.bmz.de/en/issues/Food/gruene_innovationszentren/index.html	
SCAR	208	Too good for the bin	It has the objective to reach as many consumers as possible and reduce food waste with joint effort along the entire chain.	Reduced Environmental impact	Resource efficiency and waste management	CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	Achieving zero food waste	Society at large	Information measure	Consumers	Germany	German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture	0	0	2012	https://www.bmel.de/EN/Food/Value-Of-Food/_Texte/ZgfdT.html	
SCAR	209	Model and Demonstration Project (MuD)	Model and demonstration projects (MuD) close the gap between science (research and development) and practice. The focus is on the first-time application of new procedures or techniques not previously used in the specific practice situation ("step into practice").	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	Society at large	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Germany	German Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture	0	0	2015	https://www.ble.de/DE/Projektfoerderung/Foerderung-Auftraege/Modellvorhaben/modellvorhaben_node.html	
SCAR	210	Organic Farming Act	This Act provides for the requirements for operating in the area of organic farming to the extent not regulated by EU, as well as for the grounds and extent of supervision exercised over persons operating in the area of organic farming.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Farmers	Regulation	Farmers	Estonia	Estonian Ministry of Rural Affairs	0	0	2007	https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/517012018001/consolide	
SCAR	211	Estonian Food Promotion Plan "Eesti Toit"	Promotion of Estonian food by implementing marketing activities that help to create, consolidate and disseminate the positive image of Estonian food.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Food industry	Information measure	Consumers	Estonia	Estonian Ministry of Rural Affairs	0	0	2015-2020	https://www.agri.ee/et/eesti-toit-2015-2020#eesmargid	http://eestitoit.ee/et
SCAR	212	Estonian quality labels	labels help consumers to recognize the good and high-quality products from Estonia.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Engaging citizens in food systems and science policy	Food industry	Labelling measure	Consumers	Estonia	Estonian Ministry of Rural Affairs	0	0		https://www.agri.ee/et/eesmargid-tegevused/pollumajandus-jatoiduturg/kvaliteedimargid	

SCAR	213	Rural Development Foundation	The Foundation is a self-governing private legal entity, whose activities are: guaranteeing of debt obligations, lending, shaping the reputation of rural life.	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Equity and social cohesion in EU	NA	NA	Farmers	Delivery of services	Farmers	Estonia	Rural Development Foundation	0	0	1993	http://mes.ee/maaclu-edendamise-sihtasutus
SCAR	214	Variety breeding program	This program coordinates plant breeding and related research. The breeding program is aimed at breeding varieties that help ensure the competitiveness of the crop and the agricultural sector.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Farmers	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Estonia	Estonian Ministry of Rural Affairs	0	0	2009-2019	https://www.agri.ee/et/sordiaretusprogramm-aastatel-2009-2019
SCAR	215	Applied Research Program	Research for providing science-based input to policy-making, legislation and state supervision; and co-ordination and funding of participation in international research co-operation projects are funded under the program	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Society at large	R&I economic	Research sector	Estonia	Estonian Ministry of Rural Affairs	1	0	2015-2021	https://www.agri.ee/et/pollumajanduslikud-rakendusuringud-ja-arendustegevus-aastatel-2015-2021
SCAR	216	Plan for the Promotion of Women in the Rural Environment	Plan to improve the socio-labor inclusion and economic participation of rural women.	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Equity and social cohesion in EU	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Engaging citizens in food systems and science policy	Farmers	Information measure	Farmers	Spain	Spanish Institute for Women and Equal Opportunities, Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Environment, Ministry of Education, Culture and Sports, Ministry of Industry, Energy and Tourism, Ministry of Health, Social Services and Equality, Ministry of Development, and Ministry of the Interior.	0	0	2015-2018	http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/desarrollo-rural/temas/igualdad_genero_y_des_sostenible/plan/default.aspx
SCAR	217	Innovation excellence awards for rural women	The objective is to contribute to the recognition of original and innovative projects of rural women, based on agrarian and complementary activities, as well as on agri-food activities that contribute to the diversification of economic activity and that promote the entrepreneurship of women in the territory	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Equity and social cohesion in EU	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Engaging citizens in food systems and science policy	Farmers	R&I economic	Farmers	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment	1	0	2010	http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/desarrollo-rural/temas/igualdad_genero_y_des_sostenible/subvenciones_y_premios/premios_excepcionales/
SCAR	218	Support measures to facilitate access to finance for agricultural holdings	Support measures to facilitate access to financing of agricultural holdings. Exceptional measures that contribute to alleviating lack of liquidity, facilitating access to credit.	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Equity and social cohesion in EU	NA	NA	Farmers	Income support	Farmers	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment	0	0	2014	http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/ministerio/servicios/analisis-y-prospectiva/Medidas_Financieras.aspx
SCAR	219	Aid for the renovation of agricultural machinery	Direct granting of state subsidies for the renovation of the park of agricultural machinery	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Farmers	Income support	Farmers	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment	0	0	2017	http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/agricultura/temas/medios-de-produccion/maquinaria-agricola/ayudas/ayudas_renovacion_de_maquinaria/default.aspx
SCAR	220	Fund to Support the Diversification of the Fisheries and Aquaculture Sector	Its purpose is to provide financial support to business initiatives to diversify fishing and aquaculture activities, which will improve its technological development.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Income support	Fisheries	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment	0	0	2014	http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/pesca/ayudas-y-subsvenciones/default.aspx
SCAR	221	Aid for innovation in the wine sector	Support was given to tangible or intangible investments for the development of new products, processes and technologies	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Farmers	R&I economic	Farmers	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment	0	0	2019-2023	http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/alimentacion/temas/industria-agroalimentaria/ayudas-a-la-industria-agroalimentaria/default.aspx
SCAR	222	Measures to improve the functioning of the food chain	The purpose of the project is to improve the functioning and the structure of the food chain, so as to increase the efficiency and competitiveness of the Spanish agri-food sector and to reduce the imbalance in commercial relations between the different operators of the value chain	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Fostering a sharing economy for food production and consumption	Food industry	Regulation	Food industry	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment	0	0	2013	http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/alimentacion/temas/ley-de-medidas-para-mejorar-el-funcionamiento-de-la-cadena-alimentaria/sobre-ley/default.aspx

SCAR	223	Law of Promotion of Associative Integration	Promote the integration of cooperatives and other associative entities of an agrifood nature. Promote a cooperative business model, professionalized, generating value and employment, with a relevant dimension	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Fostering a sharing economy for food production and consumption	Food industry	Regulation	Farmers	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment	0	0	2013	http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/alimentacion/temas/ley-de-fomento-de-la-integracion-cooperativa/contenido-ley/default.aspx	http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/alimentacion/temas/ley-de-fomento-de-la-integracion-cooperativa/contenido-ley/default.aspx
SCAR	224	Dairy Agreement	commitment to work for stability and value creation throughout the dairy chain and to achieve sustainable and remunerative prices in each stretch of the same	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Fostering a sharing economy for food production and consumption	Food industry	Food and agricultural standards	Food industry	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment	0	0	2015	http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/me-gustalaleche/acuerdos-lacteos/default.aspx	
SCAR	225	Promotional campaign #megustalaleche	Promotional actions for the consumption of milk and milk products	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Consumers	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment	0	0		http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/me-gustalaleche/presentacion.aspx	
SCAR	226	Sustainable Dairy Products	Achieve an efficient and sustainable operation of the value chains of milk and milk products, improving the consumer perception of dairy products as products of high nutritional value and quality.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Engaging citizens in food systems and science policy	Consumers	Information measure	Food industry	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment	0	0	2013	http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/me-gustalaleche/productos-lacteos-sostenibles/	
SCAR	227	More food, less waste	Limit losses and food waste and reduce environmental pressures.	Reduced Environmental impact	Resource efficiency and waste management	CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	Achieving zero food waste	Society at large	Information measure	Food industry	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment	0	0		http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/alimentacion/temas/estrategia-mas-alimento-menos-desperdicio/bloque1.aspx	
SCAR	228	Fruit and vegetables #DeAquíYDeAhora	It pursued a double objective: to promote the consumption of fruits and vegetables of national production among the public that is not a habitual consumer and to encourage the direct support of the Department to the producers affected by the stagnation of consumption.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Consumers	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment	1	0	2017	http://www.alimentacion.es/es/campanas/frutas/fruta-y-verdura-de-aqui-y-de-ahora-ultima-edicion/default.aspx	http://www.mapama.gob.es/es/alimentacion/temas/frutas-verduras-temporada/
SCAR	229	State Plan for Scientific and Technical Research and Innovation	state aid for the R + D + i, which are granted preferably through calls in competitive competition.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Society at large	R&I economic	Research sector	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness and Ministry of Science, Innovation and University	0	0	2017-2020	http://www.idi.mineco.gob.es/portal/site/MICINN/menuitem.7eeac5cd345b4f34f09dfd1001432ea0/?vgnextoid=abf192b9036c2210VgnVCM100001d04140aRCRD	http://www.ciencia.gob.es/portal/site/MICINN/menuitem.7eeac5cd345b4f34f09dfd1001432ea0/?vgnextoid=83b192b9036c2210VgnVCM1000001d04140aRCRD
SCAR	230	Electronic prescription of antibiotics in livestock	Royal Decree that establishes the electronic transmission of data of veterinary prescriptions of antibiotics and medicated feed destined to animals producing food for human consumption	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries, Food and Environment	0	0	2019	http://www.resistenciaantibioticos.es/es/noticias/la-nueva-normativa-para-la-prescripcion-electronica-de-antibioticos-en-ganaderia-entrara-en	
SCAR	231	Collaboration plan for improving the composition of food and beverages	Reformulation commitments of the Manufacturing and Distribution sectors, for various types of foods and beverages commonly consumed by children, Young people and families and the reduction of added sugars, salt and saturated fats.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Food industry	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Health, Social Services and Equality and Spanish Agency for Consumption, Food Safety and Nutrition - Aecosan	1	1	2017-2020	http://www.aecosan.msssi.gob.es/AECOSAN/web/nutricion/seccion/plan_colaboracion.htm	
SCAR	232	State Research Agency	guarantee accountability, improve and extend the monitoring of actions, streamline the management of available funds, reduce administrative burdens and simplify and standardize procedures.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Society at large	R&I information	Research sector	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and University	0	0		http://www.ciencia.gob.es/portal/site/MICINN/menuitem.8d78849a34f1cd28d0e9d91026041a0/?vgnextoid=664cfb7e04195510VgnVCM100001d04140aRCRD&vgnextchannel=664cfb7e04195510VgnVCM1000001d04140aRCRD	
SCAR	233	Innovative SME	This Royal Decree aims to establish a 40 percent bonus on business contributions to Social Security contributions for common contingencies with respect to the research staff who, exclusively, are engaged in research and development activities and technological innovation	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	SMEs	SME support	SMEs	Spain	Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and University	0	0	2014	http://www.ciencia.gob.es/portal/site/MICINN/menuitem.6f2062042f6a5bc43b3f6810d14041a0/?vgnextoid=45cc94d74d44a410VgnVCM100001d04140aRCRD	https://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=BOE-A-2014-6276 http://www.boe.es/diario_boe/txt.php?id=%20BOE-A-2015-6468

SCAR	234	Act on national aid for agriculture and horticulture	Under this law, agriculture and horticulture can be granted national support for livestock farming, plant production, greenhouse production and storage of horticultural products, milk and meat transportation aid and other subsidies	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Farmers	Income support	Farmers	Finland	Finnish Government	0	0	2001	http://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/ajantasa/2001/20011559
SCAR	235	Limit for pesticide residues in baby foods	Pesticides listed in Annex I shall not be used in agricultural products intended for the manufacture of baby foods.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Farmers and the food industry	Finland	Finnish Ministry of Trade and Industry	0	0	2007	http://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/alkup/2007/20071215
SCAR	236	Regulation on food information to consumers	This Regulation lays down the labeling of prepacked food and any other food information to be supplied to final consumers in connection with sales or other supplies	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Finland	Finnish Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry	0	0	2014	http://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/alkup/2014/20140834
SCAR	237	Food and catering public procurement	State-owned food purchases will take more effective account of environmentally sound cultivation methods, animal welfare and health and food safety.	Reduced Environmental impact	Multiple subgoals	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	NA	Society at large	Procurement	Public Authorities	Finland	Finnish Government	1	0	2016	https://mmm.fi/artikkeli/-/asset_publisher/periaatepaatos-julkisten-elintarvike-ja-ruokapalveluhankintojen-vastuullisuudesta-hyvaksyttiin http://www.motivanhankintapalvelu.fi/in_english http://www.motivanhankintapalvelu.fi/tietopankki/elintarvikkeet/kriteerit.html
SCAR	238	Environmental Protection Act	The operator must organize activities so that pollution can be prevented in advance. If pollution can not be totally prevented, it must be limited to the minimum. The operator shall limit its emissions to the environment and the sewerage system to a minimum.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	NA	Society at large	Regulation	Food industry	Finland	Finnish Ministry of Environment	0	0	2014	http://www.finlex.fi/fi/laki/alkup/2014/20140527
SCAR	239	Nordic Nutrition Recommendations	set the guidelines for dietary composition and recommended intake for nutrients based on the most recent global scientific research.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Consumers	Finland	Nordic Council of Ministers	0	0	2012	https://www.norden.org/en/themes/former-themes/themes-2016/nordic-nutrition-recommendation/nordic-nutrition-recommendations-2012 https://www.evira.fi/elintarvikkeet/terveytta-edistava-ruokavalio/kulttaja-ja-ammattilaismateriaali/julkaisu/
SCAR	240	Ecophyto 2	The Ecophyto plan aims to reduce the use of plant protection products (commonly known as pesticides) in France while maintaining an economically efficient agriculture.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Farmers	Education measure	Farmers	France	French Ministry of Agriculture and Food	0	0	2008	http://agriculture.gouv.fr/le-plan-ecophyto-quest-ce-quecest http://agriculture.gouv.fr/ecophyto-objectif-30-000-exploitations-agricoles http://agriculture.gouv.fr/les-fermes-dephy-objectif-reduction-des-intrants
SCAR	241	Ambition bio	A new impetus for balanced development and the structuring of all sectors that aims to mobilize the actors of production, processing and marketing as well as citizens.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Society at large	Information measure	Food industry	France	French Ministry of Agriculture and Food	1	0	2017	http://agriculture.gouv.fr/programme-ambition-bio-2017
SCAR	242	Antigaspi - waste less eat better	Prevention campaign on food waste.	Reduced Environmental impact	Resource efficiency and waste management	CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	Achieving zero food waste	Consumers	Information measure	Consumers	France	French Ministry of Agriculture and Food	0	0		http://agriculture.gouv.fr/antigaspi http://agriculture.gouv.fr/waste-less-eat-better
SCAR	243	4% Initiative Soils	The "4% Initiative : soils for food security and climate" aims to show that food security and combating climate change are complementary and to ensure that agriculture provides solutions to climate change.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Society at large	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Farmers	France	French Ministry of Agriculture and Food	0	1	2015	http://agriculture.gouv.fr/join-40-initiative-soils-food-security-and-climate http://agriculture.gouv.fr/infograpics-carbon-sequestration-soils
SCAR	244	High environmental value	The farm environmental certification is a voluntary approach which aims to identify and promote particularly environmentally-friendly practices applied by farmers. HEV covers four key areas: biodiversity conservation, plant protection strategy, management of fertiliser use and management of water.	Reduced Environmental impact	Multiple subgoals	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Consumers	Labelling measure	Farmers	France	French Ministry of Agriculture and Food	0	0		http://agriculture.gouv.fr/hev-certification http://agriculture.gouv.fr/sites/minagri/files/220517_high_env_ironmental_value_hev_bd.pdf

SCAR	245	Single interministerial fund (FUI)	This system is intended to support innovative collaborative projects for the development of products, processes or services likely to be placed on the market in the short or medium term	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Consumers	R&I economic	Industry-based research	France	French Ministry of Agriculture and Food	1	0		http://agriculture.gouv.fr/le-fonds-unique-interministeriel-un-soutien-decisif-pour-les-projets-de-rd-des-poles-de
SCAR	246	Placing on the market and use of phytopharmaceutical products	It sets out certain provisions governing the implementation of on the market and use of plant protection products and their adjuvants	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Input suppliers	France	French Ministry of Agriculture and Food	0	0	2017	http://agriculture.gouv.fr/moyens-permettant-la-limitation-de-la-derivee-de-pulverisation http://agriculture.gouv.fr/arrete-du-4-mai-2017-mise-sur-le-marche-et-utilisation-des-produits-phytopharmaceutiques
SCAR	247	Agricultural Products of France	These logos reflect the commitment of the professionals of the sectors to value the know-how, the territories and the French jobs	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Food industry	Labelling measure	Food industry	France	Association des produits agricoles de France, French Ministry of Agriculture and Food	0	0		http://www.produitsagricolesdefrance.fr/qui-sommes-nous/ http://agriculture.gouv.fr/viandes-france-la-garantie-de-lorigine-et-de-la-tracabilite http://agriculture.gouv.fr/oeufs-de-france-un-logo-pour-garantir-lorigine-et-la-tracabilite
SCAR	248	Stage 250	Program for hosting Moroccan students in France. The aim is to introduce students to the operation of the farm by immersing themselves in the professional reality and by participating actively in all its activities.	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Aid and cooperation	NA	NA	Third countries	Education measure	Third countries	Third countries	French Ministry of Agriculture and Food, Directorate General for Education and Research	0	0		http://agriculture.gouv.fr/stage-250-quand-des-etudiants-marocains-vivent-lagriculture-au-coeur-des-regions-francaises
SCAR	249	Moveagri	Moveagri is a site, functioning as a social network, dedicated to learners and teachers of agricultural education. It is designed for young people from French agricultural institutions who choose to go for an internship abroad as part of their courses.	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Equity and social cohesion in EU	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Engaging citizens in food systems and science policy	Consumers	Information measure	Education sector	France	French Ministry of Agriculture and Food	0	0		http://moveagri.ning.com/page/moveagri http://agriculture.gouv.fr/moveagri-le-concours-de-blog-qui-valorise-les-experiences-letranger
SCAR	250	EcoAntibio	The aim of the Plan is to reduce the risks of antibiotic resistance in veterinary medicine and to safeguard the efficacy of the antibiotics	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	NA	Consumers	Information measure	Farmers	France	French Ministry of Agriculture and Food	0	0	2012-2017	http://agriculture.gouv.fr/plan-ecoantibio-2012-2017-lutte-contre-lantibioreistance
SCAR	251	Plan "Seeds and seedlings for sustainable agriculture"	The Plan strengthens the contribution of the plant breeding sector to sustainable production methods, environmental protection, adaptation to climate change and the development of cultivated biodiversity.	Reduced Environmental impact	Biodiversity	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Recovering forgotten crops for nutrition and resilience	Society at large	Regulation	Farmers	France	French Ministry of Agriculture and Food	0	0	2011	http://agriculture.gouv.fr/plan-semences-et-plants-pour-une-agriculture-durable
SCAR	252	Sustainable development plan for beekeeping	Actions: training; limiting bee exposure to risk factors influencing colony health; organization and support of the beekeeping industry. The funding of actions in favor of beekeeping is maintained.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Farmers	Education measure	Farmers	France	French Ministry of Agriculture and Food	1	0	2013	http://agriculture.gouv.fr/prolongement-du-plan-de-developpement-durable-de-lapiculture
SCAR	253	Vegetable protein plan	Long-term commitment to the development of leguminous crops to improve the environmental and economic performance of French agriculture	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Supporting protein alternatives to meat	Farmers	R&I economic	Farmers	France	French Ministry of Agriculture and Food	0	0	2014-2020	http://agriculture.gouv.fr/le-plan-proteines-vegetales-pour-la-france-2014-2020
SCAR	254	National R&I funding Programme "Fusion"	FUSION, presents a funding programme that supports Research and Innovation with the ultimate goal of promoting and supporting local research and innovation	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Society at large	R&I economic	Research sector	Malta	Malta Council for Science & Technology	1	0	2014-2020	http://mcst.gov.mt/ri-programmes/fusion/
SCAR	255	National Food Research Program	FUSION, presents a funding programme that supports Research and Innovation with the ultimate goal of promoting and supporting local research and innovation	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Society at large	R&I economic	Research sector	Sweden	Swedish Government, Research Council - Formas	0	0		http://www.formas.se/Internationellt/Forskningsprogram/Nationella-forskningsprogrammet-for-livsmedel/ https://www.regeringen.se/pressmeddelanden/2017/06/agardspaket-for-starkt-forskning-innovationskraft-och-samverkan-i-livsmedelskedjan/

SCAR	256	State aid	State aid for research and development, as well as innovation in the fields of environment, land use and community construction	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Society at large	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Sweden	Swedish Government, Research Council - Formas	0	0		http://www.formas.se/sv/Internationellt/Strategiska-innovationsomraden/Statligt-stod/
SCAR	257	Strategic innovation programs	companies in Sweden, authorities and universities act together to formulate the challenges, set common long-term goals and prioritize investment in research, development and innovation.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Society at large	R&I information	Industry-based research	Sweden	Swedish Government, Research Council - Formas	1	0		http://www.formas.se/sv/Internationellt/Strategiska-innovationsomraden/
SCAR	258	National Research Program on Climate	In order to meet the climate challenge, research is needed in several different fields, such as interdisciplinary and cross-sectoral research and innovation.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	Society at large	R&I economic	Research sector	Sweden	Swedish Government, Research Council - Formas	1	0		http://www.formas.se/sv/Internationellt/Forskningsprogram/Forskningsprogrammet-om-klimat/
SCAR	259	Sweden's innovation agency - Vinnova	Vinnova is Sweden's government agency for innovation. Our mission is to contribute to sustainable growth by improving the conditions for innovation. We do this mainly by funding innovation projects and the research needed to develop new solutions.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Food industry	R&I economic	Industry-based research	Sweden	Sweden's innovation agency - Vinnova	1	0		https://www.vinnova.se/en/about-us/swedens-innovation-agency/
SCAR	260	Organic Farming support	Support payment for the environment-friendly farming and culture techniques	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Farmers	Income support	Farmers	Turkey	Turkish Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Livestock	1	0		https://www.tarim.gov.tr/Konular/Organic-Farming/Organic-Farming-Support
SCAR	261	Organic Eating Mark	free state-controlled labeling scheme for eating places, it shows how much of the food and beverage offered is organic. Both public and private eating places can get the logo (restaurant, public canteens, catering and take away)	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food services	Denmark	Danish Food Agency	1	0		https://www.oekologisk-spisemaerke.dk/om-spisemaerket
SCAR	262	State-controlled organic logo	The Danish authorities have controlled the farm or the company that has last processed, packed or labeled an organic product.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Denmark	Danish Ministry of Environment and Food	0	0		https://www.foedevarestyrelsen.dk/Leksikon/Sider/%C3%98-m%C3%A6rket.aspx
SCAR	263	Food guidelines for protection of children before commercial messages	Nutrition guidelines that will help audiovisual media service providers to develop their own code of conduct for protecting children against inappropriate commercial messages about foods during the time of children's programs.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Regulation	Media	Slovenia	Slovenian Ministry of Health	0	0	2016	http://www.mz.gov.si/si/delovna_podrocja_in_prioritete/javnostno_zdravje/varovanje_in_krjepitev_zdravja_prehrana_gibanje_dusevno_zdravje_itd/prerhrama/prehranske_smernice_za_zascito_otrok_pred_neprimernimi_komercialnimi_sporocili/
SCAR	264	Food Guidelines for Grades 5-8 of Primary Schools	Food Guidelines for Grades 5-8 of Primary Schools	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Information measure	Consumers	Croatia	Croatian Public Health Institute	0	0		https://www.hzjz.hr/sluzbapromicanje-zdravljaprehrambensmjernice-za-5-do-8-razred-osnovnih-skola/
EC	265	Milk quotas	Milk quotas were introduced to address the structural oversupply on the EU market of the late 1970s and early 1980s. EU dairy farmers were guaranteed a price for their milk (considerably higher than on world markets) regardless of market demand.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NA	NA	Farmers	Fiscal policy	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	1984 - 2015	https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/milk-quota-end_en
EC	266	Import arrangements for milk and milk products and opening tariff quotas (2535/2001)	all imports of milk products shall be subject to presentation of an import licence.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NA	NA	Food industry	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	2001	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32001R2535

EC	267	Export licences and export refunds for milk and milk products (1187/2009)	general rules concerning licences and refunds for exports from the Community of milk and milk products	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NA	NA	Food industry	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	2009	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32009R1187
EC	268	Tariff quotas for sheep, goats, sheepmeat and goatmeat (1354/2011)	This Regulation opens, as from 1 January 2012, annual Union import tariff quotas for sheep, goats, sheepmeat and goatmeat.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NA	NA	Food industry	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	2011	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32011R1354
EC	269	Marketing standards for poultrymeat (543/2008)	The regulation sets out marketing standards for poultrymeat	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Food industry	Regulation	Retailers	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	2008	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1530883123395&uri=CELEX:32008R0543
EC	270	Marketing standards for eggs (589/2008)	The regulation sets out marketing standards for eggs	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Food industry	Regulation	Retailers	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	2008	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32008R0589
EC	271	Free distribution of withdrawn fruit and vegetables	Produce withdrawn from the market to help growers manage periodic crises is donated to various charitable and public service bodies in the EU. The EU funds 100% of free distribution for quantities up to 5% of the PO's total marketed volume, the aim being to stimulate greater consumption of fruit and vegetables in the EU	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Fiscal policy	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Agri	1	0		https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/fruit-and-vegetables/free-distribution_en
EC	272	Support for withdrawals of fruit and vegetables (Article 45, Regulation (EU) 2017/891)	Support for withdrawals of fruit and vegetables	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Equity and social cohesion in EU	NA	NA	Farmers	Fiscal policy	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	2017	https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/fruit-and-vegetables/crisis-prevention#market-withdrawal https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1497541016356&uri=CELEX:32017R0891
EC	273	Specific marketing standards for fresh fruit and vegetables (543/2011)	The regulation sets out specific marketing standards for fresh fruit and vegetables	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Retailers	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	2011	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32011R0543 https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/fruit-and-vegetables/marketing-standards#specific-marketing-standards
EC	274	Community programme on the conservation, characterisation, collection and utilisation of genetic resources in agriculture (870/2004)	Promotes genetic diversity and the exchange of information including close co-ordination between Member States and between the Member States and the European Commission for the conservation and sustainable use of genetic resources in agriculture.	Reduced Environmental impact	Biodiversity	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Recovering forgotten crops for nutrition and resilience	Farmers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	2004	https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/genetic-resources_en https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32004R0870
EC	275	Birds directive	This Directive relates to the conservation of all species of naturally occurring birds in the wild state in the European territory of the Member States. It covers the protection, management and control of these species and lays down rules for their exploitation.	Reduced Environmental impact	Biodiversity	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	NA	Society at large	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Environment	0	0	2009	http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/legislation/birdsdirective/index_en.htm https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32009L0147
EC	276	CAP - Cross compliance	In order to receive payments, farmers shall respect a set of basic rules. Farmers not respecting EU law on environmental, public and animal health, animal welfare or land management will see the EU support they receive reduced.	Reduced Environmental impact	Multiple subgoals	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	NA	Society at large	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Agri	1	0	2013	https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/direct-support/cross-compliance_en
EC	277	Placing of plant protection products (PPPs) on the market	Before any PPP can be placed on the market or used, it must be authorised in the Member State(s) concerned. Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 lays down the rules and procedures for authorisation of PPPs.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Farmers	Regulation	Input suppliers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2009	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/authorisation_of_ppp_en https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32009R1107 https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:01991L0414-20110801

EC	278	EU's Nitrates Directive	The Nitrates Directive aims to protect water quality across Europe by preventing nitrates from agricultural sources polluting ground and surface waters and by promoting the use of good farming practices.	Reduced Environmental impact	Water and soil management	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Society at large	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Environment	0	0	1991	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/ALL/?uri=CELEX:31991L0676	http://ec.europa.eu/environment/water/water-nitrates/index_en.html
EC	279	Mountain product	Aims to help producers of agricultural products and foodstuffs to communicate the product characteristics and farming attributes of those products and foodstuffs to buyers and consumers	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Engaging citizens in food systems and science policy	Consumers	Labelling measure	Farmers and the food industry	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	2014	https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/quality/optional-voluntary-certification_en	https://ec.europa.eu/info/promotion-eu-farm-products_en
EC	280	Support for exporters	EU support for the internationalisation of EU businesses	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Fostering a sharing economy for food production and consumption	Food industry	Delivery of services	Import/export companies	EU	Consumers, Health, Agriculture and Food Executive Agency (Chafea)	0	0		https://ec.europa.eu/chafea/agri/enter-new-markets/support-for-exporters	
EC	281	Enjoy it's from Europe	The "Enjoy! it's from Europe" signature has been developed in order to be used by beneficiaries of EU co-financing in promotional material concerning EU agricultural products inside and outside the EU.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Labelling measure	Farmers and the food industry	EU	Consumers, Health, Agriculture and Food Executive Agency (Chafea)	0	0		https://ec.europa.eu/chafea/agri/funding-opportunities/instructions-on-the-use-of-the-signature-enjoy-it-s-from-europe	
EC	282	School Fruit and Vegetables Scheme	EU-wide scheme that provided schoolchildren with fruit and vegetables, aiming thus to encourage good eating habits in young people. Besides providing fruit and vegetables, the scheme required participating Member States to set up strategies, including educational and awareness-raising initiatives	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Education measure	School food services	EU	EC - DG Agri	1	0	2009-2017	https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/sfs_en	
EC	283	Regulations on indication of the country of origin or place of provenance meat (1337/2013)	This Regulation lays down rules on the indication of the country of origin or place of provenance on the label of fresh, chilled and frozen meat of swine, meat of sheep or goats and meat of poultry	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Labelling measure	Farmers and the food industry	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	2013	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32013R1337	
EC	284	Regulation on food supplements (2002/46/EC)	With respect to the safety of food supplements, the Directive lays down a harmonised list of vitamins and minerals that may be added for nutritional purposes in food supplements	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2002	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/labelling_nutrition/supplements_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32002L0046
EC	285	Regulation on addition of vitamins and minerals (EC No 1925/2006)	provisions regarding the addition of vitamins and minerals and of certain other substances to foods. This Regulation ensures the effective functioning of the internal market whilst providing a high level of consumer protection.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2006	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32006R1925	
EC	286	Regulation on natural mineral water (Directive 2009/54/EC)	It regulates the marketing and exploitation of natural mineral waters. Certain provisions of this Directive are also applicable to spring waters such as the microbiological requirements and labelling requirements.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2009	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/labelling_nutrition/mineral_waters_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32009L0054
EC	287	Regulation (EU) No 609/2013 on food intended for infants and young children, food for special medical purposes, and total diet replacement for weight control	aims to protect specific vulnerable groups of consumers by regulating the content and marketing of food products specifically created for and marketed to them.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2013	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/labelling_nutrition/special_groups_food_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32013R0609
EC	288	Requirements for the provision of information to consumers on the absence or reduced presence of gluten in food (Commission Implementing	The regulation defines statements on the absence or reduced presence of gluten in food that are allowed to be made and conditions ("gluten-free" and "very low gluten"	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2014	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/labelling_nutrition/special_groups_food/gluten_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32014R0828

Regulation (EU) No 828/2014																		
EC	289	Regulation (EC) No 1333/2008 on food additives	This Regulation lays down rules on food additives used in foods with a view to ensuring the effective functioning of the internal market whilst ensuring a high level of protection of human health and a high level of consumer protection.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/food_improvement_agents/additives/eu_rules_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32008R1333	
EC	290	Regulation (EC) No 1332/2008 on food enzymes	rules on food enzymes used in foods, with a view to ensuring the effective functioning of the internal market whilst ensuring a high level of protection of human health and a high level of consumer protection. It includes specific labelling requirements for food enzymes and food enzyme preparations.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/food_improvement_agents/enzymes/eu_rules_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32008R1332	
EC	291	Regulation (EC) No 1331/2008 establishing a common authorisation procedure for food additives, food enzymes and food flavourings	establishes the common authorisation procedure for food additives, food enzymes and food flavourings. It includes specific labelling requirements for food enzymes and food enzyme preparations	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/food_improvement_agents/enzymes/eu_rules_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32008R1331	
EC	292	Regulation (EC) No 1334/2008 on flavourings and certain food ingredients with flavouring properties for use in and on foods	lays down general requirements for safe use of flavourings and provides definitions for different types of flavourings. The Regulation sets out substances for which an evaluation and approval is required.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/food_improvement_agents/flavourings/eu_rules_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32008R1334	
EC	293	2009/32/EC on extraction solvents	Directive 2009/32/EC on the approximation of the laws of the Member States on extraction solvents used in the production of foodstuffs and food ingredients applies to extraction solvents used or intended for use in the production of foodstuffs or food ingredients either in the EU or imported into the EU.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2009	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/food_improvement_agents/extraction-solvents_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2009/32/2010-09-16	
EC	294	EU Guidelines for the prudent use of antimicrobials in human health	The guidelines aim to reduce inappropriate use and promote prudent use of antimicrobials in people.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Information measure	Consumers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2017	https://ec.europa.eu/health/a_mr/antimicrobial-resistance_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52017XC0701(01)	
EC	295	#KeepAntibioticsWorking	Information campaign on the responsible use of antibiotics	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Information measure	Consumers	EU	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control	0	0		https://antibiotic.ecdc.europa.eu/en/get-involved/social-media-2017/keepantibioticsworking		
EC	296	2004/478/EC concerning the adoption of a general plan for food/feed crisis management	Preparedness and management of crises related to food and feed safety aims to avoid or minimise the health and economic impact of possible future crises.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	1	0		https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/biosafety/crisis_preparedness_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32004D0478	
EC	297	Regulation (EC) No 853/2004 Rules on hygiene of foodstuffs	EU Rules regarding Food Hygiene cover all stages of the production, processing, distribution and placing on the market of food intended for human consumption.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers and the food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2004	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/biosafety/food_hygiene_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32004R0852	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32004R0853
EC	298	(EC) No 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs	Lays down food safety criteria for relevant foodborne bacteria, their toxins and metabolites in specific foods. These criteria define the acceptability of a product or a batch of food applicable to products placed on the market. In addition, process' hygiene criteria to indicate the	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Farmers and the food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2005	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/biosafety/food_hygiene/microbiological_criteria_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02005R2073-20140601	

			correct functioning of the production process are set.																			
EC	299	Requirements for the use of specific control methods for the control of salmonella in poultry (1177/2006)	This Regulation lays down certain rules for the use of antimicrobials and vaccines. Antimicrobials shall not be used as a specific method to control salmonella in poultry.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers and the food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2003	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/biosafety/food_borne_diseases/salmonella_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32006R1177					
EC	300	Commission Regulation (EC) No 798/2008 on restriction on import of live poultry and eggs	List of third countries, territories, zones or compartments from which poultry and poultry products may be imported into and transit through the Community and the veterinary certification requirements.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/biosafety/food_borne_diseases/salmonella_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32008R0798					
EC	301	2015/1375 laying down specific rules on official controls for Trichinella in meat	rules on official controls for Trichinella in meat	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2015	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/biosafety/food_borne_diseases/trichinella_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32015R1375					
EC	302	TSE Regulation (999/2001)	Regulation laying down rules for the prevention, control and eradication of certain transmissible spongiform encephalopathies. The purpose of the TSE legislation is to protect the health of consumers and animals and to control and eradicate TSEs.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2001	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/biosafety/food_borne_diseases/tse_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02001R0999-20150805					
EC	303	Directive 2003/99/EC on the monitoring of zoonoses and zoonotic agents	The purpose of this Directive is to ensure that zoonoses, zoonotic agents and related antimicrobial resistance are properly monitored, and that food-borne outbreaks receive proper epidemiological investigation, to enable the collection in the Community of the information necessary to evaluate relevant trends and sources.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2003	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/biosafety/food_borne_diseases/reports_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32003L0099					
EC	304	Regulation (EC) No 2160/2003 on the control of salmonella and other specified food-borne zoonotic agents	The purpose is to ensure that proper and effective measures are taken to detect and to control salmonella and other zoonotic agents at all relevant stages of production, processing and distribution, particularly at the level of primary production, including in feed, in order to reduce their prevalence and the risk they pose to public health.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2003	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/biosafety/food_borne_diseases_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02003R2160-20130701					
EC	305	Regulation on food irradiation	Regulation applied to the manufacture, marketing and importation of foods and food ingredients treated with ionising radiation. Irradiated food or one containing irradiated ingredients must be labelled.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Farmers and the food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1999	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/biosafety/irradiation/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:31999L0002	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:31999L0003				
EC	306	Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 on novel foods	This Regulation lays down rules for the placing of novel foods on the market within the Union. The purpose of this Regulation is to ensure the effective functioning of the internal market while providing a high level of protection of human health and consumers' interests.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers and the food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2015	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/novel_food/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32015R2283					
EC	307	Regulation on contaminant in food	The basic principles of EU legislation on contaminants in food are laid down in Council Regulation 315/93/EEC. Maximum levels for certain contaminants in food are set in Commission Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Farmers and the food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1993	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/chemical_safety/contaminants/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02006R1881-20150731	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:01993R0315-20090807				

EC	308	Council Directive 96/22/EC concerning the prohibition on the use in stockfarming of certain substances having a hormonal or thyrostatic action and of beta-agonists.	Banned the use of certain substances in food producing animals.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1996	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/chemical_safety/vet_med_residues/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:01996L0022-20081218	
EC	309	Council Directive 96/23/EC on measures to monitor certain substances and residues in live animals and animal products	Established a framework for residue monitoring in animals and animal products	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1996	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/chemical_safety/vet_med_residues/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:01996L0023-20130701	
EC	310	Regulation (EC) No 396/2005 on maximum residue levels of pesticides in or on food and feed of plant and animal origin	Established maximum residue levels for pesticides in food	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2005	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/chemical_safety/vet_med_residues/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32005R0396	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/max_residue_levels/eu_rules_en
EC	311	Commission Regulation (EU) No 37/2010 on pharmacologically active substances and their classification regarding maximum residue limits in foodstuffs of animal origin	Established a list of MRLs for permitted substances	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2010	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/chemical_safety/vet_med_residues/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32010R0037	
EC	312	Regulation (EC) No 183/2005 laying down requirements for feed hygiene	This Regulation lays down: general rules on feed hygiene; conditions and arrangements ensuring traceability of feed; conditions and arrangements for registration and approval of establishments.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Input suppliers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2005	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/animal-feed/feed-hygiene_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02005R0183-20151112	
EC	313	Regulation (EC) No 767/2009 on the placing on the market and use of feed	The objective of this Regulation is to harmonise the conditions for the placing on the market and the use of feed, in order to ensure a high level of protection of public health, as well as to provide adequate information for users and consumers and to strengthen the effective functioning of the internal market.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Input suppliers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2009	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/animal-feed/feed-marketing_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02009R0767-20180101	
EC	314	Regulation (EC) No 1831/2003 on additives for use in animal nutrition	establish a Community procedure for authorising the placing on the market and use of feed additives and to lay down rules for the supervision and labelling of feed additives and premixtures in order to provide the basis for the assurance of a high level of protection of human health, animal health and welfare.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Input suppliers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2003	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/animal-feed/feed-additives/eu-rules_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32003R1831	
EC	315	Council Directive 90/167/EEC laying down the conditions governing the preparation, placing on the market and use of medicated feedingsstuffs	conditions other than those of animal health, governing the preparation, placing on the market and use of medicated feedingsstuffs within the Community.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Input suppliers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1990	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/animal-feed/medicated-feed_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31990L0167	
EC	316	Directive 2002/32/EC on undesirable substances in animal feed	regulations on undesirable substances in animal feed, e.g. any substance or product, with the exception of pathogenic agents, present in and/or on the product intended for animal feed which presents a potential danger to human health, animal health or the environment or do not adversely affect livestock production.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Input suppliers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2002	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/animal-feed/undesirable-substances_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02002L0032-20150227	
EC	317	Regulation (EC) No 1829/2003 on genetically modified food and feed	provide the basis for ensuring a high level of protection of human life and health, animal health and welfare, environment and consumer interests in relation to genetically modified food and feed, whilst ensuring the effective functioning of the internal market.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2003	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/animal-feed/genetically-modified-feed_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02003R1829-20080410	

EC	318	Regulation (EC) No 1830/2003 concerning the traceability and labelling of GMOs and the traceability of food and feed products produced from GMOs	the objectives of facilitating accurate labelling, monitoring the effects on the environment and, where appropriate, on health, and the implementation of the appropriate risk management measures including, if necessary, withdrawal of products.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2003	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/animal-feed/genetically-modified-feed_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02003R1830-20081211	
EC	319	Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009 laying down health rules as regards animal by-products and derived products not intended for human consumption	This Regulation lays down public health and animal health rules for animal by-products and derived products, in order to prevent and minimise risks to public and animal health arising from those products, and in particular to protect the safety of the food and feed chain.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2009	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/animal-by-products/eu-rules_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32009R1069	
EC	320	Import, transit and export of animal by-products and of derived products (142/2011 Art. 25)	Regulation on import, transit and export of animal by-products and of derived products.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0		https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/animal-by-products/approved-establishments_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02011R0142-20150223	
EC	321	Regulation EC/178/2002 General Food Law Regulation	lays down general principles, requirements and procedures that underpin decision making in matters of food and feed safety, covering all stages of food and feed production and distribution. It also sets up an independent agency responsible for scientific advice and support, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA).	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2002	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/general_food_law_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32002R0178	
EC	322	Animal Health Law Regulation (EC) No 1760/2000 establishing a system for the identification and registration of bovine animals and regarding the labelling of beef and beef products	Regulation (EU) 2016/429 on transmissible animal diseases. This Regulation lays down rules for the prevention and control of animal diseases which are transmissible to animals or to humans.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2016	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/health/regulation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2016.084.01.0001.01.EN&toc=OJ.L:2016:084:TOC	
EC	323	Council Directive 2009/156/EC on animal health conditions governing the movement and importation from third countries of equidae	Each Member State shall establish a system for the identification and registration of bovine animals	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2000	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/identification/bovine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32000R1760	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32003R1082
EC	324	Commission Regulation (EC) No 504/2008 on methods for the identification of equidae	This Directive lays down animal health conditions for the movement between Member States and importation from third countries of live equidae.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2009	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/identification/equine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02009L0156-20130701	
EC	325	Council Directive 2008/71/EC on the identification and registration of pigs	This Regulation lays down rules on the identification of equidae born in the Community or released for free circulation in the Community	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/identification/equine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02008R0504-20141121	
EC	326	Council Regulation (EC) No 21/2004 establishing a system for the identification and registration of ovine and caprine animals	This Directive sets out the minimum requirements for the identification and registration of pigs	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/identification/porcine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32008L0071	
EC	327	Council Regulation (EC) No 21/2004 establishing a system for the identification and registration of ovine and caprine animals	Each Member State shall establish a system for the identification and registration of ovine and caprine animals in accordance with the provisions of this Regulation.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2004	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/identification/ovine_caprine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02004R0021-20130701	

EC	328	TRACES: TRAdE Control and Expert System	integrated computerised veterinary system	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0		https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/traces/legal-basis_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32003D0623
EC	329	Council Directive 98/58/EC concerning the protection of animals kept for farming purposes	This Directive lays down minimum standards for the protection of animals bred or kept for farming purposes.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	NA	NA	Society at large	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1998	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/welfare_en	
EC	330	European Union Reference Centre for Animal Welfare	European Union Reference Centre for Animal Welfare is responsible for supporting horizontal activities of the Commission and of the Member States in the area of welfare requirements for animals	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	NA	NA	Society at large	Delivery of services	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2018	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/welfare/eu-ref-centre_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2018.063.01.0013.01.EN&toc=OJ.L:2018:063:TOC
EC	331	Council Directive 2008/120/EC laying down minimum standards for the protection of pigs	This Directive lays down the minimum standards for the protection of pigs confined for rearing and fattening.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	NA	NA	Society at large	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/welfare/practice/farm/pigs_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32008L0120
EC	332	Council Directive 2008/119/EC laying down minimum standards for the protection of calves	This Directive lays down the minimum standards for the protection of calves confined for rearing and fattening.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	NA	NA	Society at large	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/welfare/practice/farm/calves_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32008L0119
EC	333	Council Directive 2007/43/EC laying down minimum rules for the protection of chickens kept for meat production	This Directive sets down minimum rules for the protection of chickens kept for meat production. It aims to reduce the overcrowding of chicken holdings by setting a maximum stocking density and ensure better animal welfare by specifying requirements such as lighting, litter, feeding, and ventilation.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	NA	NA	Society at large	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2007	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/welfare/practice/farm/broilers_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32007L0043
EC	334	Council Directive 1999/74/EC laying down minimum standards for the protection of laying hens	This Directive lays down minimum standards for the protection of laying hens.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Society at large	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1999	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/welfare/practice/farm/laying_hens_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1435151498494&uri=CELEX:31999L0074
EC	335	Council Regulation (EC) No 1/2005 on the protection of animals during transport and related operations	It lays down efficient monitoring tools and stricter rules for the transport and for the specific checks to be carried out by officials. No person shall transport animals or cause animals to be transported in a way likely to cause injury or undue suffering to them.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Society at large	Regulation	Logistic sector	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2005	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/welfare/practice/transport_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32005R0001
EC	336	Council Regulation (EC) No 1099/2009 on the protection of animals at the time of killing	This Regulation lays down rules for the killing of animals bred or kept for the production of food, wool, skin, fur or other products as well as the killing of animals for the purpose of depopulation and for related operations.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	NA	NA	Society at large	Regulation	Farmers and the food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2009	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/welfare/practice/slaughter_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32009R1099
EC	337	Council Directive 2006/88/EC on animal health requirements for aquaculture animals and products thereof, and on the prevention and control of certain diseases in aquatic animals	minimum control measures in the event of a suspicion or outbreak of certain diseases in aquatic animals; minimum preventive measures; the animal health requirements to be applied for the placing on the market and the imports of aquaculture animals and products thereof.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2006	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/aquaculture_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32006L0088

EC	338	Council Directive 2001/110/EC relating to honey	Definition of "honey" and indication on the label	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Labelling measure	Farmers and the food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2001	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/bees/veterinary_issues_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32001L0110
EC	339	Regulation (EC) No 470/2009 laying down Community procedures for the establishment of residue limits of pharmacologically active substances in foodstuffs of animal origin	Veterinary medicinal products intended for use in food producing animals have to be scientifically evaluated according to human food safety requirements		Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0		https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/bees/veterinary_issues_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1531228449690&uri=CELEX:52015DC0056
EC	340	Commission Regulation (EU) No 206/2010 concerning the introduction into the European Union of certain animals and fresh meat	This Directive lays down lists of third countries, territories or parts thereof authorised for the introduction into the European Union of certain animals and fresh meat and the veterinary certification requirements.		Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2010	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/bees/trade_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1531228608926&uri=CELEX:32010R0206
EC	341	Spot Checks - Veterinary and zootechnical checks applicable in intra-Community trade in certain live animals and products with a view to the completion of the internal market (90/425/EEC)	Because there are no border controls for movements between Member States, non-discriminatory spot checks are carried out en-route and at the destination, to ensure that consignments are in compliance with the guarantees provided by the health certificate.		Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1990	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/other_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:01990L0425-20021119
EC	342	Animal health requirements for intra-Union trade in bovine and porcine animals	The Directive lays down precise rules to be respected during the movement of bovine and porcine animals from the holding of origin to the final destination. In addition, there are rules regarding the health status in relation to animal diseases		Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Logistic sector	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1964	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/bovine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1531230482744&uri=CELEX:31964L0432
EC	343	Council Directive 2004/68/EC laying down animal health rules for the importation into and transit through the Community of certain live ungulate animals	This Directive lays down the animal health requirements for the importation into and transit through the Community of live ungulates, describes the animal health principles on which importation is based, and the requirements to be fulfilled by a non-EU country to be authorised to export bovine animals.		Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0		https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/bovine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32004L0068
EC	344	Border Inspection Post (BIP)	Live animals entering the Union are inspected at a Border Inspection Post (BIP) (as listed in Commission Decision 2009/821/EC) where Member States' official veterinarians ensure they fulfil all the requirements provided for in the EU legislation.		Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2009	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/bovine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32009D0821 https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32004R0136
EC	345	Common Veterinary Entry Document (CVED)	Importers must complete relevant sections of a Common Veterinary Entry Document (CVED) prior to entry into the EU. The CVED provides a standardised format for documentation relating to declaration and checks for live animals arriving into the Union.		Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2004	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/bovine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32004R0282
EC	346	Animal health conditions and veterinary certification for imports of equidae	Regulations on animal health conditions and veterinary certification for imports of equidae.		Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1993	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/equine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31993D0196 https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31993D0197
EC	347	Animal health conditions governing intra-Community trade in ovine and caprine animals (91/68/EEC)	This Directive defines the animal health conditions governing intra-Community trade in ovine and caprine animals.		Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Logistic sector	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1991	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/ovine_caprine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:01991L0068-20131220

EC	348	Council Directive 2003/50/EC regarding reinforcement of controls on movements of ovine and caprine animals	to reinforce the controls on movements of ovine and caprine animals between the Member States.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Logistic sector	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2003	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/ovine_caprine_en	http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32003L0050
EC	349	Council Directive 2009/158/EC on animal health conditions governing intra-Community trade in, and imports from third countries of, poultry and hatching eggs	The Directive lays down precise rules to be respected during the production of live poultry and hatching eggs, and movement between Members States.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2009	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/poultry_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02009L0158-20110406
EC	350	Council Directive 2005/94/EC on Community measures for the control of avian influenza	Specific control measures are laid down for Avian influenza. In the event of a suspicion and subsequent confirmation of the disease these measures must be followed with the aim to eradicate the outbreak.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2005	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/live_animals/poultry_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32005L0094
EC	351	Commission Regulation (EC) No 1251/2008 regarding conditions and certification requirements for the placing on the market and the import into the Community of aquaculture animals and products thereof	Rules governing trade and import of aquaculture products from non-EU countries. Animal health certification requirements for the placing on the market and and certification requirements for imports into the Community, and transit therein, including storage during transit of aquaculture products.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/animalproducts/aquaculture_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32008R1251
EC	352	Council Directive 2002/99/EC laying down the animal health rules governing the production, processing, distribution and introduction of products of animal origin for human consumption	This Directive lays down the general animal health rules governing all stages of the production, processing and distribution within the Community and the introduction from third countries of products of animal origin and products obtained therefrom intended for human consumption.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2002	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/animalproducts/freshmeat_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32002L0099
EC	353	Regulation (EC) No 854/2004 laying down specific rules for the organisation of official controls on products of animal origin intended for human consumption	This Regulation lays down specific rules for the organisation of official controls on products of animal origin.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2004	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/animalproducts/freshmeat_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32004R0854
EC	354	2000/572/EC laying down animal and public health conditions and veterinary certification for imports of minced meat and meat preparations from third countries	This Decision lays down the animal and public health conditions and veterinary certification for the importation of minced meat and meat preparations.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2000	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/animalproducts/freshmeat_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32000D0572
EC	355	(EC) No 119/2009 laying down a list of third countries or parts thereof, for imports into, or transit through, the Community of meat of wild leporidae, of certain wild land mammals and of farmed rabbits and the veterinary certification requirements	List of third countries or parts thereof, for imports into, or transit through, the Community of meat of wild leporidae, of certain wild land mammals and of farmed rabbits and the veterinary certification requirements	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2009	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/animalproducts/game_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32009R0119

EC	356	2007/777/EC laying down the animal and public health conditions and model certificates for imports of certain meat products and treated stomachs, bladders and intestines for human consumption from third countries	This Decision lays down animal and public health rules for imports, transit and storage in the Community. Rules include the lists of third countries and parts thereof from which such imports are authorised and the model public and animal health certificates and rules on the origin and treatments required for imports	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2007	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/animalproducts/meatproducts_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32007D0777	
EC	357	(EU) No 605/2010 laying down animal and public health and veterinary certification conditions for the introduction into the European Union of raw milk, dairy products, colostrum and colostrum-based products intended for human consumption	public and animal health conditions and certification requirements for the introduction into the European Union of consignments of raw milk, dairy products, colostrum and colostrum-based products; the list of third countries from which the introduction into the European Union of such consignments is authorised.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2010	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/animalproducts/milk_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02010R0605-20140326	
EC	358	Animal Breeding Regulation	(EU) 2016/1012 provides a single legal framework for the rules applicable to the breeding, trade and entry into the Union of breeding animals of the bovine, porcine, ovine, caprine and equine species and their germinal products	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2016	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/zootechnics/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32016R1012	
EC	359	(EU) 2017/625 - Official Controls Regulation	lays down rules for the performance of official controls and other official activities by the competent authorities of the Member States. It concerns official controls and other official activities performed to ensure the application of food and feed law, rules on animal health and welfare, plant health and plant protection products	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2017	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/zootechnics/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32017R0625	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/official_controls/legislation_en
EC	360	Animal health requirements applicable to intra-Community trade in and imports of deep-frozen semen of domestic animals of the bovine species (88/407/EEC)	This Directive lays down the animal health conditions applicable to intra-Community trade in and imports from third countries of semen of domestic animals of the bovine species.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1988	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/semen/bovine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32003L0043	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:01988L0407-20111101
EC	361	Imports into the Union of semen of domestic animals of the bovine species (2011/630/EU)	This Decision lays down a list of third countries or parts thereof from which Members States shall authorise imports into the Union of semen of domestic animals of the bovine species (semen).It also lays down certification requirements for the imports of semen into the Union.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2011	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/semen/bovine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02011D0630-20150409	
EC	362	Animal health conditions governing intra-Community trade in and importation from third countries of embryos of domestic animals of the bovine species (89/556/EEC)	The general animal health conditions governing intra-Union trade in and imports into the European Union of embryos of domestic animals of the bovine species	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1989	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/semen/bovine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:01989L0556-20080903	
EC	363	Animal health and veterinary certification requirements for imports into the Community of bovine embryos (2006/168/EC)	lays down the animal health conditions and veterinary certification for imports of bovine embryos from third countries. It contains a list of third countries from which Member States authorise imports of embryos of domestic animals of the bovine species.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2006	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/semen/bovine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02006D0168-20130801	
EC	364	Council Directive 92/65/EEC laying down animal health requirements governing trade in and imports into the Community of animals, semen, ova and embryos not subject to animal	This Directive lays down the animal health requirements governing trade in and imports into the Community of animals, semen, ova and embryos not subject to the animal health requirements	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1992	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/semen/equine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:01992L0065-20141229	

other health requirements																		
EC	365	Model health certificates for trade within the Union in semen, ova and embryos of animals of the equine, ovine and caprine species and in ova and embryos of animals of the porcine species (2010/470/EU)	This Decision lays down model health certificates for trade within the Union in semen, ova and embryos of animals of the equine species; semen, ova and embryos of animals of the ovine and caprine species; ova and embryos of animals of the porcine species.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2010	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/semen/equine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02010D0470-20150224	
EC	366	List of third countries and parts of territory thereof from which Member States authorise imports of live equidae and semen, ova and embryos of the equine species (2004/211/EC)	This Decision establishes a list of third countries, or parts thereof where regionalisation applies, from which Member States authorise the importation of equidae and semen, ova and embryos thereof, and indicates the other conditions applicable to such imports.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2004	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/semen/equine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02004D0211-20150626	
EC	367	Imports of semen, ova and embryos of animals of the ovine and caprine species into the Union (2010/472/EU)	lays down the lists of third countries from which Member States authorise imports of semen, ova and embryos of the ovine and caprine species. model health certificates for imports of ovine and caprine semen, ova and embryos from authorised third countries	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2010	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/semen/ovine_caprine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02010D0472-20150101	
EC	368	Animal health requirements applicable to intra-Community trade in and imports of semen of domestic animals of the porcine species (90/429/EEC)	This Directive lays down the animal health conditions applicable to intra-Community trade in and imports from third countries of semen of domestic animals of the porcine species.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1990	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/semen/porcine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:01990L0429-20120601	
EC	369	2012/137/EU on imports into the Union of semen of domestic animals of the porcine species	This Decision lays down a list of third countries or parts thereof from which Member States shall authorise imports into the Union of semen of domestic animals of the porcine species. It also lays down certification requirements for imports of semen into the Union.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2012	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/semen/porcine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32012D0137	
EC	370	91/496/EEC laying down the principles governing the organization of veterinary checks on animals entering the Community from third countries	Veterinary checks in respect of animals from third countries entering the Community shall be carried out by the Member States in accordance with this Directive.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1991	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/vet-border-control/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31991L0496	
EC	371	97/78/EC laying down the principles governing the organisation of veterinary checks on products entering the Community from third countries	principles governing the organisation of veterinary checks on products entering the Community from third countries	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1997	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/vet-border-control/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31997L0078	
EC	372	882/2004 on official controls performed to ensure the verification of compliance with feed and food law, animal health and animal welfare rules	This Regulation lays down general rules for the performance of official controls to verify compliance. It aims to prevent or eliminate risks which may arise for human beings and animals, or reduce these risks to an acceptable level; guarantee fair practices as regards trade in food and feed; ensure protection of consumers' interests	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2004	https://ec.europa.eu/food/animals/vet-border-control/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32004R0882	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/official_controls/legislation_en
EC	373	2001/18/EC on the deliberate release into the environment of genetically modified organisms	Member States shall, in accordance with the precautionary principle, ensure that all appropriate measures are taken to avoid adverse effects on human health and the environment which might arise from the deliberate release or the placing on the market of GMOs.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2001	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/gmo/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32001L0018	

EC	374	2015/412 regarding the possibility for the Member States to restrict or prohibit the cultivation of genetically modified organisms (GMOs) in their territory	Member States in which GMOs are cultivated shall take appropriate measures in border areas of their territory with the aim of avoiding possible cross-border contamination into neighbouring Member States in which the cultivation of those GMOs is prohibited, unless such measures are unnecessary in the light of particular geographical conditions.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2015	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/gmo/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32015L0412
EC	375	2009/41/EC on the contained use of genetically modified micro-organisms	This Directive lays down common measures for the contained use of genetically modified micro-organisms with a view to protecting human health and the environment.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2009	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/gmo/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32009L0041
EC	376	2018/350 regarding the environmental risk assessment of genetically modified organisms	This measure brings the requirements on ERA up to date with developments in scientific knowledge and technical progress, while building on the EFSA Guidance Document for the ERA of plants. Member States shall bring into force the laws, regulations and administrative provisions necessary to comply with this Directive	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2018	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/gmo/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018L0350
EC	377	GM-free labelling	There exist "GM-free labels" pointing out that, in addition to what is laid down by the EU legislation on GMOs, specific measures have been taken on a voluntary basis to strictly exclude the presence or the use of GMOs in some food or feed products.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0		https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/gmo/traceability_labelling_en	
EC	378	619/2011 laying down the methods of sampling and analysis for the official control of feed as regards presence of genetically modified material for which an authorisation procedure is pending or the authorisation of which has expired	A 'technical zero' for GM presence in feed is set up at the level of 0.1%, which is the lowest level where results are satisfactorily reproducible between official laboratories. This 'technical zero' is referred as the Minimum Required Performance Limit	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2011	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/gmo/post_authorisation/technical_zero_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32011R0619
EC	379	1946/2003 on transboundary movements of genetically modified organisms	The exporter shall ensure notification to the competent authority of import prior to the first intentional transboundary movement of a GMO intended for deliberate release into the environment	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2003	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/gmo/transboundary_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32003R1946
EC	380	2000/29/EC on protective measures against the introduction into the Community of organisms harmful to plants or plant products and against their spread within the Community	Measures aim to protect crops, fruits, vegetables, flowers, ornamentals and forests from harmful pests and diseases (harmful organisms) by preventing their introduction into the EU or their spread within the EU.	Reduced Environmental impact	Plant health	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Farmers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2000	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/plant_health_biosecurity_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32000L0029
EC	381	2016/2031 on protective measures against pests of plants - Plant Health Law	This Regulation establishes rules to determine the phytosanitary risks posed by any species, strain or biotype of pathogenic agents, animals or parasitic plants injurious to plants or plant products ('pests') and measures to reduce those risks to an acceptable level.	Reduced Environmental impact	Plant health	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Farmers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2016	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/plant_health_biosecurity/legislation/new_eu_rules_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32016R2031
EC	382	Emergency control measures for plant health	Emergency control measures for plant health.	Reduced Environmental impact	Plant health	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Farmers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0		https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/plant_health_biosecurity/legislation/emergency_measures_en	

EC	383	Trade in plants and plant products within the EU (92/90/EEC)	Establishing obligations to which producers and importers of plants, plant products or other objects are subject and establishing details for their registration.	Reduced Environmental impact	Plant health	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Farmers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1992	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/plant_health_biosafety/trade_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31992L0090
EC	384	EUROPHYT	The main objective is to help to protect the territory of the EU from the introduction and spread of new pests and plant diseases. Web-based network and database that connect Plant Health Authorities of the EU Member States and Switzerland, the European Food Safety Authority and DG Santé.	Reduced Environmental impact	Plant health	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Farmers	Delivery of services	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0		https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/plant_health_biosafety/europhyt/network_en	
EC	385	2009/128/EC establishing a framework for Community action to achieve the sustainable use of pesticides	The framework establishes a framework to achieve a sustainable use of pesticides by reducing the risks and impacts of pesticide use on human health and the environment and promoting the use of integrated pest management and of alternative approaches or techniques, such as non-chemical alternatives to pesticides.	Reduced Environmental impact	Climate	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	Farmers	Regulation	Input suppliers	EU	EC - DG Sante	1	0	2009	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/pesticides/sustainable_use_pesticides_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:02009L0128-20091125
EC	386	No 2100/94 on Community plant variety rights	A system of Community plant variety rights is hereby established as the sole and exclusive form of Community industrial property rights for plant varieties.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Farmers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	1994	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/plant_property_rights/legislation_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:31994R2100
EC	387	2002/54/EC on the marketing of beet seed	Seed and propagating material are marketed in: Different marketing categories; Homogenous lots where lots are identified for traceability reasons; Specific requirements for packaging, sealing, labelling and documentation apply.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Farmers	Regulation	Input suppliers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2002	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/plant_propagation_material/legislation/eu_marketing_requirements_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32002L0054
EC	388	2002/57/EC on the marketing of seed of oil and fibre plants	This Directive shall apply to the production with a view to marketing, and to the marketing within the Community, of seed of oil and fibre plants intended for agricultural production but not for ornamental purposes. It shall not apply to seed of oil and fibre plants which is shown to be intended for export to third countries.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Farmers	Regulation	Input suppliers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2002	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/plant_propagation_material/legislation/eu_marketing_requirements_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32002L0057
EC	389	2002/56/EC on the marketing of seed potatoes	This Directive shall apply to the production with a view to marketing, and to the marketing, of seed potatoes within the Community.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Farmers	Regulation	Input suppliers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2002	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/plant_propagation_material/legislation/eu_marketing_requirements_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32002L0056
EC	390	2008/90/EC on the marketing of fruit plant propagating material and fruit plants intended for fruit production	This Directive shall apply to the marketing of fruit plant propagating material and fruit plants intended for fruit production within the Community.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Farmers	Regulation	Input suppliers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/plant_propagation_material/legislation/eu_marketing_requirements_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32008L0090
EC	391	2002/55/EC on the marketing of vegetable seed	This Directive shall apply to the production with a view to marketing, and to the marketing, of vegetable seed within the Community.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Farmers	Regulation	Input suppliers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2002	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/plant_propagation_material/legislation/eu_marketing_requirements_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32002L0055
EC	392	2008/72/EC on the marketing of vegetable propagating and planting material, other than seed	This Directive shall apply to the marketing of vegetable propagating and planting materials, other than seeds, within the Community.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Farmers	Regulation	Input suppliers	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/plant_propagation_material/legislation/eu_marketing_requirements_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32008L0072

EC	393	2003/17/EC on the equivalence of field inspections carried out in third countries on seed-producing crops and on the equivalence of seed produced in third countries	Non-EU countries seeking to export to the EU must meet the same criteria for seed characteristics, examination, identification, marking, control and packaging as seed harvested and controlled in the EU.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Farmers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2003	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/plant_propagation_material/equivalence_requirements_non-eu_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32003D0017	
EC	394	Council Directive 2002/53/EC on the common catalogue of varieties of agricultural plant species	Each Member State shall establish one or more catalogues of the varieties officially accepted for certification and marketing in its territory. Any person may consult the catalogues.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Farmers	Delivery of services	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2003	https://ec.europa.eu/food/plant/plant_propagation_material/plant_variety_catalogues_databases_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32002L0053	
EC	395	Better Training for Safer Food	Commission initiative aimed at organising a Community (EU) training strategy in the areas of food law, feed law, animal health and animal welfare rules, as well as plant health rules.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Education measure	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2006	https://ec.europa.eu/food/safety/btsf_en#Legal	http://ec.europa.eu/chafea/food/training_courses.html	http://ec.europa.eu/chafea/food/about.html
EC	396	Third Health Programme	funding instrument to support cooperation among EU countries and underpin and develop EU health activities	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	R&I economic	Public Authorities	EU	Consumers, Health, Agriculture and Food Executive Agency (Chafea)	1	0	2014-2020	http://ec.europa.eu/chafea/health/index.html	https://ec.europa.eu/health/funding/programme_en	https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls_en
EC	397	652/2014 laying down provisions for the management of expenditure relating to the food chain, animal health and animal welfare, and relating to plant health and plant reproductive material	contributing to a high level of health for humans, animals and plants along the food chain by preventing and eradicating diseases and pests and by ensuring a high level of protection for consumers and the environment, while enhancing the competitiveness of the Union food and feed industry and favouring the creation of jobs;	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Sante	0	0	2014	https://ec.europa.eu/food/funding_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1531468878124&uri=CELEX:32014R0652	
EC	398	2015/104 fixing the fishing opportunities for certain fish stocks and groups of fish stocks, applicable in Union waters and, for Union vessels, in certain non-Union waters	Pelagic trawling ban until the end of April 2015. The ban protected the stock from being targeted when at its most vulnerable – when the fish is coming together in shoals during the spawning season to reproduce. It applied to the Channel, Celtic Sea, Irish Sea and southern North Sea.	Reduced Environmental impact	Biodiversity	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2015	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/fishing_rules/sea-bass_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2015.022.01.0001.01.EN.G	
EC	399	2015/960 monthly catch limit and closed area	The EU set catch limits for particular fishing gears in order to protect sea bass.	Reduced Environmental impact	Biodiversity	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2015	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/fishing_rules/sea-bass_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2015.157.01.0001.01.EN.G	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/sites/fisheries/files/docs/body/2015-06-19-seabass-facts_en.pdf
EC	400	2015/1316 regarding the minimum conservation reference size for sea bass	The EU increased the minimum size for northern sea bass from 36 to 42 cm. This will further improve the protection of this valuable stock and give it more chances to reproduce young fish before it is caught.	Reduced Environmental impact	Biodiversity	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2015	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/fishing_rules/sea-bass_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1440763073745&uri=CELEX:32015R1316	
EC	401	2018/120 fixing for 2018 the fishing opportunities for certain fish stocks and groups of fish stocks, applicable in Union waters and, for Union fishing vessels, in certain non-Union waters	This Regulation fixes the fishing opportunities available in Union waters and to Union fishing vessels in certain non-Union waters, for certain fish stocks and groups of fish stocks. The fishing opportunities include catch limits and fishing effort limits.	Reduced Environmental impact	Biodiversity	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2018	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/fishing_rules/tacs_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32018R0120	
EC	402	2017/2360 fixing for 2018 the fishing opportunities for certain fish stocks and groups of fish stocks in the Black Sea.	2017/2360 fixing for 2018 the fishing opportunities for certain fish stocks and groups of fish stocks in the Black Sea.	Reduced Environmental impact	Biodiversity	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2018	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/fishing_rules/tacs_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32017R2360	

EC	403	2017/1970 fixing for 2018 the fishing opportunities for certain fish stocks and groups of fish stocks applicable in the Baltic Sea.	2017/1970 fixing for 2018 the fishing opportunities for certain fish stocks and groups of fish stocks applicable in the Baltic Sea.	Reduced Environmental impact	Biodiversity	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2018	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/fishing_rules/tacs_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32017R1970	
EC	404	CFP - Multi-annual plans	Almost all important stocks and fisheries are managed by means of a multiannual plan. The plans contain the goal for fish stock management, expressed in terms of fishing mortality and/or targeted stock size.	Reduced Environmental impact	Biodiversity	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0		https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/fishing_rules/multi_annual_plans_en		
EC	405	Measures for the conservation of fishery resources through technical measures for the protection of juveniles of marine organisms	Measures for the conservation of fishery resources through technical measures for the protection of juveniles of marine organisms and specifying conditions under which herring may be landed for industrial purposes other than direct human consumption.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2013	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/fishing_rules/technical_measures_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32013R0227	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32011R0579
EC	406	517/2008 laying down detailed rules as regards the determination of the mesh size and assessing the thickness of twine of fishing nets.	This Regulation lays down detailed rules for the implementation of Regulation (EC) No 850/98 as regards the determination of the mesh size and the assessment of the twine thickness of fishing nets by Community and national inspectors.	Reduced Environmental impact	Biodiversity	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0		https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/fishing_rules/technical_measures_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32008R0517	
EC	407	2017/1004 on the establishment of a Union framework for the collection, management and use of data in the fisheries sector and support for scientific advice regarding the common fisheries policy	This Regulation establishes rules on the collection, management and use of biological, environmental, technical and socioeconomic data in the fisheries sector.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	Fisheries	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2017	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/fishing_rules/data_collection_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32017R1004	
EC	408	CFP - Regulation (EU) No 1380/2013 on the Common Fisheries Policy	The CFP shall ensure that fishing and aquaculture activities are environmentally sustainable in the long-term and are managed in a way that is consistent with the objectives of achieving economic, social and employment benefits, and of contributing to the availability of food supplies.	Reduced Environmental impact	Biodiversity	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	1	0	2013	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=153148453406&uri=CELEX:32013R1380		
EC	409	1224/2009 establishing a Community control system for ensuring compliance with the rules of the common fisheries policy	This Regulation establishes a Community system for control, inspection and enforcement (Community control system) to ensure compliance with the rules of the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP).	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	Fisheries	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2009	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/control_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32009R1224	
EC	410	1005/2008 illegal, unreported and unregulated fishing (IUU) regulation	This Regulation establishes a Community system to prevent, deter and eliminate illegal, unreported and unregulated (IUU) fishing, each Member State shall take appropriate measures, in accordance with Community law, to ensure the effectiveness of that system	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/illegal_fishing_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1408984470270&uri=CELEX:02008R1005-20110309	
EC	411	304/2011 concerning use of alien and locally absent species in aquaculture	It provides a framework to ensure adequate protection of aquatic habitats from the risks associated with the use of non-native species in aquaculture. The objective is to optimise benefits associated with introductions and translocations while at the same time avoiding negative impacts on ecosystems and indigenous populations.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2011	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/aquaculture/alien-species_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32011R0304	
EC	412	1143/2014 on the prevention and management of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species	It provides for a set of measures to be taken across the EU in relation to invasive alien species included on a list of Invasive Alien Species of Union concern. Three distinct types of measures are envisaged: Prevention, Early detection and rapid eradication, Management.	Reduced Environmental impact	Animal welfare	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2014	http://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/invasivealien/index_en.htm	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1417443504720&uri=CELEX:32014R1143	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/aquaculture/alien-species_en

EC	413	2000/60/EC - Water Framework Directive (WFD)	It aims to establish a framework which: protects and enhances the status of aquatic ecosystems and environment, promotes sustainable water use, ensures the progressive reduction of pollution of groundwater, contributes to mitigating the effects of floods and droughts.	Reduced Environmental impact	Water and soil management	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Society at large	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2000	http://ec.europa.eu/environment/water/water-framework/index_en.html	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32000L0060	
EC	414	2008/56/EC - Marine Strategy Framework Directive	It establishes a framework within which Member States shall take the necessary measures to achieve or maintain good environmental status in the marine environment by the year 2020 at the latest. It is aimed at the protection of the marine environment and natural resources and creating a framework for the sustainable use of our marine waters.	Reduced Environmental impact	Water and soil management	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Society at large	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2008	http://ec.europa.eu/environment/marine/eu-coast-and-marine-policy/index_en.htm	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32008L0056	
EC	415	Recommendation on Integrated Coastal Zone Management	It defines the principles of sound coastal planning and management.	Reduced Environmental impact	Water and soil management	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Society at large	Information measure	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2002	http://ec.europa.eu/environment/marine/eu-coast-and-marine-policy/index_en.htm	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32002H0413	
EC	416	Integrated maritime policy	It seeks to provide a more coherent approach to maritime issues, with increased coordination between different policy areas. It focuses on issues that do not fall under a single sector-based policy (e.g. "blue growth"), but require the coordination of different sectors and actors (e.g. marine knowledge).	Reduced Environmental impact	Water and soil management	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Society at large	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2007	https://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/policy_en	https://ec.europa.eu/maritimeaffairs/policy_en	http://ec.europa.eu/environment/marine/eu-coast-and-marine-policy/index_en.htm
EC	417	Environmental Impact Assessment - EIA 2011/92/EU	The environmental impact assessment (EIA) process ensures that certain private and public projects that are likely to have significant effects on the environment are made subject to an assessment, prior to their authorisation.	Reduced Environmental impact	Multiple subgoals	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Implementing data-driven food and nutrition systems	Society at large	Regulation	Public Authorities	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2011	http://ec.europa.eu/environment/eia/eia-legalcontext.htm	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32011L0092	
EC	418	1379/2013 on the common organisation of the markets in fishery and aquaculture products (CMO regulation)	A common organisation of the markets in fishery and aquaculture products (CMO) is hereby established.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Market regulation	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2013	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/market_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1424680663995&uri=CELEX:32013R1379	
EC	419	1967/2006 Mediterranean Regulation - concerning management measures for the sustainable exploitation of fishery resources in the Mediterranean Sea	It contains two sets of rules: I) management measures, and II) obligations intended to protect sensitive habitats from the impact of fishing activities, to enlarge the network of marine protected areas and to prohibit destructive fishing practices, technical measures on the dimension, number and selectivity of the fishing gears allowed in the various fisheries.	Reduced Environmental impact	Biodiversity	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2006	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/mediterranean/rules_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1481546248599&uri=CELEX:32006R1967	
EC	420	508/2014 on the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund	The European Maritime and Fisheries Fund (EMFF) is established and contributes to the achievement of the following objectives: promoting competitive, environmentally sustainable, economically viable and socially responsible fisheries and aquaculture; fostering the implementation of the CFP; promoting a balanced and inclusive territorial development of fisheries and aquaculture areas; fostering the development and implementation of the Union's IMP in a manner complementary to cohesion policy and to the CFP.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2014-2020	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/emff_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2014.149.01.0001.01.EN.G	
EC	421	717/2014 de minimis aid in the fishery and aquaculture sector	State aid not exceeding 30 000 EUR per beneficiary over any period of three years. each Member State has to respect the maximum cumulative amount while granting aid to the undertakings active in the fishery and aquaculture sector.	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Aid and cooperation	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Income support	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2014	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/state_aid_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2014.190.01.0045.01.EN.G	

EC	422	1388/2014 Fisheries Block exemption regulation (FIBER) declaring certain categories of aid to undertakings active in the production, processing and marketing of fishery and aquaculture products	This Regulation shall apply to aid granted to small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) active in the production, processing or marketing of fishery and aquaculture products. aid granted to undertakings active in the production, processing or marketing of fishery and aquaculture products to make good the damage caused by natural disasters	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Aid and cooperation	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Fighting climate change through healthy soils	SMEs	SME support	SMEs	EU	EC - DG Mare	0	0	2014	https://ec.europa.eu/fisheries/cfp/state_aid_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/FR/TXT/?uri=urisrv%3AQLL...2014.369.01.0037.01.ENG	
EC	423	1293/2013 on the establishment of a Programme for the Environment and Climate Action (LIFE)	LIFE is the EU's financial instrument supporting environmental, nature conservation and climate action projects throughout the EU.	Reduced Environmental impact	Multiple subgoals	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	NA	Society at large	R&I economic	Research sector	EU	EC - DG Environment and DG Climate Action	1	0	2014-2020	http://ec.europa.eu/environment/life/index.htm	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=urisrv:OJ.L...2013.347.01.0185.01.EN.G	
EC	424	Guidelines on the application of the specific rules set out in Articles 169, 170 and 171 of the CMO Regulation for the olive oil, beef and veal and arable crops sectors	The Guidelines aim to support European farmers by clarifying how they can, under certain conditions, cooperate to jointly sell olive oil, beef and veal, and arable crops without breaching EU competition rules.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Fostering a sharing economy for food production and consumption	Consumers	Information measure	Farmers and the food industry	EU	EC - DG Competition	0	0	2015	http://ec.europa.eu/competition/sectors/agriculture/overview_en.html	http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_IP-15-6187_en.htm	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=urisrv:OJ.C...2015.431.01.0001.01.ENG&toc=OJ.C.2015:431:TOC
EC	425	Cohesion Fund - funding of environmental R&I	The Cohesion Fund is aimed at Member States whose Gross National Income (GNI) per inhabitant is less than 90 % of the EU average. It aims to reduce economic and social disparities and to promote sustainable development. Cohesion Fund can also support projects related to energy or transport, as long as they clearly benefit the environment in terms of energy efficiency, use of renewable energy, developing rail transport, supporting intermodality, strengthening public transport, etc.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Society at large	R&I economic	Research sector	EU	EC - DG Regio	1	0		http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/en/funding/cohesion-fund/	https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls_en	
EC	426	Energy Efficiency Directive (2012/27/EU)	A common framework of measures for the promotion of energy efficiency within the Union, in order to ensure the achievement of the Union's 2020 20% headline target on energy efficiency and to pave the way for further energy efficiency improvements beyond that date.	Reduced Environmental impact	Resource efficiency and waste management	CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	Tackling primary production waste streams	Society at large	Regulation	Food industry	EU	EC - DG Clima	0	0	2012	https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficiency-directive	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1399375464230&uri=CELEX:32012L0027	
EC	427	1287/2013 establishing a Programme for the Competitiveness of Enterprises and small and medium-sized enterprises (COSME)	COSME aims to make it easier for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) to access finance, helps businesses to access markets, supports entrepreneurs by strengthening entrepreneurship education, aims to reduce the administrative and regulatory burden on SMEs by creating a business-friendly environment	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	SMEs	R&I economic	SMEs	EU	EASME - Executive Agency for SMEs	0	0	2014-2020	https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes/cosme_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32013R1287	
EC	428	SME instrument (Horizon 2020)	Horizon 2020 funds high-potential innovation developed by SMEs through the SME instrument. The SME instrument offers Europe's brightest and boldest entrepreneurs the chance to step forward and request funding for breakthrough ideas with the potential to create entirely new markets or revolutionise existing ones.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	SMEs	R&I economic	SMEs	EU	EASME - Executive Agency for SMEs	0	0	2018-2020	https://ec.europa.eu/easme/en/sme-instrument	http://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/sme-instrument	
EC	429	Fast Track to Innovation (Horizon 2020)	fully-bottom-up innovation support programme promoting close-to-the-market innovation activities open to industry-driven consortia	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Consumers	R&I economic	Industry-based research	EU	EASME - Executive Agency for SMEs	1	0	2018-2020	https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/h2020-section/fast-track-innovation-pilot		
EC	430	Future and Emerging Technologies (FET) Open (Horizon 2020)	funds and supports early-stage, science and technology research by consortia exploring novel ideas for radically new future technologies that challenge current paradigms and venture into the unknown, with the aim to generate genuine societal or economic innovations.	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	Cross sectional (R&I oriented)	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Society at large	R&I economic	Research sector	EU	EC	1	0	2018-2020	https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/en/node/2932		

EC	431	834/2007 on organic production and labelling of organic products	It provides the basis for the sustainable development of organic production while ensuring the effective functioning of the internal market, guaranteeing fair competition, ensuring consumer confidence and protecting consumer interests. Common objectives concerning all stages of production, preparation and distribution of organic products and their control and the use of indications referring to organic production in labelling and advertising.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Labelling measure	Farmers and the food industry	EU	EC - DG Agri	1	0	2007	https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/organic/eu-policy/eu-legislation/brief-overview_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1531753383502&uri=CELEX:32007R0834
EC	432	1235/2008 as regards the arrangements for imports of organic products from third countries	Products that are produced and controlled in precisely the same manner as in the EU may have free access to the common market. Control bodies that intend to undertake such controls must apply to the EU Commission and be authorised by the Commission and the Member States for this purpose.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Border measure	Import/export companies	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/organic/eu-policy/eu-rules-on-production/legal-frame_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32008R1235
EC	433	889/2008 on organic production, labelling and control	all levels of plant and animal production are regulated, from the cultivation of land and keeping of animals to the processing and distribution of organic foods and their control.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	2008	https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/organic/eu-policy/eu-rules-on-production/legal-frame_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32008R0889
EC	434	710/2009 laying down detailed rules on organic aquaculture animal and seaweed production	conditions for the aquatic production environment and impacts on other species. It deals with the separation of organic and non-organic units and specifies animal welfare conditions. The rules specify that biodiversity should be respected, and does not allow the use of induced spawning by artificial hormones.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	CLIMATE smart and environmentally sustainable food systems	Demonstrate sustainable aquaculture for Europe	Fisheries	Regulation	Fisheries	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	2009	https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/organic/eu-policy/eu-rules-on-production/seaweed-and-aquaculture_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32009R0710
EC	435	203/2012 detailed rules on organic wine	The rules on organic wine-making introduce a technical definition of organic wine, which is consistent with the organic objective and principles as laid down in Council Regulation (EC 834/2007) Organic production. The regulation identifies oenological techniques and substances to be authorized for organic wine.	Viable and socially balanced EU agri-food business	Competitiveness	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Farmers and the food industry	EU	EC - DG Agri	0	0	2012	https://ec.europa.eu/agriculture/organic/eu-policy/eu-rules-on-production/wine_en	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1531754480338&uri=CELEX:32012R0203
EC	436	European Development Fund	The European Development Fund (EDF) is the EU's main instrument for providing development aid to African, Caribbean and Pacific (ACP) countries and to overseas countries and territories (OCTs).	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Aid and cooperation	NA	NA	Third countries	R&I economic	Third countries	Third countries	EC		0	0	https://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/funding/funding-instruments-programming/funding-instruments/european-development-fund_en	
EC	437	Fund for European Aid to the Most Deprived (FEAD)	Under the FEAD the assistance available for the most deprived persons of the Union includes, besides food aid, the supply of basic materials (e.g. clothing) and social inclusion as well.	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Equity and social cohesion in EU	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	NA	Consumers	Income support	Consumers	EU		0	0	2014-2020	http://ec.europa.eu/social/main.jsp?langId=en&catId=1089	https://www.eca.europa.eu/Lists/ECADocuments/BP_FEAD/BP_FEAD_EN.pdf
SCAR	438	Together for consumers	Voluntary commitments that the food producers can join, e.g. they will significantly reduce the salt, fat and/or caloric content of their products, they will advertise in a responsible way.	Balanced and sufficient diets for all EU citizens	Reduced economic and social burden of diet related diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Tackling malnutrition and obesity	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Food industry	Hungary	Hungarian Association of Food Manufacturers (ÉFOSZ)	0	1		http://egyuttafogyasztokert.hu/rolunk/	http://egyuttafogyasztokert.hu/vallalasaik/
SCAR	439	Codex Alimentarius Hungaricus	National food regulation that contains specific product descriptions.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Food and agricultural standards	Food industry	Hungary	Hungarian Ministry of Agriculture	0	0		http://elelmiszerlanc.korman.hu/magyar-elelmiszerkonyv	
SCAR	440	GMO free trademark	The GMO exemption mark may be used in a package, label, accompanying document or document made available to the final consumer when the requirements laid down in this Regulation are fulfilled	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Labelling measure	Food industry	Hungary	Hungarian government	0	0	2016	https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A1600061.FM&timeShift=fffff4&xtrefere=0000001.TXT	

EC	441	Directive 2008/98/EC on waste (Waste Framework Directive)	The Waste Framework Directive lays down some basic waste management principles: it requires that waste be managed without endangering human health and harming the environment, and in particular without risk to water, air, soil, plants or animals, without causing a nuisance through noise or odours, and without adversely affecting the countryside or places of special interest.	Reduced Environmental impact	Resource efficiency and waste management	CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	Tackling primary production waste streams	Society at large	Regulation	Food industry	EU	EC	0	0	2008	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32008L0098	http://ec.europa.eu/environment/waste/legislation/a.htm
EC	442	Commission Decision (EU) No 2014/955/EU on the list of waste	Commission Decision No 2014/955/EU amending Decision 2000/532/EC on the list of waste pursuant to Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council Text with EEA relevance	Reduced Environmental impact	Resource efficiency and waste management	CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	Tackling primary production waste streams	Society at large	Regulation	Food industry	EU	EC	0	0	2014	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32014D0955	
EC	443	Commission Regulation (EU) No 1357/2014 on waste	Commission Regulation (EU) No 1357/2014 of 18 December 2014 replacing Annex III to Directive 2008/98/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council on waste and repealing certain Directives	Reduced Environmental impact	Resource efficiency and waste management	CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	Tackling primary production waste streams	Society at large	Regulation	Food industry	EU	EC	0	0	2014	https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32014R1357	
	444	The General Food Regulations 2004	These Regulations provide for the enforcement of the following provisions of Regulation (EC) No. 178/2002 of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down the general principles and requirements of food law, establishing the European Food Safety Authority and laying down procedures in matters of food safety	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Food services	UK	UK	0	0	2004	http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2004/3279/pdfs/uksi_20043279_en.pdf	
	445	Circular concerning the provisions applicable to food banks and charities	This circular provides guidelines for the interpretation of the dates of expiry, traceability, labeling and freezing of foodstuffs. According to the circular, foodstuffs which have passed their 'best before' date can still be delivered to the consumer without any risk to public health. A non-limiting list of foods that can be used by food banks and charities is given in the Annex of the legislation, providing guidance assessing the longevity of food after their date of minimum durability reached or exceeded.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Food and agricultural standards	Belgium	Belgian Federal Agency for the Safety of the Food Chain (FASFC)	0	0	2013	http://www.favv-afsca.be/denreesalimentaires/circulaires/_documents/2013_08_02_BAetAC_FR.pdf	
	446	Royal Decree on the self, mandatory notification and traceability in the food chain	This law introduces provisions for traceability by obliging food business operators to keep more information about their incoming and outgoing products such as the nature of the product, the identification of the products, the quantity, the date of receipt and identification of the food business operator who delivers the product. The Royal Decree contains a derogation according to which the list of retailers/manufacturers who donated the foodstuff can serve as a record of incoming products and the list of food banks and charities can serve as a record for outgoing products. According to the Federal Agency for the Safety of the Food Chain (FASFC), this flexibility reduces the administrative burdens for food donation in Belgium.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Retailers	Belgium	Belgian Federal Agency for the Safety of the Food Chain (FASFC)	0	0	2005	http://www.ejustice.just.fgov.be/cgi_loi/change_lg.pl?language=fr&la=F&cn=2003111441&table_name=loi	
	447	German Regulation on hygiene requirements for the manufacture, treatment and supply of food	This Regulation addresses specific food hygiene issues and the transposition and implementation of European Community or European Union legislation in the field of food hygiene.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Retailers	Germany	Federal Ministry of Justice and Consumer Protection	0	0	2007	http://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/lmhv_2007/index.html	
	448	Legislative Decree n. 460	The Italian Legislative Decree of December 4, 1997, n. 460/115 recognizes a specific category of nonprofit charitable organizations: the O.N.L.U.S. (Organizzazioni non Lucrative di Utilità Sociale). The O.N.L.U.S. that recover and distribute surplus food benefit from a "special status" in comparison to all	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Equity and social cohesion in EU	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Ensuring sustainable and accessible food in cities	Consumers	Regulation	Food services	Italy	Italian government	0	0	1997	https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/atto/serie_generale/caricaDettaglioAtto/originario?atto.dataPubblicazioneGazzetta=2003-07-01&atto.codiceRedazionale=003G0174&normativi=false&tipoVigenza=originario&ti	

455	Law n. 46 on food chain and its official control	According to Art. 15, section 2, it is forbidden to donate food which is past its 'use by' and 'best before' date.	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Food services	Hungary	Hungarian government	0	0	2008	https://net.jogtar.hu/jogszabaly?docid=A0800046.TV
456	Act on Food Safety and Nutrition	This Act establishes: sanitary requirements applicable to food; hygienic conditions to be fulfilled by foodstuffs as well as materials and products intended to come into contact with food; properties of institutions responsible for the official control of food, pursuant to Regulation (EC) No. 882/2004; provisions on food inspection. According to the Polish Federation of Food Banks, this Act is transposed in a more rigid way than the actual EU legislation. Also, in the light of Art. 52, it is unacceptable to donate food after the expiry period ('use by') or minimum durability date ('best before').	Food safety	Reduced economic and social burden of food-borne diseases	NUTRITION for sustainable and healthy diets	Ensuring food authenticity and developing future safety systems	Consumers	Regulation	Food services	Poland	Polish government	0	0	2006	http://prawo.sejm.gov.pl/isap.nsf/download.xsp/WDU20101360914/T/D20100914L.pdf
457	Act n. 788/2010 (Grenelle 2)	The legislation sets objectives for the upcoming years regarding the quantity of bio-waste to be separated at the source and treated organically through anaerobic digestion. Almost half of the bio-waste generated by retailers in France is composed of food surplus which could have been redistributed to food banks and charities.	Reduced Environmental impact	Resource efficiency and waste management	CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	Achieving zero food waste	Society at large	Regulation	Retailers	France	French government	0	0	2010	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichTexte.do?cidTexte=JORFTEXT000022470434
458	Law n. 1720/2005	According to Article 238bis of the French General Tax Code, "bodies of general interest having a philanthropic, educational, scientific, social, humanitarian, sports, family or cultural objective qualify for a tax reduction equal to 60% of the amount of the donation, in the limit of 5 per thousand of sales, made by companies subject to corporate income tax".	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Equity and social cohesion in EU	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Ensuring sustainable and accessible food in cities	Consumers	Regulation	Food services	France	French government	0	0	2005	https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/affichCodeArticle.do?idArticle=LEGIARTI000006303974&cidTexte=LEGITEXT000006069577
459	Law No 166/2016 on the donation and distribution of food and pharmaceutical products (Gadda Law)	The Gadda Law creates a regulatory framework to comprehend the existing rules concerning fiscal incentives (L. 460/97, L. 133/99), civil liability (L. 155/03) and hygiene and food safety procedures (L. 147/13). It provides a set of definitions (e.g. food business operator, surplus food, food waste, donation, best before and use by dates, etc.); it fosters the donation of confiscated food products; it establishes a hierarchy for the use of products prioritizing the recovery for human consumption; it adds EUR 2 millions to the National Fund for the distribution of food products to the most deprived in order to purchase food.	Equitable outcomes and conditions	Equity and social cohesion in EU	INNOVATION and empowerment of communities	Ensuring sustainable and accessible food in cities	Consumers	Regulation	Food services	Italy	Italian government	0	0	2016	https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2016/08/30/16G00179/sg
460	Piano Nazionale di Prevenzione dei Rifiuti (PNPR)	The Program sets objectives to be reached by 2020: 5% reduction of urban waste per unit of GDP; 10% reduction of special hazardous waste per unit of GDP; 5% reduction of non-hazardous special waste per unit of GDP.	Reduced Environmental impact	Resource efficiency and waste management	CIRCULARITY and resource efficiency of food systems	Tackling primary production waste streams	Society at large	Food and agricultural standards (voluntary)	Food industry	Italy	Ministero dell'Ambiente e della Tutela del Territorio e del Mare	0	1	2013	https://www.minambiente.it/sites/default/files/archivio/comunicati/Programma%20nazionale%20prevenzione%20rifiuti.pdf